

Report and policy brief on the results of the integrated model-based assessment

MATS Deliverable 3.3

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Summary

For the assessment of tangible linkages between trade regimes, market dynamics and real-life impacts, MATS integrates qualitative and quantitative modelling with the analysis carried out for 15 case studies.

Three modelling techniques are used, one qualitative and two quantitative (one applied at the national level, and one focused on international trade dynamics). The use of three modelling techniques is required to assess trade policy frameworks and instruments (drivers), in terms of shaping demand, determining production practices and generating social and environmental impacts (at global, national and local level), measured using various SDGs.

Specifically, qualitative modelling (i.e., system maps) were created using a participatory, co-creation approach for CS2 on oats (EU, Finland), CS3 on dairy (EU, Finland), CS5 on poultry (Ghana), CS10 on beef (EU, Africa, South America), CS13 on milk (EU, Africa, America), CS14 on pork (Brazil), CS15 on olive oil (Tunisia). This offers a wide variety of applications across sectors and geographies. Each system map, also called Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is fully customized to the socio-economic and environmental context analysed and offers insights on the dynamic interrelations existing across indicators. This analysis offers information on the transformative potential of policy intervention for agricultural trade sustainability.

Quantitative models were also developed for selected case studies (CS3, CS5, CS13 and CS14). Different models were employed for these assessments, ranging from spatial analysis to assess impacts of land cover change on ecosystem service provisioning, to MS Excel-based Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA), to integrated systems models.

These assessments implemented at the sectoral, national or sub-national level are complemented by an international trade analysis, informed by the work carried out across case studies. This analysis was performed with a GCE model. This model, named GDynEP, is dynamic and recursive, in order to include capital accumulation and technological change over time. Different scenarios are created and compared to represent the economic and distributional impacts of alternative climate policy design, including (i) the unilateral implementation of a net zero emissions target by the European Union (EU) in line with the Fit-for-55 objectives, (ii) the introduction of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) as a compensatory measure for reducing carbon leakage and competitiveness loss of energy-intensive EU industries, and (iii) the possible multilateral implementation of a net zero carbon emissions target thanks to the adoption of climate clubs arriving at an ideal climate policy setting with a world-

based climate club, corresponding to an average 30% reduction of global emissions with respect to the reference case (Tagliapietra and Wolff, 2021). Scenarios are also differentiated according to the specific GHG aggregation used, comparing standard CGE results with only energy-based emissions with the new GDynEP version including all GHGs.

The key findings of the CGE analysis can be summarized as follows:

- A unilateral climate policy implemented by the EU might bring to a 60% carbon leakage effect by 2030 since the abatement effort by the EU are largely compensated by the increase in emissions by several regions driven by trade diversion effects and lower international energy prices.
- The introduction of a CBAM trade policy based on a carbon intensity measure compliant with WTO (World Trade Organization) rules applied to the rest of the world is not effective in reducing the carbon leakage effect since a large portion of the increased emissions is provoked by the augmented trade flows directed to non-EU regions.
- The combination of a unilateral EU carbon pricing and a CBAM trade policy might result in a reduction of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for the EU by -0.2% w.r.t. the carbon pricing alone. African regions experience mixed effects by 2030, with a GDP loss by -0.36% for energy exporters and a GDP gain by 0.10-0.12% for countries located in the Horn of Africa.
- There is a valuable improvement in global emissions reduction from the implementation of a trade policy agreement between the EU and African regions where African countries are excluded from the CBAM policy application and engaged into a domestic emissions abatement policy. An average -27% reduction in emission intensity is registered by 2030 in African regions, with peaks by -19% in rice production in South Africa or by -35% for livestock production in North African countries.
- The inclusion of all GHGs in the climate policy strategy and related carbon pricing mechanism significantly changes the economic and emissions impact related to different policies as agricultural productions and emission-intensive chemical industries strictly connected to the primary sector (including fertilizers and pesticides) are fully involved in the abatement policies.
- While distinguishing African regions that are also covered in several of the MATS case studies (incl. AFNorth, AFCentr and SouthAfrica), many African regions would contribute significantly to the reduction of GHGs when applying domestic measures for reduction in carbon intensity, while gaining in terms of GDP and export competitiveness towards the EU

market. Significantly, when all GHGs are included in policy scenarios, abatement efforts by African regions bring the largest positive impact on GDP of those agricultural intensive regions (AFNorth, AFWest, AFHorn). On the opposite, when only combustion-based CO₂ emissions are modelled, African energy exporters are those countries gaining the most from the removal of CBAM and the implementation of domestic abatement policies.

- All regions and sectors are affected by an increase in consumer prices when the introduction of low-carbon objectives is achieved only by carbon pricing. There is a large diversity in the impact on prices for different regions and sectors, with selected African regions as AFEnex, AFCentr and SouthAfrica strongly suffering from price increases in agricultural sectors that are key to increase food security issues with respect to rice, vegetables, and livestock activities.
- On the opposite, improvements in factor productivity associated to the introduction of sustainable agricultural practices also contribute to reducing consumer prices. The efficiency gains in the production process of primary goods combined with a reduction in domestic prices turns abatement efforts into an improvement in food security.
- Trade gains for selected African regions participating into the climate club with the EU are significantly high since the European market represents a large quota of African exports. The region benefiting the most from being included in the EU climate club is AFWest with an increase in the export share both on the EU market and on the rest of the world for all primary goods. Similar results are found for the AFCentr region, where export activities are improved especially in the rice and raw meat sectors.
- The combination of carbon neutral improvements with selected efficiency gains in input productivity for the agricultural sector in African regions on average is responsible for positive socio-economic impacts. Consumer prices are reduced and food security improved, GDP growth rate is sustained by efficiency gains and the participation into the EU climate club makes these regions more competitive in exports of primary goods in the EU and the global market. All these positive outcomes also constitute an effective strategy to reduce potential negative distributional impacts on households related to stringent climate policies, turning climate neutrality into a win-win solution also for developing regions.

The policy implication from these results is that the capacity of CBAM to prevent the risk of carbon leakage and support the EU's increased ambition on climate

mitigation, while ensuring WTO compatibility, is limited if foreign partners do not apply domestic carbon pricing mechanisms. On the opposite, in the case of the African regions considered in this study, domestic efforts in mitigation and the consequent exemption from CBAM application would generate both an improvement in export competitiveness towards the EU market and a reduction of carbon leakage by 6% in the case of fossil-based CO₂ emissions and by 21% when all GHGs are considered.

We therefore find that the EU carbon policy mechanisms, to meet the targets of the Fit-for-55 plan, should include both a CBAM and efforts in forming as many climate clubs as possible (with the goal to build a global commitment to carbon neutrality, originating from a stimulus towards decarbonization at country level).

Additionally, by sustaining technology transfer and the diffusion of best practices in agricultural production in less developed regions, the inclusion into a climate club could be complemented by ad hoc support instruments to make the carbon neutrality pathway also compatible with a more inclusive and equal development transition, resulting into typical win-win solution with environmental gains followed by positive well-being achievements.

In D3.3, the integrated modelling framework applies to seven case studies and its results provide guidance for assessing the impact of sustainable agricultural trade policy at local, national, regional and global level, across a range of social, economic and environmental indicators. The policy brief - integrated model-based simulation and assessment of linkages with agricultural market, trade and investment dynamics summarizes the insights emerging from these modelling assessments.

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List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
B	Balancing feedback loop
BAT	Best Available Technology
BAU	Business As Usual
BCA	Border Carbon Adjustment
BMP	Best Management Practice
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
CCR	Benefit-to-Cost Ratio
CEPII	Centre d'études prospectives et d'informations internationales
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
CLC	CORINE Land Cover
CLD	Causal Loop Diagram
CN	Curve Number
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CO ₂ e	Carbon dioxide equivalent
CS	Case Study
CSIR-STEPRI	CSIR-Science and Technology Policy Research Institute
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
EITE	Energy-Intensive Trade-Exposed
ET ₀	Average annual reference evapotranspiration
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro
EUREF	European Commission reference case
EV	Equivalent variation
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDynEP	GTAP-Dynamic Energy and Power
GECO	Global Economic and Climate Outlook
GEMPACK	General Equilibrium Modelling Package
GHC	Ghanian cedi
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GIS	Geographic Information System
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis Project
Ha	Hectare
HQ	Habitat Quality
ILO	International Labour Organisation
InVEST	Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs
IO	Input Output
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRR	Internal Rate of Return

KE	Knowledge Srl
Kg	Kilogram
Km	Kilometre
LULC	Land Use and Land Cover
MATS	Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable
MIN	Minimum function
MJ	Megajoule
NCO2	Non-CO2 GHG emissions
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
NPV	Net-Present Value
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PAWC	Plant Available Water Content
PV	Photovoltaic
R	Reinforcing feedback loop
RES	Renewable Electricity Sources
SAM	Social Accounting Matrix
SDG	Sustainability Development Goal
SSP	Shared Socio-Economic Pathway
ST	Systems Thinking
UH	University of Helsinki
UK	United Kingdom
UpM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
US	United States
USA	United States of America
USD	United States dollar
USLE	Universal Soil Loss Equation
WIOD	World Input-Output Database
WP	Work Package
WTO	World Trade Organisation
Yr	Year

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1 Introduction

The MATS project aims to expand and enhance the available knowledge on the relationships between agricultural markets, trade, investments, policy, environmental sustainability, and human well-being. It intends, through the improvement of the design, governance, and implementation of trade regimes and policies at the private sector, national, EU, African and global levels, to set a new benchmark in agricultural trade policy analysis to deliver novel solutions for the necessary sustainability transition.

This deliverable presents the integrated model-based simulation and assessment of linkages with agricultural market, trade and investment dynamics, performed in WP3, specifically in T3.3.

Three modelling approaches are used to generate estimates and forecasts of outcomes across sectors, economic actors, dimensions of development, over time and in space (on a map).

First, a participatory systems approach was used, starting with the co-creation of system maps, to identify key indicators, their interconnections, and dynamics of change in the system. This exercise was performed for 7 case studies (three were indicated in the project plan).

Second, customized quantitative, systems models were created for 4 case studies (three were indicated in the project plan). Different modelling approaches were employed, including spatial models (based on GIS maps), integrated Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) using MS Excel, and System Dynamics models using the software Vensim.

Third, a CGE model was used to explore trade dynamics between countries and regions, as well as instruments such as a carbon border adjustment and how these would impact trade dynamics.

The approach used and resulting insights are presented first for the qualitative modelling exercises, followed by the systems models, and finally by the CGE assessment.

2 System maps (Causal Loop Diagrams)

2.1 CS2 – Oats (EU, Finland)

The issue analysed is the intra-EU trade, resilience and social sustainability of oats production in Finland – with respect to social, environmental and economic dimensions - of oats production as part of the oats value chain in Finland and in Europe. The methodology used for the creation of the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is called Systems Thinking (see Text Box 1). A CLD is a graphical representation of variables and their interconnections, giving shape to the dynamics of a given system (see Text Box 2).

The CLD is presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2, and was created as a team effort (UH & KE), founded on co-creation (with a step by step, participatory approach). The core information comes from 11 interviews with oats value chain actors in Finland and Sweden, which took place between April and May 2022. This information has been processed together with secondary data (industry reports, sustainability reports, and a government report that examined the future of Finland’s retail sector) as part of a Master thesis project at the University of Helsinki, and provided the main input into the CLD developed here.

Several factors that stimulate, as well as constrain, the production of oats in Finland’s oats value chain were identified. These are underlying the presence of both reinforcing and balancing feedback loops in the system (value chain), or dynamics that stimulate or counter (oppose) change, as described as follows.

At the beginning of the creation of the CLD, we have analysed the dynamics that likely determine the profitability of oats production, processing and retailing, in the absence of trade. Investment is a key determinant of production and processing capacity, which allows for the generation of revenues, resulting in profits and hence in more investment. This circular relation represents a reinforcing feedback loop (R1 in the CLD), one that - when unconstrained - should result in the increase of profits and in the growth of the oats sector.

This market dynamic is, on the other hand, not reflective of the diversity of the national context in Finland, characterized by both large and small oats producers and processors, and a duopoly in the Finnish retail sector. Specifically, it was discussed that large processors and retailers use their dominant position (in relation to farming and thus production capacity) to manipulate market prices. This results in two different outcomes: one, resulting in changes in revenues at a level that is conducive to the continuation of operations for larger oats

producers, but may be too low for small farmers; and a second one that establishes a trend of worsening social sustainability, where lack of transparency and poor working conditions at farm and processing level can lead to unfair competition in the market (oats value chain). The consequences of this trend are visible: reduction of the market for small farmers (reducing equality), and hence reduced economic viability for small farm operations. The results is even higher potential for price manipulation and the strengthening of the market position of large producers, processors and retailers (R2). A potential balancing factor, represented by the balancing loop B1 in the diagram, is the increased attention to social and environmental sustainability in the country (also evidenced for Sweden in the interviews), resulting in requests for fair pricing vis a vis the farmers on the consumer side.

A macroeconomic consequence of the centralization of the market (duopoly in the Finnish retail sector, small number of larger processors), and the consolidation of the farming sector, is the potential increase in the cost of sourcing oats when imports become prevalent. This outcome emerges when the operations of small local oats producers are not economically viable, reducing national production and raising resilience (national self-sufficiency) concerns. The side effect is an increase of costs in the whole oats sector (B1), which further increases the need to invest in increasing production and processing capacity, and in investing into sustainable production and processing technologies, also to avoid that market dynamics (pricing power) moves against the oats producers in the value chain.

In order to break this vicious cycle of market power (pricing) imbalances and increasing need for sustainability investment incentives, it was discussed that it is critical to improve the understanding of the importance of social sustainability in the sector, manifesting itself - to provide an example - with the compilation of reporting on social sustainability. If reporting is prepared, interventions to address social sustainability are identified, and organizational change may be triggered (e.g. with the introduction of a department within the processing company that focuses on sustainability). With such change, new data may become available to strengthen the reporting on social sustainability (R3). This could lead to the following outcomes, at the market (value chain) level. On the one hand, there could be a positive economic return from marketing and branding. On the other hand, there could be an increase in awareness for social sustainability, resulting in improved data transparency (e.g. in fair pricing and labour conditions) and more trustworthiness into processors and retailers (in an EU-funded EIT Food project from 2022, the lead author of the CS#2 identified that consumers' trustworthiness into the Finnish processing and retailing

businesses was significantly lower compared to farmers). These developments would challenge the vicious cycle described earlier, turning it into a virtuous cycle, one that support equality (pricing power parity), employee wellbeing, environmental sustainability (esp. more sustainable oats production) and economic sustainability at all levels of the oats value chain.

There are several intervention options that could be considered to trigger the improved social sustainability performance of EU oats value chains contributes to resilient intra-EU trade in oats and oats products. These include private initiatives, such as the introduction of labelling standards going above EU minima, or processes and investment support for more sustainable oats production coming from processing and retailing, or a sectoral coming from processing and retailing, government investment support for social and environmental sustainability initiatives in production and processing, or a sectoral coordination on the establishment of a holistic (value-chain wide) sustainability reporting initiative, in line with the Global Reporting Initiative standards. As highlighted, these intervention options can be applied by different value chain actors, across different thematic areas (see Figure 2), including producers and processors, as well as consumers and government, via increased awareness on sustainability and resilience issues through more extensive and harmonized sustainability reporting and organizational changes (specifically at processor level, placing social sustainability issues not into HR departments, but rather into the relevant sustainability-responsible organizational unit), resulting in higher transparency, stimulating investments and more sustainable trade.

Figure 1. CLD for the dynamics influencing oats production in Finland.

Figure 2. CLD and key thematic areas for oats production in Finland.

Text box 1: Introduction to Systems Thinking

Systems Thinking (ST) is an approach that allows us to better understand and forecast the outcomes of our decisions, across sectors, economic actors, over time and in space (Probst & Bassi, 2014). It emphasizes the system, being made of several interconnected parts, rather than focusing on its individual parts.

With ST being an approach, there are several methodologies and tools that support its implementation and hence the identification of the underlying functioning mechanisms of a system and their quantification and evolution over time. In general terms, it can be said that the identification of the components of a system and of the relationships existing among these components (e.g. carried out through the use of Causal Loop Diagrams) represents (i) the *soft* side of Systems Theory. Instead, attempts to quantify these linkages and forecast how their strength might change over time (e.g. carried out using System Dynamics models) represent (ii) the *hard* side of the field.

Concerning the former (i), Causal Loop Diagrams (CLD) allow to create a shared understanding of how the system works, and hence identify effective entry points for (human) intervention, such as public policies. When this is done using a participatory approach, it helps to bring people together, creating the required building blocks for the co-creation of a shared and effective theory of change.

On the latter (ii), System Dynamic models allow to quantify policy outcomes across social, economic and environmental indicators (UNEP, 2014) providing insights on the relative strength of various drivers of change (scenario analysis) and supporting the identification and prioritization of policy intervention (policy analysis). These models can be bottom up or top down (Probst & Bassi, 2014).

In the context of this research, the role of ST is to assess the extent to which the main drivers of change considered (i.e. ageing of population, technological change and fiscal sustainability) can shape future trends, affect existing policy effectiveness and require future interventions. This in turn allows to identify a system's safe operating space and limits, anticipating the emergence of side effects, across social, economic and environmental indicators.

Text box 2: Causal Loop Diagrams (CLD)

A causal loop diagram (CLD) is a map of the system analysed, or, better, a way to explore and represent the interconnections between the key indicators in the analysed sector or system (Probst & Bassi, 2014). As indicated by John Sterman, “A causal diagram consists of variables connected by arrows denoting the causal influences among the variables. The important feedback loops are also identified in the diagram. Variables are related by causal links, shown by arrows. Link polarities describe the structure of the system. They do not describe the behavior of the variables. That is, they describe what would happen if there were a change. They do not describe what actually happens. Rather, it tells you what would happen if the variable were to change.” (Sterman, 2000)

As indicated by Sterman, CLDs include variables and arrows (called causal links), with the latter linking the variables together with a sign (either + or –) on each link, indicating a positive or negative causal relation (see Table 1). A causal link from variable A to variable B is positive if a change in A produces a change in B in the same direction. A causal link from variable A to variable B is negative if a change in A produces a change in B in the opposite direction. Circular causal relations between variables form causal, or feedback, loops. There are two types of feedback loops: reinforcing and balancing. The former can be found when an intervention in the system triggers other changes that amplify the effect of that intervention, thus reinforcing it (Forrester, 2002). The latter, balancing loops, tend towards a goal or equilibrium, balancing the forces in the system (Forrester, 2002).

By highlighting the drivers and impacts of the issue to be addressed and by mapping the causal relationships between the key indicators, CLDs support the identification of policy outcomes using a systemic approach (Probst & Bassi, 2014). CLDs can be in fact be used to create storylines corresponding to the implementation of policy interventions, by highlighting direct, indirect and induced policy outcomes across social, economic and environmental indicators.

Variable A	Variable B	Sign
↑	↑	+
↓	↓	+
↑	↓	-
↓	↑	-

Table 1. Causal relations and polarity

2.2 CS3 – Dairy (EU, Finland)

The issue analysed is the sustainability of dairy production in Finland. The methodology used for the creation of the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is called Systems Thinking (see Text Box 1). A CLD is a graphical representation of variables and their interconnections, giving shape to the dynamics of a given system (see Text Box 2).

The CLD is presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4, and was created as a team effort, founded on co-creation (with a step by step, participatory approach).

Several factors that constrain the production of dairy products in Finland were identified. These are underlying the presence of balancing feedback loops in the system, or dynamics that counter (oppose) change, as described as follows.

At the beginning of the creation of the CLD, we have analysed the dynamics that determine the number of animals, which then affects the amount of dairy production. The number of animals has been historically impacted by regional economic activity, with dairy farming being an option that offers income under different climatic conditions, being more resilient than crop farming for instance. On the other hand, over time the growth of the number of animals has slowed down, to the point that it has plateaued. The availability of land is not the primary cause of this stabilization of the number of animals. On the other hand, the availability of *suitable* land has declined over time. This is represented by balancing loops B2 and B2, which indicate that land is required for both feed and for animals.

We have then explored the implications of such stabilization of the number of animals which, on the one hand limits the potential to generate more employment (an undesirable emerging dynamic represented by B8) and revenues; on the other hand, a somewhat contained production, well aligned with demand for local consumption and exports, guarantees economical market prices (B1). This is important to keep profitability at a reasonable level for farmers which, under a scenario of supply outstripping demand, would see market prices decline and revenues follow suit. Profitability is also impacted by two additional dynamics: (i) the fact that a higher number of animals carries higher costs (with a somewhat reduced possibility to create economies of scale in the Finnish context) and (ii) revenues are supported by EU and national subsidies, currently based on the number of animals (and hence, also in this case there is no possibility to generate economies of scale).

Two additional, and currently more relevant constraints, characterize the dairy sector in Finland, and both are related to environmental sustainability.

On the one hand, there are limitations to the expansion of the animal stock in relation to (a) manure application and (b) GHG emissions. Regulation on the acceptable manure application per hectare and on GHG emissions effectively puts a cap to the number of animals allowed (see B4 and B5).

On the other hand, consumers are becoming more and more aware of -and interested in- environmental issues, and have begun to reduce the consumption of environmentally unsustainable dairy products, and dairy products in general.

A change in consumer preference, together with the possibility of the introduction of a carbon tax, affects both production costs (higher, due to the carbon tax, B6) and revenues (lower, due to reduced local demand, B9). Under this scenario, it can be expected that a larger share of production may be exported. On the other hand, the Finnish dairy market faces fierce competition within Europe, and is not competitive on cost and brand attractiveness.

Concluding, it was assessed that, if Finnish farmers use a virtuous approach to environmental protection, e.g. via ecosystem service preservation, tourism opportunities may emerge at the local level (offering economic diversification), and subsidies for environmental preservation may be received both from the national government and the EU. This would generate a revenue stream that is in line with environmental sustainability goals, a sharp contrast with the current approach where subsidies are provided based on the number of animals, but constraints are applied based on manure and GHG generation.

Figure 3. CLD for the dynamics influencing dairy production in Finland.

Legend: Red variables (external factors), Orange variables (policy options).

Figure 4. CLD and key thematic areas for dairy production in Finland.

2.3 CS5 – Poultry (Ghana)

The issue analysed is the sustainability of poultry production in Ghana. The methodology used for the creation of the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is called Systems Thinking (see Text Box 1). A CLD is a graphical representation of variables and their interconnections, giving shape to the dynamics of a given system (see Text Box 2).

The CLD is presented in Figure 5, and was created by UPM through a participatory approach with stakeholders from the poultry sector in Ghana, and in close collaboration with CSIR-STEPRI.

The Conceptual Model of the Poultry System in Ghana shows a dynamic system that connects various elements and dimensions influencing the sustainability and competitiveness of the poultry farming sector. This model reflects how different elements and dimensions interrelate within the industry, forming reinforcing loops that amplify trends and balancing loops that mitigate them.

At the core of the model are the strategic investments in quality inputs and improved farming practices which lead to increased performance rates thus enhancing profitability, represented by the Reinvestment – Farm Performance Reinforcement Loop (R1). In turn, this profitability is used as a start for further investment into poultry farming supporting continuous improvement within the sector. Moreover, investing in better farm practices improves compliance with quality standards, resulting in better prices and increased profitability, as shown in R2. This reinforces farmers' ability to reinvest in poultry farming. Farmers' investing capacity, represented by R1 and R2, is also reinforced when accessing to appropriate processing, storage, and retail facilities, which allows farmers to comply with quality standards and obtain better prices for their products, further improving profitability (as shown in R3). Farmers with higher reinvestment capacity are more likely to increase the flock size in their farms, which will give them better access to loans to invest in improving farm performance and products quality through better access to services, and facilities, reinforcing competitiveness of their products and thus the domestic poultry sector (R5). As a result, farmers' profitability is enhanced and thus their reinvestment capacity will stimulate increasing their flock size (R6). Besides, if farmers adopt better management practices, they have better access to low-interest loans, which reinforces their adoption of good practices and technologies, including management practices (R7). Improving management practices at the farm level puts farmers in better conditions to access loans, that will allow them to continue improving their practices.

Along with the improvements in poultry farming profitability resulting from the dynamics above, the competitiveness of domestic poultry meat is also enhanced. This more competitive domestic poultry sector can positively impact farmer's access to tailored knowledge and technology transfer services, reinforcing competitiveness (R4).

On the other hand, investing in the adoption of better practices and technologies leads to an increase in costs associated with improved husbandry practices, housing facilities, and equipment at the farm, as well as those related to processing, storage, and retail facilities. These costs balance the profitability of poultry farming and, therefore, the farmers' capacity to reinvest (B1). Moreover, a more competitive domestic poultry sector drives tailored knowledge and technology transfer services and improves the enforcement of regulations that support the sector. These two conditions help farmers to adopt better practices and technologies, which leads to an increase in costs that balance the competitiveness of the domestic poultry meat (B2).

Figure 5: CLD for the dynamics influencing poultry production in Ghana

2.4 CS10 – Beef (EU, Africa, South America)

The issue analysed is the sustainability of beef production and the potential role of current and upcoming policies to increase sustainability both on the production and consumption side. The methodology used for the creation of the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is called Systems Thinking (see Text Box 1). A CLD is a graphical representation of variables and their interconnections, giving shape to the dynamics of a given system (see Text Box 2).

The CLD is presented in Figure 6 and Figure 7, and was created as a team effort, founded on co-creation (with a step by step, participatory approach).

Several factors determine the potential to grow, as well as constraints for the beef production sector. These are underlying the presence of reinforcing feedback loops, or dynamic that stimulate change (e.g. an increase in cost competitiveness results in the growth of farms and in the creation of economies of scale, which further increase cost competitiveness), and balancing feedback loops in the system, or dynamics that counter (oppose) change (e.g. constraints on land availability may result in higher costs, a factor that reduced costs competitiveness and curbs the growth potential of farms), as described as follows.

At the beginning of the CLD creation process, we have analysed the dynamics that determine the farm size, which then affects the cost of production. The farm size has been historically impacted by access to capital, which then allows to reduce the cost of production and increase cost competitiveness, resulting in the further growth of farm size (R1). A growing farm size also influences labor intensity (declining) and the number of animals (increasing). Access to capital also influences technology adoption, which affects labor intensity (reducing it). As a result, employment is impacted both by labor intensity (affected by farm size and technology adoption) and by the number of animals. With higher employment come higher labor costs (both due to the total number of employees and the skill level of employees), showing that labor costs are pushed higher by increased skills (R3), but also pushed lower by reduced labor intensity (B1).

We have then explored the implications of the growth of farm size that has occurred historically. On the one hand, it generates a lock-in effect (with farms becoming bigger and bigger, underlying the dominance of reinforcing loops, via an improvement of cost competitiveness, R2), on the other hand it leads to higher production, economic activity and revenues. This, together with the reduced cost achieved via economies of scale and technology adoption, results

in higher profitability, and hence higher access to capital (as a combination of R1, R2 and R3).

This being considered, constraints also emerged. The higher is production, the lower is beef price (if supply is larger than demand). This would generate a balancing dynamic, that would reduce profitability and the expansion of farms (unless export potential allows to further increase production without affecting local dynamics), but possibly trigger an increase in demand for beef (B5). Further, on the environmental side, higher production results in (i) higher land requirements, feed production, which may face higher costs if land availability is constrained (B3); (ii) higher manure generation, causing an increase in nutrient concentration per hectare, and (iii) higher GHG emissions. National and international legislation may limit production when excessive amounts of nutrients and emissions are produced (e.g., measured in terms of emissions productivity per ton of meat produced). In the same way, consumer preferences have, in certain instances, shifted to low emission, animal welfare certified products. These emerging dynamics would reduce demand (if sustainability is not addressed, B4) or increase demand, including for export (if sustainability concerns are addressed, R5).

Several intervention options were identified that could support investments in sustainability for beef production. Within sector operations, the adoption of technology (via access to capital) would increase productivity, reducing nutrient concentration and GHG emissions. Lobby groups, animal welfare legislation, and consumer attention could trigger efforts towards labelling of the sustainability of beef, stimulating affecting exports, and beef demand overall. This intervention would generate positive returns for investments in improved sustainability, a factor that is currently -for the most part- an intangible benefit.

Concluding, it was assessed that, product sustainability through both improved production practices, animal welfare, land use (e.g. avoided deforestation) and GHG emission reduction can positively impact beef prices (with a premium being applied to sustainable products) and boost export to premium markets. National legislations, lobby groups, and consumer attention can support the internalization of intangible benefits, e.g. via product labelling, payments for ecosystem services, generating a stream of revenues that it is in line with sustainability goals. At the same time, higher profitability and investments in technology can also improve wages, generating a mutually reinforcing synergy between economic, social and environmental performance.

Figure 6. CLD for the dynamics influencing beef production.

Legend: Red variables (external factors), Orange variables (policy options).

Figure 7. CLD and key thematic areas for beef production

2.5 CS13 – Milk (EU, Africa, America)

The issue analysed is the sustainability of dairy production and the potential role of current and upcoming policies to increase sustainability. The methodology used for the creation of the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is called Systems Thinking (see Text Box 1). A CLD is a graphical representation of variables and their interconnections, giving shape to the dynamics of a given system (see Text Box 2).

The CLD is presented in Figure 8 and Figure 9, and was created as a team effort, founded on co-creation (with a step by step, participatory approach).

At the beginning of the CLD creation process, we have analysed the dynamics that determine the total cost of production of dairy products. At first, we focused on the labor costs, in relation to salaries, as a key cost item. We identified that salaries are impacted by the profitability of operations, which are in turn impacted by revenues (driven by production and market price) and by the total cost of production (including considerations on the total number of cows, employment and labor costs). Considerations were made on the market price, being impacts both by demand and supply. At this stage two feedback loops were identified, one a key determinant of growth (R) related to production resulting in higher profitability and in the expansion of operations, and one being of a balancing nature (B), tending towards equilibrium in relation to the level of salaries provided.

After these initial considerations, the attention moved towards the key drivers of productivity, also a factor affecting the total cost of production. In this context we identified feed quality, genetic improvements, mechanization and robotization as options to increase productivity and reduce the levelized cost of production. On the other hand, national legislation, e.g. on animal welfare, safety and security, while increasing productivity, may also result in higher costs.

As a subsequent step in the creation of the diagram, environmental considerations were added. It was discussed that a higher number of cows would result in increased manure creation, resulting in a higher concentration of nutrients per hectare (e.g. nitrogen and phosphorous). This is a potential limiting factor for the expansion of the animal stock, and is represented by a balancing loop (B) in the diagram. On the other hand, if it is possible to expand the land area available for cows, then this constraint is removed, and reinforcing mechanism is introduced (R). This highlights that land availability, depending on

specific local contexts, can be an enabling factor but also a constraint to the expansion of the operations in the dairy sector. On the other hand, environmental constraints do remain, especially when considering GHG emissions. When land is available for expansion, and this is realized via deforestation, carbon sequestration would be lost, increasing the GHG footprint of dairy production. When considering that cows also generate emissions, e.g. via enteric fermentation, GHG intensity may increase.

Several intervention options were identified to remove bottlenecks while increasing the sustainability of dairy production. On the environmental side, reforestation, land restoration and the introduction of renewable energy for farm operations were considered to reduce GHG emissions. Efforts to improve labor and animal conditions were considered to increase revenues (e.g. via subsidies) while at the same time increase productivity. Finally, considerations were made on trade dynamics, with the price of milk import affecting the potential for local production, reason why both improved productivity and environmental sustainability are essential.

Figure 8. CLD for the dynamics influencing dairy production.

Legend: Red variables (external factors), Orange variables (policy options).

Figure 9. CLD and key thematic areas for dairy production

2.6 CS14 – Pork (Brazil)

The issue analysed is the sustainability of production of soybeans for the pork industry in the Cerrado region in Brazil. The methodology used for the creation of the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is called Systems Thinking (see Text Box 1). A CLD is a graphical representation of variables and their interconnections, giving shape to the dynamics of a given system (see Text Box 2).

The CLD is presented in Figure 10 and Figure 11, and was created as a team effort, founded on co-creation (with a step by step, participatory approach).

Several factors that influence soy production in the Cerrado region were identified. These are underlying the presence of balancing feedback loops in the system, or dynamics that counter (oppose) change, as described as follows.

At the beginning of the creation of the CLD, we have analysed the dynamics that determine land cover change in the region, which then affects the amount of land allocated to soy production. Soy demand, which is driven by demand from feedstock, has been identified as one of the causes for land cover change. Moreover, the land allocated to soy cultivation is a limiting factor for land cover change. This is represented by balancing loop B1, which indicates that land allocated to soy production is limited, and by balancing loop B2, which shows that the availability of cheap land influence land cover changes as well. In essence both land availability and the cost of land are limiting factors to the expansion of soy production.

We have then explored the main factors that influence land cover change, investigating the dynamics related to value chain of soy. To begin with, soy revenues are influenced by soy price and production, which is in turn affected by demand. Secondly, the cost of soy production is influenced by the size of operations (i.e. land), the cost of land conversion, and the cost of capital. Both soy revenues and the cost of soy production impact the economic profitability of soy production. When profitability is high, there is an incentive to convert protected Cerrado land in private areas, triggering R1 and R2. These feedback loops are critical, as the conversion of protected land allows for both (i) new areas to be exploited, and (ii) cheap land becoming available for farmers. These two dynamics make B1 and B2 (constraints to growth) weaker, creating an opportunity for growth.

If land, both private and public, is better protected (and they increase as well), we reduce the availability of cheap land for soy production in the region and increase the cost of land, reducing the profitability of soy production, and further reduce the temptation to clear protected land for soy production. In order to improve environmental sustainability and stabilize the expansion of soy production, we

explored the use of seven policy options (coloured in orange). First expanding the Amazon Soy Moratorium to the Cerrado region in the private land, further limiting the availability of land for soy production; second adopting EU DR policies and the MERCOSUR EU trade agreement, intervening on both public and private land. The introduction of certifications would also affect private land, while also increasing soy revenues. Other policies targeting illegal deforestation, strengthening trade regulations with China, and developing multi-actor territorial agreements would further support monitoring and enforcement of protected areas and limit soy demand and land allocated to soy production.

Supporting traditional communities and promoting products that support social and environmental (e.g. biodiversity) dimensions through targeted policies (expanding the Amazon Soy Moratorium, eradicate illegal deforestation, and develop multi-actor territorial agreement) would also result in increased protected land. Official credit for family farming and large-scale agriculture would also support land protection while promoting biodiversity products and decreasing the cost of capital.

Figure 10: CLD for the dynamics influencing land-use dynamics of soy production as feed for the pork's industry in the Cerrado region (Brazil).

Legend: Red variables (external factors), Orange variables (policy options), Green variables (protected areas), Blue variables (community dimension).

Figure 11: CLD and key thematic areas for feed production for the pork's industry

2.7 CS15 – Olive oil (Tunisia)

The Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) presented in Figure 12 shows the main drivers of change of olive oil production in Tunisia. In our analysis, we have highlighted certain factors using color coding. The intervention options are colored in orange (such as olive oil production targets for export), as they represent potential course of actions, while external factors beyond the control of local actors (such as precipitation and temperature) are marked in red.

One crucial aspect is the government's irrigation policy, which shows support for irrigation infrastructure, particularly concerning olive oil production, geared towards exports. However, this focus on olive oil production targets has a notable impact on the use of agricultural land. As the largest portion of land is allocated to olive oil production, the space available for other crops diminishes. This adjustment affects both crop and livestock production, ultimately influencing income creation of farmers and reducing income diversification, which reduces affordability of olive oil and hence domestic consumption.

It is worth noting that the pursuit of export targets can have two main consequences. While it leads to increased olive oil production, benefiting farmers through trade, it also raises water demand due to the irrigation infrastructure required for monocultural practices. The higher irrigation demand strains water resources, causing water stress, particularly regarding groundwater. In this context, water stress is further exacerbated by precipitation (such as current droughts and future precipitation declines) and increases in temperature as a consequence of climate change, as well as by water demand for other uses. As a consequence, groundwater resources are further depleted, decreasing water availability for agriculture, including for olive oil production.

In response to water stress, we have identified potential intervention options. Efficiency in irrigation practices emerges as a potential solution to decrease overall water demand for agriculture (B1 in the diagram). The level of water stress directly influences groundwater demand, which subsequently feeds into the water requirements for agricultural purposes. Hence, a decrease in available groundwater corresponds to limitations on agricultural water demand. Another path involves embracing ecologically responsible agricultural practices, which could help mitigate the negative impact of intensive olive oil production on water resources (B2 in the diagram). Besides, shifting away from monoculture olive oil practices, which are water-intensive, would reduce water demand for irrigation while increasing land availability to create revenues from crop and livestock production, which would help to offset the expected decline in revenues from olive oil production, and diversify

income creation. Another approach centers around the development of the olive oil value chain to maximize the revenues from production. Nonetheless, it is crucial to remember that more irrigation infrastructure and agricultural land dedicated to olive oil mean greater water demand. Addressing water stress requires considering not only agriculture-related water needs but also those for general use. Moreover, the intricate interplay between climate variables like precipitation and temperature influences water supply.

In essence, the balancing act between these factors forms the basis for effective decision-making. For example, when water availability decreases due to lower precipitation and more groundwater use, transparency for water use rights could be an option to make water use for agriculture more efficient.

Figure 12: Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) presenting the main drivers of change of olive oil production in Tunisia

Legend: Red variables (external factors), Orange variables (policy options).

3 Systems models

3.1 CS3 – Dairy (EU, Finland)

Based on conversations with UH, we focused on land use changes in North Ostrobothnia that occurred from since the 2000s. We used the Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST) suite of models to quantify changes in carbon storage, habitat quality, and nutrient export. The analysis indicates that the expansion of agricultural areas leads to the deterioration of those selected ecosystem services.

3.1.1 Model set up

3.1.1.1 Study area

The study area of this analysis is composed by the Southern regions of North Ostrobothnia (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Location of the Study Area

3.1.1.2 Coordination system

Based on world project coordinate system called “V WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator -- Spherical Mercator – EPSG: 3857”

Here is the detail of the coordinate system:

```
PROJCS["WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator",
  GEOGCS["WGS 84",
    DATUM["WGS_1984",
      SPHEROID["WGS 84",6378137,298.257223563,
        AUTHORITY["EPSG","7030"]],
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","6326"]],
    PRIMEM["Greenwich",0,
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","8901"]],
    UNIT["degree",0.0174532925199433,
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","9122"]],
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","4326"]],
    PROJECTION["Mercator_1SP"],
    PARAMETER["central_meridian",0],
    PARAMETER["scale_factor",1],
    PARAMETER["false_easting",0],
    PARAMETER["false_northing",0],
    UNIT["metre",1,
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","9001"]],
    AXIS["X",EAST],
    AXIS["Y",NORTH],
    EXTENSION["PROJ4","+proj=merc +a=6378137 +b=6378137 +lat_ts=0.0 +lon_0=0.0 +x_0=0.0 +y_0=0 +k=1.0 +units=m
+nadgrids=@null +wktext +no_defs"],
    AUTHORITY["EPSG","3857"]]
```

3.1.1.3 Land Cover maps

Initially, the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) land use and land cover (LULC) in 2000 and 2018³ have been used in this study. The resolution of the map was set to 100m. However, we suspect that those two maps were probably created in two different seasons, since in 2018 there are 120,780 ha of water bodies less than in 2000, which are replaced mainly by forest. Therefore, we excluded the results obtained with the 2018 LULC map and considered an “Alternative 2000” LULC map instead, which is the 2000 LULC scenario where we also included the expanded agricultural land in 2018.

Figure 14, Figure 15, and Figure 16 show the LULC in 2000, in 2018, and under the Alternative 2000 LULC scenarios.

³ <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover>

Legend

- Study Area
- LULC 2000
- 2 - Discontinuous urban fabric
- 3 - Industrial or commercial units
- 4 - Road and rail networks and associated land
- 5 - Port areas
- 6 - Airports
- 7 - Mineral extraction sites
- 8 - Dump sites
- 9 - Construction sites
- 10 - Green urban areas
- 11 - Sport and leisure facilities
- 12 - Non-irrigated arable land
- 16 - Fruit trees and berry plantations
- 18 - Pastures
- 20 - Complex cultivation patterns
- 21 - Mix of agriculture and areas of natural vegetation
- 23 - Broad-leaved forest
- 24 - Coniferous forest
- 25 - Mixed forest
- 29 - Transitional woodland-shrub
- 30 - Beaches - dunes - sands
- 31 - Bare rocks
- 35 - Inland marshes
- 36 - Peat bogs
- 37 - Salt marshes
- 40 - Water courses
- 41 - Water bodies
- 44 - Sea and ocean
- OSM Standard

Figure 14: Land-use map - 2000

Legend

- Study Area
- LULC 2018
- 2 - Discontinuous urban fabric
- 3 - Industrial or commercial units
- 4 - Road and rail networks and associated land
- 5 - Port areas
- 6 - Airports
- 7 - Mineral extraction sites
- 8 - Dump sites
- 9 - Construction sites
- 10 - Green urban areas
- 11 - Sport and leisure facilities
- 12 - Non-irrigated arable land
- 16 - Fruit trees and berry plantations
- 18 - Pastures
- 20 - Complex cultivation patterns
- 21 - Mix of agriculture and areas of natural vegetation
- 23 - Broad-leaved forest
- 24 - Coniferous forest
- 25 - Mixed forest
- 29 - Transitional woodland-shrub
- 30 - Beaches - dunes - sands
- 31 - Bare rocks
- 35 - Inland marshes
- 36 - Peat bogs
- 37 - Salt marshes
- 40 - Water courses
- 41 - Water bodies
- 44 - Sea and ocean
- OSM Standard

Figure 15: Land-use map – 2018

Figure 16: Land-use map– Alternative 2000

3.1.1.4 Software and simulation

The ecosystem services map simulation has been performed using InVEST Software V.3.9.0 (<https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/invest/>). The inputs spatial data for the InVEST model have been prepared by utilizing QGIS-OSGeoW-3.4.2-1 (qgis.org/downloads/). The tabulated data will be managed and prepared in Ms. Excel V. 2016.

3.1.2 Carbon Storage

3.1.2.1 Input data preparation and processing

1. Land use/land cover maps – see section 3.1.1.3

2. Carbon Pools - Table of LULC classes, containing data on carbon stored in each of the four fundamental pools for each LULC class

- Carbon above ground: The values of carbon density in aboveground mass (Tons/ha) of each land-use type are shown in Table 1
- Carbon below ground: The values of carbon density in belowground mass (Tons/ha) of each land use-type are shown in Table 1.
- Carbon stored in organic matter: The values of carbon density in dead mass (Tons/ha) of each land-use type are shown in in Table 1
- Carbon stored in soil: The values of carbon density in dead mass (Tons/ha) of each land-use type are shown in in Table 1

The unit of measurement for these coefficients is Tons/ha. Average carbon coefficients values have been found in the “2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories” report, chapter 4 “Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use” (IPCC, 2006).

lucode	C_above	C_below	C_soil	C_dead
2	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0
9	47	10.81	0.68	0
10	0	0	0	0
11	18.8	6.2	0.68	0
12	18.8	6.2	0.68	0
16	18.8	6.2	0.68	0
18	18.8	6.2	0.68	0
20	18.8	6.2	0.68	0
21	94	21.62	0.68	0
23	94	21.62	0.68	0
24	94	21.62	0.68	0
25	0.8	3.05	0.68	0
29	0	0	0	0
30	0	0	0	0
31	0	0	0	0
35	14.1	54.05	0.68	0
36	14.1	54.05	0.68	0
37	0	0	0	0
40	0	0	0	0
41	0	0	0	0
44	18.8	6.2	0.68	0

Table 1: Carbon pools

3.1.2.2 Results

Figure 17, and Figure 18 show the amount of carbon stored in Tons in each pixel using the LULC in 2000 and under the Alternative 2000 LULC scenario, respectively. They are a sum of all the carbon pools provided by the biophysical table.

Figure 17: Carbon model outputs (LULC 2000)

Figure 18: Carbon model outputs (Alternative LULC 2000)

Scenario	Carbon Stored (Tons)	Change from 2000
2000	74,454,795	
Alternative 2000	71,990,009	-3.31%

Table 2: Carbon storage statistics

As Table 2 shows, the total carbon storage would decrease by roughly 3.5% under the “Alternative 2000” scenario compared to 2000 due to the expansion of agricultural land.

3.1.3 Habitat Quality

3.1.3.1 Input data preparation and processing

1. Land use/land cover maps - see section 3.1.1.3

2. Threat Data - several major threads such as cropland areas, urban areas, and the road network have been identified as the threat sources to the natural habitat and biodiversity. See table below (Table 3). See Table 9 for data sources.

N.	Threat name	Max_Distance	Weighted value	Decay function
2	Industrial or commercial units	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
3	Road and rail networks and associated land	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
4	Port areas	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
5	Airports	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
6	Mineral extraction sites	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
7	Dump sites	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
8	Construction sites	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
10	Sport and leisure facilities	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
11	Non-irrigated arable land	4 km	0.7	Linear
12	Fruit trees and berry plantations	4 km	0.7	Linear
16	Pastures	4 km	0.7	Linear
18	Complex cultivation patterns	4 km	0.7	Linear
20	Land principally occupied by agriculture with significant areas of natural vegetation	4 km	0.7	Linear

Table 3: Table of threat (maximum distance, weighted value, and decay function) for InVEST simulation

3. Half-saturation constraint – the default value of 0.5 was used

4. Sensitivity of land cover types to each threat - characterizing each LULC type to be habitat or non-habitat and the type’s sensitivity to the threats (shown in Table 4, see Table 10 for data sources). The table contains the following fields:

4.1 LULC – codes identify each LULC class

4.2 Name – abbreviation of each LULC class

4.3 Habitat – score characterizing each LULC as habitat or non-habitat. The values of 0 and 1 are used for the purpose, in which 0 for non-habitat class and 1 for habitat class of LULC.

L_urban_2, L_urban_3, L_urban_4, L_urban_5, L_urban_6, L_urban_7, L_urban_8, L_urban_10, L_crop_11, L_crop_12, L_crop_16, L_crop_18, L_crop_20, - these are columns for the relative sensitivity of LULC classes to the threat

LULC	Habitat	crop_11_c	crop_12_c	crop_16_c	crop_18_c	crop_20_c	urban_2_c	urban_3_c	urban_4_c	urban_5_c	urban_6_c	urban_7_c	urban_8_c	urban_10_c
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0.4	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69
12	0.4	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69
16	0.4	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69
18	0.4	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69
20	0.4	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69
21	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
23	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
24	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
25	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
35	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
36	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
37	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4: Table of Sensitivity of land cover types to each threat for InVEST simulation

3.1.3.2 Results

Figure 19, and Figure 20 show the relative level of habitat quality using the LULC in 2000 and under the Alternative 2000 LULC scenario, respectively.

Figure 19: Scores of habitat quality – 2000

Figure 20: Scores of habitat quality – Alternative 2000

Scenario	Mean of HQ	Change from 2000
2000	0.2788	
Alternative 2000	0.2564	-8.03%

Table 5: mean of HQ per year

As Table 5 shows, under the “Alternative 2000” LULC scenario (which is the 2000 LULC scenario where we also included the expanded agricultural land in 2018), habitat quality decreases by more than 8% compared to 2000 due to the expansion of agriculture, which leads to habitat loss and fragmentation.

3.1.4 Nutrient export

3.1.4.1 Input data preparation and processing

1. **DEM Raster** – the hydrologically conditioned elevation dataset which is distributed by Hydrosheds (<https://www.hydrosheds.org/>) was downloaded on December 4th, 2023 for InVEST sediment model input. The data was prepared for hydrological model input purpose mainly for flow direction, accumulation simulation, river network and biome delineation. The original spatial resolution of the dataset 15 arcsec.
2. **Land use/land cover maps** – see section 3.1.1.3
3. **Nutrient Runoff Proxy Raster (Precipitation)** – The average precipitation (in mm) from 1970 to 2000 downloaded from WorldClim version 2 (www.worldclim.com) was used for this study. The dataset was released on the first of June 2016. The original spatial resolution of the data is 30 seconds x 30 seconds (which is approximately 1 km²).
4. **Watershed Polygons** – This is the polygon shapefile representing the watersheds.
5. **Biophysical Table** – A table of land use/land cover (LULC) classes, containing data on water quality coefficients used in this tool (Table 6). NOTE: these data are attributes of each LULC class rather than attributes of individual cells in the raster map. These data were derived from Kulsoontornrat & Ongsomwang (2021). The table has the following field:
 - 5.1 **Lucode** – unique identifier for each LULC class.
 - 5.2 **load_n / load_p** – The nutrient loading for each land use. If nitrogen is being evaluated, supply values in load_n, for phosphorus, supply values in load_p. The potential for terrestrial loading of water quality impairing constituents is based on nutrient export coefficients.

The nutrient loading values are given as integer values and have units of $\text{kg. ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

5.3 *eff_n / eff_p* – The vegetation filtering value per pixel size for each LULC class, as an integer percent between zero and 1. If nitrogen is being evaluated, supply values in *eff_n*, for phosphorus, supply values in *eff_p*. This field identifies the capacity of vegetation to retain nutrients, as a percentage of the amount of nutrient flowing into a cell from upslope. For example, if the user has data describing that a wetland of 5000 m^2 retains 82% of nitrogen, then the retention efficiency that she/he should input into this field for *eff_n* is equal to $(82/5000 * (\text{cell size})^2)$. In the simplest case, when data for each LULC type are not available, high values (60 to 80) may be assigned to all natural vegetation types (such as forests, natural pastures, wetlands, or prairie), indicating that 60-80% of nutrients are retained. An intermediary value also may be assigned to features such as contour buffers. All LULC classes that have no filtering capacity, such as pavement, can be assigned a value of zero

5.4 *crit_len_n (and/or crit_len_p)* (at least one is required): The distance after which is assumed that a patch of a particular LULC type retains nutrient at its maximum capacity, given in meters. If nutrients travel a distance smaller than the retention length, the retention efficiency will be less than the maximum value *eff_x*, following an exponential decay. This value represents the typical distance necessary to reach the maximum retention efficiency. It was introduced in the model to remove any sensitivity to the resolution of the LULC raster. In the absence of local data for land uses that are not forest or grass, it is possible to simply set the retention length constant, equal to the pixel size: this will result in the maximum retention efficiency being reached within a distance of one pixel only.

5.5 *proportion_subsurface_n or p (optional)*: The proportion of dissolved nutrients over the total amount of nutrients, expressed as floating point value (ratio) between 0 and 1. By default, this value should be set to 0, indicating that all nutrients are delivered via surface flow.

lucode	load_n	eff_n	load_p	eff_p	crit_len_n	crit_len_p	proportion_subsurface_n
2	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
3	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
4	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
5	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
6	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
7	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
8	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
9	5.855	0.36	0.583	0.36	100	100	0
10	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
11	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0
12	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0
16	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0
18	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0
20	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0
21	2.89	0.51	0.077	0.51	100	100	0
23	2.89	0.51	0.077	0.51	100	100	0
24	2.89	0.51	0.077	0.51	100	100	0
25	5.855	0.36	0.583	0.36	100	100	0
29	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
30	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
31	13.361	0.13	4.195	0.13	100	100	0
35	13.361	0.13	4.195	0.13	100	100	0
36	13.361	0.13	4.195	0.13	100	100	0
37	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
40	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
41	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
44	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0

Table 6: Biophysical table – Annual Nutrient Delivery Ratio

6. Threshold flow accumulation value: Integer value defining the number of upstream pixels that must flow into a pixel before it is considered part of a stream. This is used to generate a stream layer from the DEM. This threshold expresses where hydrologic routing is discontinued, i.e. where retention stops, and the remaining pollutant will be exported to the stream. The value of 100 was used in this simulation.

7. Subsurface maximum retention efficiency (Nitrogen or phosphorus): the maximum nutrient retention efficiency that can be reached through subsurface flow, a value between 0 and 1. This field characterizes the retention due to biochemical degradation in soils. The default value of 0.8 was used for this study.

8. Subsurface_crit_len (Nitrogen or phosphorus) (in meter): the distance (traveled subsurface and downslope) after which is assumed that soil retains nutrient at its maximum capacity. If dissolved nutrients travel a distance smaller than subsurface_crit_len, the retention efficiency is lower than the maximum value defined above. The value of 100 was used in this simulation.

9. Borselli k parameter: calibration parameter that determines the shape of the relationship between hydrologic connectivity (the degree of connection from patches of land to the stream) and the sediment delivery ratio (percentage of soil loss that actually reaches the stream). The default value is 2.

3.1.4.2 Results

Scenario	Nitrogen export (kg)	Change from 2000
2000	1,800,916	
Alternative 2000	1,901,607	5.59%

Table 7: Nitrogen Export Statistics

Scenario	Phosphorus export (kg)	Change from 2000
2000	249,703	
Alternative 2000	256,932	2.90%

Table 8: Phosphorus Export Statistics

Table 7 and Table 8 show that the total export of both Nitrogen and Phosphorus (kg) would increase under the “Alternative 2000” LULC scenario (which is the 2000 LULC scenario where we also included the expanded agricultural land in 2018) due to the increase of cropland replacing forestland.

3.1.5 Annex I

Threat	Max _Dist ance	Max_Dist ance Adopted sources	Weighte d value	Weight value Adopted sources	Decay function	Decay func. Adopted sources
Croplands and Pastureland	4 km	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.7	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	Linear	(Bhagabati , et al., 2012)
Urban area	7.1 km	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.7	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	Linear	(Bhagabati , et al., 2012)

Table 9: Habitat Quality model – references “threat table”

Value	Habitat	Habitat Adopted sources	Sensitivity to Agricultural source	Sensitivity to Agri source Adopted Sources	Sensitivity to Urban Areas Sources	Sensitivity to Urban Area Adopted sources
2	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
3	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
4	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
5	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
6	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
7	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
8	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
9	0.5	Assumed	0.5	Assumed	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
10	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
11	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)
12	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)
16	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)
18	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)
20	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)
21	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
23	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
24	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
25	0.5	Assumed	0.5	Assumed	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
29	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
30	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
31	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
35	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
36	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
37	0	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0
40	0	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0
41	0	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0
44	0	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0

Table 10 Habitat Quality model – references “threat sensitivity table”

3.2 CS5 – Poultry (Ghana)

3.2.1 Introduction and data used

The economic viability of poultry investments (disaggregated per broilers and layers as well as per farm size) has been assessed via the creation of an integrated Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA). CBA serves as a "pre-investment tool," conducting economic analyses to help guide investment choices (IFAD, 2015). As the costs and benefits of investments typically do not occur at the same time, with costs usually preceding benefits, the comparison is not straightforward. Nevertheless, CBA offers reliable indicators that aid in decision-making, enabling the comparison of projects using a consistent analytical framework. The assessment includes the calculation of the financial Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Net-Present Value (NPV), and Benefit-to-Cost Ratio (BCR) of selected investment options. Please note that the assumed duration of the investments is 5 years and that the financial discount rate of all investments was assumed to be 31.16% (an average of the first four months of 2023 obtained from The Bank of Ghana (2023)).

The product of this CS is an Excel Spreadsheet structured with the following sheets:

- 1) **CBA – Layers:** This is the CBA for layers, it uses data from the sheet "Calculations – Layers". Here, we calculated the key economic indicators of the CBA, such as the IRR, the BCR, the NPV, and the Payback Period. Please note that we have added in columns L-N the "Levers for economic viability", which are the required subsidies for feed prices, and the needed increases in productivity and in market prices to make the investment positive.
- 2) **Calculations – Layers:** Here we calculated the various Costs and Benefits that are included in the CBA.
- 3) **Data Collection:** In this sheet it is possible to find all the data that we have used in the CBAs, often disaggregated per type of bird (layer/broiler), and type of farm.
- 4) **Eggs:** This sheet shows extra calculations related to egg production.
- 5) **CBA – Broilers:** Same as "CBA – Layers" except that here we consider meat production instead of egg production as an added benefit.
- 6) **Calculations – Broilers:** Same as "Calculations – Layers" except that here we consider meat production instead of egg production as an added benefit.

- 7) **Sensitivity Analysis:** This sheet considers three alternative scenarios using the results of the CBAs, showing how the NPV and IRR changes. The first scenario assumes that costs are 20% higher than the base case; the second scenario assumes that both (i) costs are 20% higher and (ii) benefits are 20% lower. Finally, the third scenario assumes that benefits are 20% lower than the base case and the costs are 20% higher. The user can change these assumptions based on her/his needs.

Most of the data used for the CBA came from the contact point of UpM in Ghana, specifically from Dr. Gordon Akon-Yamga, Ph.D., who works for the CSIR-Science and Technology Policy Research Institute. He and his colleagues provided large datasets of indicators related to poultry production. We calculated averages based on the type of poultry (broilers or layers) and farm size, that then we used in the CBA. When data were not available, we conducted desk research. Table 11 shows the sources of the data that we found independently.

Indicator	Source
Number of workers per chicken	Okantah et al (2005)
Manure production per Chicken	Tańczuk et al (2019)
Average weight per Chicken	VFC (2022)

Table 11: Data found through desk research

Please also note that layers do not produce eggs the first 3 weeks of their lifetime of 2.5 years and that this reduction in revenues from egg production has been considered in the CBA during the first two years of the investment.

3.2.2 Results

The results of the analysis here presented consider indicators for small farms. Overall, the CBAs show that the investments are not economically viable unless levers for economic viability are considered.

Specifically, the total investment for layers and for broilers amounts to 2,567,982 GHC and 1,533,101 GHC, respectively, while the total revenues for the two investments (with no levers in place) reach 1,574,470 GHC for layers and 504,893 GHC for broilers. In other words, the economic losses of the two investments amount roughly to 1 million GHC each.

We then considered levers of economic viability in place. Specifically, a market price increase of 10%, a productivity increase of 10%, and annual subsidies for feed prices amounting to 150,000 GHC for layers production and 260,000 GHC for broilers production. The CBAs for layers and broilers are shown in

Figure 21 and Figure 22. The results for layers production indicate that the BCR is slightly positive (1.01), while the IRR reaches 44% and the NPV generates a value of more than 11,000 GHC, with a payback period of 3 years. Similar results are

generated for broilers production (BCR of 1, IRR of 32%, and same payback period), but the NPV is lower (roughly 4,500 GHC), despite the higher annual subsidies for feed prices.

Layers									
	Value	1	2	3	4	5	total	Unit	
	1/1/2023	1/1/2024	1/1/2025	1/1/2026	1/1/2027	1/1/2028			
Investment									
Capital cost									
Purchase price of the farmland	1,638.89						1,638.89	GHC	
Total purchase prices of chicks	40,120.00						40,120.00	GHC	
Operation and maintenance									
Rent price of the farm land		52.44	52.44	52.44	52.44	52.44	262.22	GHC	
Wages		1,180.00	1,180.00	1,180.00	1,180.00	1,180.00	5,900.00	GHC	
Feed prices		493,152	493,152	493,152	493,152	493,152	2,465,761.04	GHC	
Veterinary services and accessories		3,000	3,000	3,000	3,000	3,000	15,000.00	GHC	
Energy		300	300	300	300	300	1,500.00	GHC	
Water		300	300	300	300	300	1,500.00	GHC	
Transport costs		2,000	2,000	2,000	2,000	2,000	10,000.00	GHC	
Bedding		300	300	300	300	300	1,500.00	GHC	
Coop cleaning and disinfection		800	800	800	800	800	4,000.00	GHC	
Feed mixing and preparation		2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	12,500.00	GHC	
Business operation permit		100	100	100	100	100	500.00	GHC	
Rodent control		60	60	60	60	60	300.00	GHC	
Maintenance of buildings and machinery		1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	5,000.00	GHC	
Electricity		500	500	500	500	500	2,500.00	GHC	
Characoal (Heating)		0	0	0	0	0	-	GHC	
Insurance		0	0	0	0	0	-	GHC	
Total	41,759	505,245	505,245	505,245	505,245	505,245	2,567,982.15	GHC	
Added benefits									
Manure production		9,690.75	9,690.75	9,690.75	9,690.75	9,690.75	48,453.75	GHC	
Eggs production		364,133.69	364,133.69	372,735.27	372,735.27	372,735.27	1,846,473.19	GHC	
Required subsidies for feed prices		150,000.00	150,000.00	150,000.00	150,000.00	150,000.00	750,000.00	GHC	
Total	-	523,824	523,824	532,426	532,426	532,426	2,644,927	GHC	
Net Benefit	(41,758.89)	18,579.79	18,579.79	27,181.37	27,181.37	27,181.37	76,944.79	GHC	
IRR	44%								
BCR	1.01								
NPV	11,412.27								
Payback period	3								
First value above 100%	101%	0%	0.96	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.03		
		0	0	0	3	0	0		

Figure 21: CBA Layers (Considering levers for economic viability in place)

Broilers								
	Value	1	2	3	4	5	total	Unit
	1/1/2023	1/1/2024	1/1/2025	1/1/2026	1/1/2027	1/1/2028		
Investment								
Capital cost								GHC
Purchase price of the farmland	1,458.33						1,458.33	GHC
Total purchase prices of chicks	464,100.00						464,100.00	GHC
Operation and maintenance								
Rent price of the farm land		46.67	46.67	46.67	46.67	46.67	233.33	GHC
Wages		1,050.00	1,050.00	1,050.00	1,050.00	1,050.00	5,250.00	GHC
Feed prices		201,552	201,552	201,552	201,552	201,552	1,007,759.55	GHC
Veterinary services and accessories		3,000	3,000	3,000	3,000	3,000	15,000.00	GHC
Energy		300	300	300	300	300	1,500.00	GHC
Water		300	300	300	300	300	1,500.00	GHC
Transport costs		2,000	2,000	2,000	2,000	2,000	10,000.00	GHC
Bedding		300	300	300	300	300	1,500.00	GHC
Coop cleaning and disinfection		800	800	800	800	800	4,000.00	GHC
Feed mixing and preparation		2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	12,500.00	GHC
Business operation permit		100	100	100	100	100	500.00	GHC
Rodent control		60	60	60	60	60	300.00	GHC
Maintenance of buildings and machinery		1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	5,000.00	GHC
Electricity		500	500	500	500	500	2,500.00	GHC
Charcoal (Heating)		0	0	0	0	0	-	GHC
Insurance		0	0	0	0	0	-	GHC
Total	465,558	213,509	213,509	213,509	213,509	213,509	1,533,101.22	GHC
Added benefits								
Manure production		8,623.13	8,623.13	8,623.13	8,623.13	8,623.13	34,492.50	GHC
Meat production		142,296.00	142,296.00	142,296.00	142,296.00	142,296.00	569,184.00	GHC
Required subsidies for feed prices		260,000.00	260,000.00	260,000.00	260,000.00	260,000.00	1,040,000.00	GHC
Total	-	410,919	410,919	410,919	410,919	410,919	603,677	GHC
Net Benefit	(465,558.33)	197,410.55	197,410.55	197,410.55	197,410.55	197,410.55	(929,424.72)	GHC
IRR	32%							
BCR	1.00							
NPV	4,525.26							
Payback period	3							
First value above 100%	111%	0%	0.61	0.92	1.11	1.25	1.34	
		0	0	0	3	0	0	

Figure 22: CBA Broilers (Considering levers for economic viability in place)

3.3 CS13 – Milk (EU, Africa, America)

3.3.1 Overview of the mathematical model

The quantitative, mathematical model was created following the structure of the CLD (see Figure 24). The same variables are considered, as well as the same dynamics of change. On the other hand, the mathematical model includes several additional variables that are required for (i) quantification and (ii) simulation of alternative scenarios.

The structure of the model is presented first, and scenario options are introduced next.

Milk production

Milk production is estimated considering the number of cows and the average milk productivity per cow. It is a straightforward way to estimate the total output of milk from the entire herd. On the other hand, productivity can be modified to account for several intervention options, including feed quality, geniting improvements, mechanization and robotization, as well as by accounting for the impact of climate change (e.g. temperature) on cows.

$$\text{production} = \text{number of cows} * \text{milk productivity per cow}$$

The number of cows is estimated using a minimum (MIN) function to determine the optimal number of cows for the farm. It considers the desired number of cows, adjusted by the effect of profitability on farm size, while ensuring that the result does not surpass the maximum number of cows the farm can accommodate. This approach helps balance the farm's financial goals with practical constraints on herd size.

$$\text{number of cows} = \text{MIN}(\text{desired number of cows} * \text{effect of profitability on farm size}, \text{maximum number of cows})$$

Production costs

Total Cost of Production is the sum of various cost components, including production cost, labor cost, food safety and food security costs, and animal welfare and animal health costs. This equation represents the comprehensive cost structure associated with milk production.

$$\text{Total Cost of Production} = \text{Production Cost} + \text{Labor Cost} + \text{Food Safety and Food Security} + \text{Animal Welfare and Animal Health}$$

Production costs are estimated for two different scenarios, a base case and an alternative case. This allows for flexibility in considering different cost structures depending on specific conditions or policies, with the baseline cost per liter used as a default. Production costs are calculated based on production and a unit cost per kg of milk.

Labor Cost is calculated as the product of the salary level and the employment level. Employment is based on the labor intensity per cow, and changes in alignment with the size of a farm. This equation represents the overall cost associated with the labor employed in milk production.

$$\text{Labor Cost} = \text{Salary Level} \times \text{Employment}$$

Profitability of Milk Production is calculated as the difference between revenues from milk production and the total cost of production. This equation provides a measure of the financial gain or loss from the milk production activities.

$$\text{Profitability of Milk Production} = \text{Revenues from Milk Production} - \text{Total Cost of Production}$$

Additional indicators are included in the model, such as the aggregate cost per kg, and the profit (or loss) per kg of milk produced.

These equations collectively help in understanding and managing the financial aspects of milk production, taking into account labor, revenue, and various costs associated with the production process.

Manure and emissions

Manure creation is calculated as the product of the number of cows and the manure creation per cow. This equation estimates the total amount of manure produced by the herd, and is used to estimate emissions, as well as manure concentration, two indicators that can be used to determine constraints to the further expansion of farms.

$$\text{Manure Creation} = \text{Number of Cows} \times \text{Manure Creation per Cow}$$

The maximum number of cows is determined by multiplying the maximum concentration allowed by national legislation (if present) by the ratio of hectares per ton of manure. It calculates the maximum number of cows that can be sustained on the given land area while adhering to the maximum allowed concentration and considering the manure creation per cow.

$$\text{Maximum Number of Cows} = \frac{\text{Maximum Concentration Allowed} \times \text{Total Land Area}}{\text{Manure Creation per Cow}}$$

CO₂e emissions are estimated as the sum of various components, each contributing to the total carbon emissions.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CO}_2\text{e Emissions} = & \\ & \text{Emissions per Cow} \times \text{Number of Cows} \\ & + \text{Land Cover Change (Deforestation)} \times \text{Emissions per Hectare} \\ & - \text{Land Restoration} \times \text{Emissions per Hectare} \\ & - \text{Reforestation} \times \text{Emissions per Hectare} \\ & - \text{Renewable Energy} \end{aligned}$$

- Emissions per cow represent carbon emissions associated with each individual cow. a more refined formulation could be used, that considers both enteric fermentation and emissions from liquid, dry and wet manure.
- Land cover change (deforestation) emissions represent the contribution to emissions due to changes in land cover, specifically deforestation when a farm expands.
- Land restoration carbon sequestration represents the reduction in emissions due to land restoration efforts.
- Reforestation carbon sequestration represents the contribution to emissions reduction due to reforestation efforts.
- Renewable energy emission reduction represents the reduction in emissions due to the use of renewable energy sources, substituting fossil fuel use.

This set of equations allows for a comprehensive calculation of carbon emissions associated with the livestock operation, considering emissions from individual cows, land-use changes, and efforts towards land restoration, reforestation, and the use of renewable energy. The carbon intensity (or productivity), an additional indicator in the model, provides a normalized measure, allowing for comparisons relative to production.

Trade dynamics

Trade dynamics are estimated using national (as opposed to farm) production. Total milk production at the country level is calculated as the product of production and the number of farms in the country. This equation provides the total milk production in a given country, based on the production per farm and the number of farms.

$$\text{Total Milk Production (country)} = \text{Production per farm} \times \text{Number of Farms (country)}$$

The demand to supply ratio is calculated as the ratio of milk demand to total milk production in a given country. This ratio provides insight into how well the production in a given country meets the local demand for milk. Milk import or export are estimated by subtracting domestic production from domestic demand.

Built-in scenarios

The model allows to simulate several alternative scenarios. The variables currently considered for alternative parametrizations are: (i) milk productivity, (ii) production cost per liter, (iii) salary per worker, (iv) public subsidies and (v) market price, (vi) maximum nutrient concentration allowed, and (vii) farm size.

Below, a tree diagram presents the chain of causality impacted by changes in the desired number of cows per farm.

Figure 23: Tree diagram presenting the chain of causality impacted by a change in the number of cows per farm.

Figure 24: Screenshot of the mathematical model.

3.3.2 Summary of results

We have analyzed two different scenarios, applied to each of the three countries studied (Germany, USA and Algeria).

Specifically, the Business As Usual (BAU) assumes no changes to the current practices. This scenario assumes that each country continues its current trajectory without any significant alterations to production, trade, or social conditions related to the dairy industry. In other words, each country produces according to its current practices, and trade dynamics remain unchanged.

In the alternative scenario there are specific changes in production and trade patterns designed to achieve a better trade balance and align production with domestic demand. The implications are different for different countries. In the case of Algeria, production is adjusted to be sufficient to meet domestic demand (higher productivity and larger number of cows per farm). This implies that Algeria is working towards self-sufficiency in dairy production, aiming to produce enough to satisfy its own consumption needs. Further, this scenario also includes an aim to improve social conditions in Algeria (via higher salaries). Concerning Germany and the USA, in contrast to the BAU case, where production remains unchanged, the alternative scenario involves a reduction in production. This reduction is aligned with national demand in these countries, suggesting a more intentional approach to avoid overproduction and align production with local consumption patterns.

The alternative scenario implies changes in the trade dynamics between countries. With Algeria producing more to meet its domestic demand, and with improved social conditions, there will be a decreased reliance on imports. The Government of Algeria has, in fact, reopened the imports of dairy cattle in 2022 to reduce the imports of milk powder and improve local milk production (USDA, 2022). Nevertheless, the implications of this policy have not been clearly identified, calling for a modelling approach that can allow understanding the socio-economic implications that would arise from a decrease in imports of dairy products.

Meanwhile, Germany and the USA, with reduced production, will experience changes in their export capacities.

The main assumptions used in the alternative scenario, are as follows:

- Algeria:

- An increase in milk productivity from 3,550 kg/cow/year to 4,850 kg/cow/year (+36%).
 - An increase in the average farm size from 18 to 50 cows (2.7x increase).
 - An increase of the salary level from USD 2,430 per person per year to USD 16,000 (6.6x increase).
- Germany: a reduction in the average farm size from 313 to 244 cows, or reduction of farms in the range of 20%.
 - USA: a reduction in the average farm size from 500 to 450 cows, or reduction of farms in the range of 10%.

Results show that Algeria would produce at higher unit cost (1.01 USD/kg, as opposed to 0.81 USD/kg in the BAU scenario), while at the same time improving profitability (-0.1 USD/kg, as opposed to -0.29 USD/kg in the BAU scenario). The cost increase is primarily the result of higher labor costs, while the reduction is primarily due to higher productivity per cow. Overall, annual milk production per farm could increase to 243,000 kg in the alternative scenario, as opposed to 64,000 kg in the BAU case. Total annual milk production at the country level would increase to 6.7 billion kg in the alternative scenario, against 1.77 billion kg in the BAU.

In the case of Germany, production per farm would decline to 2.4 million kg/year, compared to 3.08 million kg/year in the BAU. At the national level the reduction reaches 8.3 billion kg/year. Reduced production results in lower CO₂ emissions, in the range of 0.9 million kg/year.

Similarly, for the USA, production per farm would decline to 5.09 million kg/year, compared to 5.65 million kg/year in the BAU. At the national level the reduction reaches 10.8 billion kg/year. Reduced production results in lower CO₂ emissions, in the range of 0.95 million kg/year.

3.4 CS14 – Pork (Brazil)

Based on conversations with UPM, we focused on forecasted changes in land-use in the Cerrado region (Brazil). We used the Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST) suite of models to quantify changes in carbon storage, habitat quality, annual water yield, sediment and nutrient export, and flood risk mitigation. The analysis indicates that the expansion of agricultural areas replacing forestland and grassland will deteriorate those selected ecosystem services.

3.4.1 Model set up

3.4.1.1 Study area

The study area of this analysis is the Cerrado region in Brazil (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Location of Cerrado

3.4.1.2 Coordination system

Based on world project coordinate system called "V WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator -- Spherical Mercator – EPSG: 3857"

Here is the detail of the coordinate system:

```

PROJCS["WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator",
  GEOGCS["WGS 84",
    DATUM["WGS_1984",
      SPHEROID["WGS 84",6378137,298.257223563,
        AUTHORITY["EPSG","7030"]],
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","6326"]],
    PRIMEM["Greenwich",0,
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","8901"]],
    UNIT["degree",0.0174532925199433,
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","9122"]],
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","4326"]],
    PROJECTION["Mercator_1SP"],
    PARAMETER["central_meridian",0],
    PARAMETER["scale_factor",1],
    PARAMETER["false_easting",0],
    PARAMETER["false_northing",0],
    UNIT["metre",1,
      AUTHORITY["EPSG","9001"]],
    AXIS["X",EAST],
    AXIS["Y",NORTH],
    EXTENSION["PROJ4", "+proj=merc +a=6378137 +b=6378137 +lat_ts=0.0 +lon_0=0.0 +x_0=0.0 +y_0=0 +k=1.0 +units=m
+nadgrids=@null +wktext +no_defs"],
    AUTHORITY["EPSG","3857"]]

```

3.4.1.3 Land Cover maps

The MapBiomass 10 meters BETA land use and land cover (LULC) of 20224 has been used in this study. The resolution of the map has been changed to 100m. Using the InVEST Scenario Generator Proximity Based, we created two future LULCs based on projections of the Ministry of Agriculture where agriculture will expand by 17.1% in the next 10 years (Ministério da Agricultura e Pecuária, 2023). Using this forecast, we considered a scenario where agriculture will expand replacing only grassland, and a second one where agriculture will replace only forests.

Figure 26, Figure 27, and Figure 28 show the LULC in 2022, and with a 17.1% expansion of agriculture into grassland and forestland, respectively. We also modelled a more moderate expansion of agriculture (4.2%) into grassland and forestland, shown in Figure 29 and Figure 30, respectively.

Figure 26: Land-use map of Cerrado in 2022

⁴ <https://brasil.mapbiomas.org/en/mapbiomas-cobertura-10m/>

Figure 27: Land-use map of Cerrado – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Grassland loss

Figure 28: Land-use map of Cerrado – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Forest Loss

Figure 29: Land-use map of Cerrado – 4.2% expansion of agriculture - Grassland loss

Figure 30: Land-use map of Cerrado – 4.2% expansion of agriculture - Forest loss

3.4.1.4 Software and simulation

The ecosystem services map simulation has been performed using InVEST Software V.3.9.0 (<https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/invest/>). The inputs spatial data for the InVEST model have been prepared by utilizing QGIS-OSGeoW-3.4.2-1 (qgis.org/downloads/). The tabulated data will be managed and prepared in Ms. Excel V. 2016.

3.4.2 Carbon Storage

3.4.2.1 Input data preparation and processing

1. Land use/land cover maps – see section 3.4.1.3

2. Carbon Pools - Table of LULC classes, containing data on carbon stored in each of the four fundamental pools for each LULC class

- Carbon above ground: The values of carbon density in aboveground mass (Tons/ha) of each land-use type are shown in Table 12
- Carbon below ground: The values of carbon density in belowground mass (Tons/ha) of each land use-type are shown in Table 12
- Carbon stored in organic matter: The values of carbon density in dead mass (Tons/ha) of each land-use type are shown in in Table 12
- Carbon stored in soil: The values of carbon density in dead mass (Tons/ha) of each land-use type are shown in in Table 12

The unit of measurement for these coefficients is Tons/ha. Average carbon coefficients values have been found in the "2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories" report, chapter 4 "Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use" (IPCC, 2006).

lucode	C_above	C_below	C_soil	C_dead
3	44.744	25.05664	1.36	0
4	9.87	4.7376	1.36	0
5	52.64	42.112	1.36	0
9	12.69	2.3688	1.36	0
11	9.87	2.6649	1.36	0
12	8.46	4.7376	1.36	0
15	2.961	1.65816	1.36	0
19	2.961	1.65816	1.36	0
21	4.23	2.3688	1.36	0
23	0	0	0	0
24	0	0	0	0
25	0	0	0	0
29	0	0	0	0
30	0	0	0	0
33	0	0	0	0
36	2.961	1.65816	1.36	0

Table 12: Carbon pools

3.4.2.2 Results

Figure 31, Figure 32, and Figure 33 show the amount of carbon stored in Tons in each pixel using the LULC 2022, and the scenarios with a 17.1% expansion of agriculture into grassland and forestland, respectively. They are a sum of all the carbon pools provided by the biophysical table.

Figure 34 and Figure 35 show the amount of carbon stored in Tons in each pixel using the LULC scenarios with a 4.2% expansion of agriculture into grassland and forestland, respectively.

Figure 31: Carbon model outputs (LULC 2022)

Figure 32: Carbon model outputs – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Grassland loss

Figure 33: Carbon model outputs – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Forest Loss

Figure 34: Carbon model outputs – 4.2% expansion of agriculture – Grassland Loss

Figure 35: Carbon model outputs – 4.2% expansion of agriculture - Forest Loss

Scenario	Carbon Stored (Tons)	Change from 2022
2022	4,024,582,855	
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	3,984,135,540	-1.01%
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing forest	3,717,252,408	-7.64%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	4,014,648,423	-0.25%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing forest	3,949,098,157	-1.88%

Table 13: Carbon storage statistics

As Table 13 shows, the tons of carbon storage are expected to decrease by roughly 1% when agriculture expands by 17.1% replacing grassland and by more than 7.5% when it replaces forest. These changes are more contained under the scenarios where agriculture expands by 4.2%.

3.4.3 Habitat Quality

3.4.3.1 Input data preparation and processing

5. Land use/land cover maps - see section 3.4.1.3

6. Threat Data - several major threads such as cropland areas, urban areas, and the road network have been identified as the threat sources to the natural habitat and biodiversity. See table below (Table 14). See Table 26 for data sources

N.	Threat name	Max_Distance	Weighted value	Decay function
9	Forest Plantation	6 km	0.7	Linear
15	Pasture	4 km	0.7	Linear
19	Temporary Crop	4 km	0.7	Linear
21	Mosaic of Uses	0.5 km	0.3	Linear
24	Urban Area	7.1 km	0.7	Linear
30	Mining	5.6 km	1	Linear
36	Perennial Crop	4 km	0.7	Linear

Table 14: Table of threat (maximum distance, weighted value, and decay function) for InVEST simulation

7. Sensitivity of land cover types to each threat - characterizing each LULC type to be habitat or non-habitat and the type's sensitivity to the threats (shown in Table 15, see Table 27 for data sources). The table contains the following fields:

7.1 LULC - codes identify each LULC class

7.2 Name - abbreviation of each LULC class

7.3 Habitat - score characterizing each LULC as habitat or non-habitat. The values of 0 and 1 are used for the purpose, in which 0 for non-habitat class and 1 for habitat class of LULC.

L_plantation_9, L_pasture_15, L_crop_19, L_mosaic_21, L_urban_24, L_mining_30, L_crop_36 - these are columns for the relative sensitivity of LULC classes to the threat. In this case, L_plantation_9 contains the value for the sensitivity of each LULC class to "Forest Plantation" threat, L_pasture_15 sensitivity to - "Pasture", L_crop_19 sensitivity to - "Temporary Crop", L_mosaic_21 sensitivity to "Mosaic of Uses", L_urban_24

sensitivity to “Urban Area”, L_mining_30 sensitivity to “Mining”, and L_crop_36 sensitivity to “Perennial Crop”.

LULC	HABITAT	Plantation _9_c	Pasture _15_c	Crop _19_c	Mosaic _21_c	Urban _24_c	mining_30 _c	Crop _36_c	Plantation _9_c
3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
9	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
12	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
15	0.3	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	1	0.03	0.03
19	0.3	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	1	0.03	0.03
21	0.3	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	1	0.03	0.03
23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
33	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.8	1	0.7	0.7
36	0.3	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.69	1	0.03	0.03

Table 15: Table of Sensitivity of land cover types to each threat for InVEST simulation

1. Half-saturation constraint – the default value of 0.5 was used

3.4.3.2 Results

Figure 36, Figure 37, and Figure 38 show the relative level of habitat quality in Cerrado in 2022, and with a 17.1% expansion of agriculture into grassland and forestland, respectively. Higher numbers indicate better habitat quality vis-a-vis the distribution of habitat quality across the rest of the landscape. Areas on the landscape that are not habitat get a quality score of 0. The habitat scores values range from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates the highest habitat suitability.

Figure 39 and Figure 40 show the relative level of habitat quality in Cerrado considering the LULC scenarios with a 4.2% expansion of agriculture into grassland and forestland, respectively.

Figure 36: Scores of habitat quality – 2022

Figure 37: Scores of habitat quality – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Grassland loss

Figure 38: Scores of habitat quality – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Forest Loss

Figure 39: Scores of habitat quality – 4.2% expansion of agriculture - Grassland Loss

Figure 40: Scores of habitat quality – 4.2% expansion of agriculture - Forest Loss

Scenario	Mean of HQ	Change from 2022
2022	0.3680	
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	0.3630	-1.38%
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing forest	0.3572	-2.96%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	0.3648	-0.88%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing forest	0.3647	-0.91%

Table 16: mean of HQ per year

As Table 16 shows, the mean of habitat quality is expected to decrease by roughly 1.5% when agriculture expands by 17.1% replacing grassland and by more than 3% when it replaces forest. These changes are more contained under the scenarios where agriculture expands by 4.2%.

3.4.4 Annual Water Yield

3.4.4.1 Input data preparation and processing

- 1. Precipitation**– A GIS raster dataset with a non-zero value for average annual precipitation for each cell. Its value is expressed in millimeters. The average precipitation (in mm) from 1970 to 2022 downloaded from WorldClim version 2 (www.worldclim.com) was used for this study. The dataset was released on the first of June 2016. The original spatial resolution of the data is 30 seconds x 30 seconds (which is approximately 1 km²).
- 2. Average annual reference evapotranspiration (ET₀)** – A GIS raster dataset with an annual average evapotranspiration value for each cell in millimeters. Reference evapotranspiration is the potential loss of water from the soil by both evaporation from the soil and transpiration by healthy alfalfa (or grass) if sufficient water is available. Its value is in millimeters. In this study, the global evapotranspiration of reference crops was adopted from “Global Aridity Index and Potential Evapotranspiration (ET₀) Climate Database v2”. The spatial resolution of the data is 30 arc-seconds (approximately 1km at the equator). The dataset can be found here:
(https://figshare.com/articles/Global_Aridity_Index_and_Potential_Evapotranspiration_ET0_Climate_Database_v2/7504448/3)
- 3. Root restricting layer depth** – These terms were defined as an average root restricting layer depth value for each cell. It is the soil depth at which root penetration is strangler inhibited because of physical or chemical characteristics. Root restricting layer depth may be obtained from some soil maps. If a root restricting layer depth is not available, soil depth can be used as a proxy. If several soil horizons are detailed, the root restricting layer depth is the sum of the depths of non-restrictive soil horizons. Its value is in millimeters. In this study, the absolute depth to bedrock downloaded from soilgrid.org stored in cm was used to present for root restricting layer depth
- 4. Plant Available Water Content** – Plant Available Water Content (PAWC) is the fraction of water that can be stored in the soil profile that is available for plants’ use. PAWC can be measured from 0 to 1. The format of PAWC for the model is a GIS raster dataset. Plant available water content is a fraction obtained from some standard soil maps. It is defined as the difference between the fraction of volumetric field capacity and permanent wilting point. The plant available water content is often available as a volumetric value (mm). To obtain the fraction it is necessary to divide it by soil depth. Soil characteristic layers are estimated by performing a weighted average from all horizons within a soil component. If PAWC is not available, raster grids obtained from polygon shapefiles of weight average soil texture (%clay, %sand, %silt) and soil porosity will be needed. In this study, the average calculation of available soil

water capacity of the volumetric fraction of 2.0 (pF 2.0) from 0 to 2 m was used to represent the plant available water contents for water yield model simulation.

5. Land use/land cover maps – see section 3.4.1.3

6. Watersheds – This is the polygon shapefile representing the watersheds

7. Biophysical Table – A table of land use/land cover (LULC) classes, containing data on biophysical coefficients used in this tool. These data are attributes of each LULC class rather than attributes of individual cells in the raster map. This table contains 5 variables included: [1] *lucode* (*Land use code*), [2] *LULC_desc*, [3] *LULC_veg*, [4] *root_depth*, and [5] K_c . Table 17 shows the biophysical table used in this study. Values have been derived from Hoy et al. (2015).

7.1 Lucode (Land use code): Unique integer for each LULC class (e.g., 1 for forest, 3 for grassland, etc.), must match the LULC raster above.

7.2 LULC_desc: Descriptive name of land use/land cover class (optional).

7.3 LULC_veg: Values must be 1 for vegetated land use except wetlands, and 0 for all other land uses, including wetlands, urban, water bodies, etc.

7.4 root_depth: The maximum root depth for vegetated land use classes, given in integer millimeters. This is often given as the depth at which 95% of a vegetation type’s root biomass occurs. For land uses where the generic Budyko curve is not utilized (i.e. where evapotranspiration is calculated based on the equation below, rooting depth is not needed). In these cases, the rooting depth should be set to NA. The equation can be found here in:

$$AET(x) = \text{Min}(K_c(\ell x) \cdot ET_0(x), P(x))$$

where

$ET_0(x)$ is the reference evapotranspiration,
 $K_c(\ell x)$ is the evaporation factor for each land use and land cover.
 K_c factor is the plant evapotranspiration coefficient for each LULC class. It is used to convert from reference evaporation to potential evaporation for each land use.

7.5 K_c : The plant evapotranspiration coefficient for each LULC class, used to obtain potential evapotranspiration by using plant physiological characteristics to modify the reference evapotranspiration, which is based on alfalfa. The evapotranspiration coefficient is thus a decimal in the range of 0 to 1.5 (some crops evapotranspire more than alfalfa in some very wet tropical regions and where water is always available).

lucode	LULC_veg	root_depth	Kc
3	1	7300	1.3
4	1	2600	1
5	1	500	1
9	1	7000	0.9
11	1	500	1
12	1	2600	1
15	1	2600	1
19	1	2100	0.65
21	1	2100	0.65
23	0	100	0.05
24	0	100	0.05
25	0	100	0.05
29	0	100	0.05
30	0	100	0.05
33	0	2000	1
36	1	2100	0.65

Table 17: biophysical table used in this study.

Z parameter - Z is an empirical constant that captures the local precipitation pattern and hydrogeological characteristics, with typical values ranging from 1 to 30. It is corresponding to the seasonal distribution of precipitation. This parameter is mainly used for model calibration, however, in this study, there is no observed data for the model calibration. Therefore, the recommended default value of the Z parameter equals to 5 was used.

3.4.4.2 Results

The main output is a table containing biophysical output values per watershed, with the following attributes:

- *wyield_vol* (m³): Volume of water yield in the watershed.

Scenario	wyield_vol (m3)	Change from 2022
2022	553,611,637,376	
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	568,148,995,856	2.63%
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing forest	575,049,371,416	3.87%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	557,583,199,411	0.72%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing forest	558,802,011,217	0.94%

Table 18: water yield results

As Table 18 shows, water yield is expected to increase by more than 2.5% when agriculture expands by 17.1% replacing grassland and by almost 4% when it replaces forest, compared to 2022. Such an increase could make water more available for different uses (e.g. irrigation). However, it could also raise the risk of floods or water-borne diseases, and further research is needed to understand the gravity of such threats. These changes are more contained under the scenarios where agriculture expands by 4.2%.

3.4.5 Sediment and Nutrient Export

3.4.5.1 Input data preparation and processing (Sediment)

- 1. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) Raster** – DEM: the hydrologically conditioned elevation dataset which is distributed by Hydrosheds (<https://www.hydrosheds.org/>) was downloaded on December 4th, 2023 for InVEST sediment model input. The data was prepared for hydrological model input purpose mainly for flow direction, accumulation simulation, river network and biome delineation. The original spatial resolution of the dataset 30 arcsec.
- 2. Rainfall Erosivity Index I Raster** – A GIS raster dataset containing erosivity index for each cell. This variable depends on the intensity and duration of rainfall in the area of interest. The greater the intensity and duration of the rain storm, the higher the erosion potential. The erosivity index is widely used, but in case of its absence, there are methods and equations to help generate a grid using climatic data. Its value is MJ*mm*(ha*h*yr)⁻¹. The R factor dataset in spatial resolution of 25 km downloaded from <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-017-02142-7> was employed for this study. The technical report of the data also can be found here: https://static-content.springer.com/esm/art%3A10.1038%2Fs41467-017-02142-7/MediaObjects/41467_2017_2142_MOESM1_ESM.pdf

3. **Soil Erodibility (K) Raster** – A raster dataset of soil erodibility. It is a measure of the susceptibility of soil particles to detachment and transport by rainfall and runoff. Its value is in $T.ha.h.(ha.MJ.mm)^{-1}$. The spatial resolution of 25 km of soil erodibility download from <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-017-02142-7> was used in this study.
4. **Land use/land cover maps** – see section 3.4.1.3
5. **Watershed Polygons** – See Annual Water Yield Inputs
6. **Biophysical Table** – A table containing model information corresponding to each of the LULC types (see Table 19). These data were derived from Vallet et al. (2016). We also used values utilized for the Department of Caquetá which have been readapted for Cerrado. The table has the following field:
 - 6.1 **Lucode (Land use code)** – unique integer to identify each LULC class.
 - 6.2 **LULC_desc** – nominal name for each LULC class.
 - 6.3 **usle_c** – It refers to cover management factor or sometimes called cropping management factor (C factor) for the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE). This value is used to calculate the cover management in USLE. The C factor represents the effect of surface cover and roughness on soil erosion. The cover factor is the most common factor used to assess the impact of Best Management Practices (BMPs) on reducing erosion because the C factor represents the effect of land use on soil erosion (Renard, 1997). Erosion control blankets and surface applied BMPs such as blown straw are represented as C factors within RUSLE. By definition, $C = 1$ under standard fallow conditions. As the surface cover is added to the soil, the C factor value approaches zero. For example, a C factor of 0.20 signifies that 20% of the amount of erosion will occur compared to continuous fallow conditions. C factors vary from region to region because they are strongly influenced by different Rainfall Erosivity Index (R factors) (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978). In the InVEST model, its value is stored in a float value ranging from 0 to 1.
 - 6.4 **usle_p** – It refers to management practice, support or conservation practice factor (P factor) in USLE. The P factor reflects the impact of support practices on the average annual erosion rate. P is the ratio of soil loss with a support factor to that with straight row farming up and down slope. Strip-cropping, contouring, and terracing are all activities that are considered support practices by RUSLE. The support factor is unitless and its value is stored in a float value ranging from 0 to 1.

lucode	usle_c	usle_p
3	0.015	1
4	0.381	1
5	1	1
9	0.025	1
11	1	1
12	0.381	1
15	0.381	1
19	0.412	1
21	0.025	1
23	0.883	1
24	0.883	1
25	0.883	1
29	0.883	1
30	0.883	1
33	1	1
36	0.412	1

Table 19: Biophysical table annual sediment delivery ratio

7. **Threshold flow accumulation** – The number of upstream cells that must flow into a cell before it is considered part of a stream, which is used to classify streams from the DEM. This threshold directly affects the expression of hydrologic connectivity and the sediment export result: when a flow path reaches the stream, sediment deposition stops, and the sediment exported is assumed to reach the catchment outlet. It is important to choose this value carefully, so modeled streams come as close to reality as possible. The value of 300 was used in this simulation.
8. **Borseli K parameter (kb) and Borseli IC0 parameter (IC₀)** – two calibration parameters that determine the shape of the relationship between hydrologic connectivity (the degree of connection from patches of land to the stream) and the sediment delivery ratio (percentage of soil loss that actually reaches the stream). The default values of kb=2 and IC₀=0.5 were used in the simulation.
9. **Max SDR value (SDRmax)** – the maximum SDR that a pixel can reach, which is a function of the soil texture. More specifically, it is defined as the fraction of topsoil particles finer than coarse sand. The default value of 0.8 was used in this simulation.

10. Maximum L Value – The maximum allowed value of the slope length parameter (L) in the LS factor. Its default value is 122

3.4.5.2 Input data preparation and processing (Nutrient)

- 1. DEM Raster** – See input section of Annual Sediment Delivery Ratio
- 2. Land use/land cover maps** – see section 3.4.1.3
- 3. Nutrient Runoff Proxy Raster (Precipitation)** – A GIS raster dataset with a non-zero value for average annual precipitation for each cell. Its value is in millimetres. In this study, the data was utilized the same precipitation dataset as employing in water yield model.
- 4. Watershed Polygons** – See Annual Water Yield Inputs
- 5. Biophysical Table** – A table of land use/land cover (LULC) classes, containing data on water quality coefficients used in this tool (Table 20). NOTE: these data are attributes of each LULC class rather than attributes of individual cells in the raster map. These data were derived from Kulsoontornrat & Ongsomwang (2021). The table has the following field:
 - 5.1 Lucode** – unique identifier for each LULC class.
 - 5.2 load_n / load_p** – The nutrient loading for each land use. If nitrogen is being evaluated, supply values in load_n, for phosphorus, supply values in load_p. The potential for terrestrial loading of water quality impairing constituents is based on nutrient export coefficients. The nutrient loading values are given as integer values and have units of kg. ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.
 - 5.3 eff_n / eff_p** – The vegetation filtering value per pixel size for each LULC class, as an integer percent between zero and 1. If nitrogen is being evaluated, supply values in eff_n, for phosphorus, supply values in eff_p. This field identifies the capacity of vegetation to retain nutrients, as a percentage of the amount of nutrient flowing into a cell from upslope. For example if the user has data describing that a wetland of 5000 m² retains 82% of nitrogen, then the retention efficiency that she/he should input into this field for eff_n is equal to $(82/5000 * (\text{cell size})^2)$. In the simplest case, when data for each LULC type are not available, high values (60 to 80) may be assigned to all natural vegetation types (such as forests, natural pastures, wetlands, or prairie), indicating that 60-80% of nutrients are retained. An intermediary value also may be assigned to features such as contour buffers. All LULC classes that have no filtering capacity, such as pavement, can be assigned a value of zero

5.4 *crit_len_n (and/or crit_len_p)* (at least one is required): The distance after which is assumed that a patch of a particular LULC type retains nutrient at its maximum capacity, given in meters. If nutrients travel a distance smaller than the retention length, the retention efficiency will be less than the maximum value *eff_x*, following an exponential decay. This value represents the typical distance necessary to reach the maximum retention efficiency. It was introduced in the model to remove any sensitivity to the resolution of the LULC raster. In the absence of local data for land uses that are not forest or grass, it is possible to simply set the retention length constant, equal to the pixel size: this will result in the maximum retention efficiency being reached within a distance of one pixel only.

5.5 *proportion_subsurface_n or p (optional)*: The proportion of dissolved nutrients over the total amount of nutrients, expressed as floating-point value (ratio) between 0 and 1. By default, this value should be set to 0, indicating that all nutrients are delivered via surface flow.

lucode	load_n	eff_n	load_p	eff_p	crit_len_n	crit_len_p	proportion_subsurface_n
3	2.89	0.51	0.077	0.51	100	100	0
4	5.855	0.36	0.583	0.36	100	100	0
5	13.361	0.13	4.195	0.13	100	100	0
9	5.855	0.36	0.583	0.36	100	100	0
11	13.361	0.13	4.195	0.13	100	100	0
12	5.855	0.36	0.583	0.36	100	100	0
15	5.855	0.36	0.583	0.36	100	100	0
19	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0
21	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0
23	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
24	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
25	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
29	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
30	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
33	0.035	0.05	0.001	0.05	100	100	0
36	11.925	0.13	1.14	0.13	100	100	0

Table 20: Biophysical table – Annual Nutrient Delivery Ratio

6. Threshold flow accumulation value: Integer value defining the number of upstream pixels that must flow into a pixel before it is considered part of a stream. This is used to generate a stream layer from the DEM. This threshold expresses where hydrologic routing is discontinued, i.e. where retention stops and the remaining pollutant will be exported to the stream. The value of 100 was used in this simulation.

7. Subsurface maximum retention efficiency (Nitrogen or phosphorus): the maximum nutrient retention efficiency that can be reached through subsurface flow, a value between 0 and 1. This field characterizes the retention due to biochemical degradation in soils. The default value of 0.8 was used for this study.

8. Subsurface_crit_len (Nitrogen or phosphorus) (in meter): the distance (traveled subsurface and downslope) after which is assumed that soil retains nutrient at its maximum capacity. If dissolved nutrients travel a distance smaller than subsurface_crit_len, the retention efficiency is lower than the maximum value defined above. The value of 100 was used in this simulation.

9. Borselli k parameter: calibration parameter that determines the shape of the relationship between hydrologic connectivity (the degree of connection from patches of land to the stream) and the sediment delivery ratio (percentage of soil loss that actually reaches the stream). The default value is 2.

3.4.5.3 Results

Scenario	Sediment export (tons)	Change from 2022
2022	2,998,357,414	
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	3,003,460,056	0.17%
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing forest	3,200,404,563	6.74%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	2,997,931,013	-0.01%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing forest	3,052,790,819	1.82%

Table 21: Sediment export statistics

Scenario	Nitrogen export (kg)	Change from 2022
2022	331,400,982	
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	339,897,527	2.56%
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing forest	349,347,815	5.42%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	333,591,856	0.66%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing forest	335,161,149	1.13%

Table 22: Nitrogen Export Statistics

Scenario	Phosphorus export (kg)	Change from 2022
2022	35,356,458	
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	36,167,043	2.29%
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing forest	37,319,367	5.55%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	35,567,457	0.60%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing forest	35,769,533	1.17%

Table 23: Phosphorus Export Statistics

As Table 21 shows that sediment export (tons) is not expected to change substantially under the LULC scenario where 17.1% of agriculture replaces grassland, but it would increase by almost than 7% when it replaces forest, compared to 2022. When agriculture expands by only 4.2% into grassland the changes are minimal (even negative, but so small that they are not relevant), while when it expands into forestland there is an increase in sediment export by almost 2%.

Table 22 and Table 23 show that the total export of both Nitrogen and Phosphorus (kg) would increase by roughly 2.5% under the LULC scenario where 17.1% of agriculture replaces grassland. This figure would double in case agriculture would expand by 17.1% at the cost of forest land. These changes are more contained under the scenarios where agriculture expands by 4.2%.

3.4.6 Urban Flood Risk Mitigation

3.4.6.1 Input data preparation and processing

1. **Watershed Vectors** - This is the polygon shapefile representing the watersheds.
2. **Land cover maps** -- see section 3.4.1.3
3. **Depth of rainfall in mm** – for this analysis, we used 97.6 mm as reference. This was the maximum value recorded on July 2022, when heavy rainfalls caused severe flooding in the state of Alagoas (Floodlist, 2022).
4. **Soils Hydrological Group Raster** - raster of categorical hydrological groups. Pixel values must be limited to 1, 2, 3, or 4, which correspond to soil hydrologic group A, B, C, or D, respectively (used to derive the CN number). The dataset can be requested by Dr. Gijs Simons MSc - futurewater.eu/about-us/our-team/gijs-simons/
5. **Biophysical Table** – a table containing model information corresponding to each of the land use classes in the Land Cover Map (Table 24). All LULC classes in the Land Cover raster MUST have corresponding values in this table. These values have been derived from sample data provided by InVEST. Each row is a land use/land cover class and columns must be named and defined as follows:
 - **lucode:** and use/land cover class code. LULC codes must match the 'value' column in the Land Cover Map raster and must be integer or floating-point values, in consecutive order, and unique.
 - **Curve number (CN) values** for each LULC type and each hydrologic soil group. Column names should be: CN_A, CN_B,

CN_C, CN_D, which the letter suffix corresponding to the hydrologic soil group.

lucode	CN_A	CN_B	CN_C	CN_D
3	35	60	65	80
4	50	70	80	80
5	60	75	80	90
9	35	60	70	80
11	60	75	80	90
12	50	65	75	80
15	50	70	80	80
19	60	75	80	90
21	60	75	80	90
23	90	90	90	95
24	90	90	90	95
25	90	90	90	95
29	90	90	90	95
30	90	90	90	95
33	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
36	60	75	80	90

Table 24: Biophysical table

3.4.6.2 Results

Figure 42 and Figure 43 show the runoff retention volume (m³) in Cerrado in 2022, and with a 17.1% expansion of agriculture into grassland and forestland, respectively. Natural infrastructure operates mainly by reducing runoff production, slowing surface flows, and creating space for water.

Figure 44 and Figure 45 shows the runoff retention volume (m³) in Cerrado under the 4.2% expansion of agriculture into grassland and forestland scenarios, respectively.

Figure 41: Runoff retention volume (2022)

Figure 42: Runoff retention volume – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Grassland loss

Figure 43: Runoff retention volume – 17.1% expansion of agriculture - Forest Loss

Figure 44: Runoff retention volume – 4.2% expansion of agriculture - Grassland Loss

Figure 45: Runoff retention volume – 4.2% expansion of agriculture - Forest Loss

Scenario	Runoff retention (m3)	Change from 2022
2022	111,081,562,351	
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	110,628,468,323	-0.41%
17.1% Agric. expansion replacing forest	109,916,342,091	-1.05%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing grassland	110,969,594,520	-0.10%
4.2% Agric. expansion replacing forest	110,796,298,827	-0.26%

Table 25: Urban Flood Risk Mitigation statistics

As Table 25 shows, the runoff retention capacity is expected to decrease by less than 0.5% when agriculture expands by 17.1% replacing grassland and by more than 1% when it replaces forest. These changes are more contained under the scenarios where agriculture expands by 4.2%.

3.4.7 Annex II

Threat	Max_Distance	Max_Distance Adopted sources	Weighted value	Weight value Adopted sources	Decay function	Decay func. Adopted sources
Forest Plantation	6 km	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.7	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	Linear	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
Croplands and Pastureland	4 km	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.7	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	Linear	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
Mosaic of uses	0.5 km	(Ciobotaru, et al., 2019)	0.3	(Ciobotaru, et al., 2019)	Linear	(Ciobotaru, et al., 2019)
Urban area	7.1 km	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.7	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	Linear	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
Mining	5.6 km	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	Linear	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)

Table 26: Habitat Quality model – references "threat table

Value	Habitat	Habitat Adopted sources	Sensitivity to Agricultural source	Sensitivity to Agri source Adopted Sources	Sensitivity to Urban Areas Sources	Sensitivity to Urban Area Adopted sources	Sensitivity to Mining Sources	Sensitivity to Mining Sources
3	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
4	0.5	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
5	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
9	0.5	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
11	0.5	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
12	0.5	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
15	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
19	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
21	0.3	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.03	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	0.69	(Terrado, et al., 2016)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
23	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
24	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
25	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
29	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
30	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
33	0.5	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)	0.7	(Sulistiyawan, et al., 2017)	0.8	(Sulistiyawan, et al., 2017)	1	(Bhagabati, et al., 2012)
36	0.7	(Sulistiyawan, et al., 2017)	0.8	(Sulistiyawan, et al., 2017)	0.7	(Sulistiyawan, et al., 2017)	0.8	(Sulistiyawan, et al., 2017)

Table 27: Habitat Quality model – references "threat sensitivity table"

4 CGE modeling

The present work is part of the Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable (MATS) Project, the objective of which is to investigate the advantageous changes needed in agricultural trade and related policies to achieve sustainable outcomes. In this report, a synthesis of the results of a simulation exercise based on scenarios developed under an *ad hoc* dynamic CGE model named GDynEP is reported with the scope of comparing alternative carbon and trade policy solutions. Particular attention is paid to the carbon-related effects and the potential competitiveness gains for African countries as a case study for the implementation of EU trade policies designed to enhance domestic mitigation in developing countries. The main steps carried out for this analysis are:

(1) The description of the model, its data inputs and calibration:

- model databases used for this GDynEP version;
- common assumptions for model design;
- description of the methodology to embed non-CO₂ emissions;
- regional and sectoral aggregations and temporal profile.

(2) The description of scenarios:

- assumptions related to the reference cases;
- description of policy scenarios for unilateral and multilateral mitigation actions.

(3) The description of results:

- comparison across scenarios for an assessment of economic impacts of alternative policy solutions;
- specific quantification of the carbon leakage effects associated to the alternative solutions;
- trade effects associated with a carbon and trade policy agreement with African countries, as a case study on the potential effects of a climate club approach;
- further socio-economic effects related to the implementation of sustainable production solutions in the African agricultural sectors.

In the context of the steps described above, a detailed description of model assumptions and original databases used for the development of the model version used for this simulation exercise is provided in order to ensure full replication and transparency of models (Section 2 and Annex A). The specific trajectories related to the evolution of exogenous macro trends as GHG emissions, GDP, population and labour force in the reference scenario together with the policy scenarios associated to mitigation targets and alternative or complementary policy instruments are described in Section 3. Results of each scenario, and comparison to the reference case, without or with non-CO₂ emissions associated to the agricultural and livestock sector, are described with the help of graphical tools and commented in Section 4.

4.1 GDynEP model settings

4.1.1 General description of GDynEP as a dynamic CGE

Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models provide an analytical representation of the economic relationships (e.g., production, demand, trade) between economic agents (e.g., firms, household, governments) in a multi-region, multi-sector (and, in case of dynamic models, inter-temporal) perspective. CGE models are based on observed data and usually includes a detailed database (Hertel, 1997), in the form of Input–Output (IO) matrices or Social Account Matrices (SAMs), and a set of equations linking variables through behavioural parameters often referred as elasticities (Armington, 1969).

In what follows we describe the assumptions and the data used for building the GDYnEP model version as a GTAP-based dynamic CGE model. The GTAP resources include information on: base data for running the model; standard behavioural parameters (e.g., elasticities); parameters regulating the dynamic features of the model; the mapping (e.g., region, sector commodity) required to run the model according to the equations in the command file. The GDynEP model here developed is based on Fortran compiler associated to the GEMPACK solution for coding the equations that are collected in the command file here named Tablo file.

The GDynEP version here developed results from combining (and upgrading) different GTAP model versions:

- GTAP, providing a consistent representation of the world economy is an Input Output (IO) approach representing all bilateral relationships at the country level and intermediate sector transactions for the production process;
- GTAP-E static energy model (Burniaux and Truong, 2002; McDougall and Golub, 2009);
- GDyn recursive-dynamic extension of the standard GTAP (Ianchovichina and Walmsley, 2012);
- GDynEP dynamic recursive model version including the energy sector and emissions (Antimiani et al., 2023).

The final version used for the simulation exercise starts from the latest GDynEP model developed by Antimiani et al. (2023) for the representation of the economic impacts of the EU climate policy mix with two novelties originally introduced for this analysis:

- (1) The specification of the electricity sector with three production sources, distinguishing between electricity produced by fossil fuels (coal, natural gas, oil, oil products) named ely_f , by renewable sources (hydropower, solar PV, wind, and others) named ely_{rw} , and by nuclear power named ely_n (Figure 46).
- (2) The introduction of a CBAM among the policy instruments forming the carbon strategy for the EU, complementing the domestic carbon pricing.

Figure 46 – Structure of the production function including the electricity nest

The CBAM policy instrument is modelled in the Tablo as an *ad valorem* equivalent applied to the internal market price of EU imports, whose impact is correlated to two key variables: i) the carbon price level of the EU endogenously computed for respecting the mitigation target; ii) the carbon content of the imported good

computed on the basis of a best technology approach (BAT), assuming that the EU carbon content of each good is the lowest at the world level.

In so doing, the CBAM policy here simulated is perfectly compliant with WTO rules since the carbon content is that of the EU applied to the amount of goods imported from abroad, as a weight for the internal carbon price level applied to the value of imported goods. More precisely, the market price equation including CBAM as an *ad valorem* import taxation is expressed in lines 4029-4033 of the Tab1o file as follows:

```

4029 Equation MKTPRICES
4030 # eq'n links domestic and world prices (HT 24) #
4031 (all,i,TRAD_COMM)(all,r,REG)(all,s,REG)
4032 pms(i,r,s) = tm(i,s)+tms(i,r,s)+pcif(i,r,s)
4033 +[CBAT(i,r,s)+CBAC(i,r,s)]*[100*CO2CBAM(i,s)*NCTAXB(REGTOBLOC(s))];

```

where the expression $[CBAT(i,r,s)+CBAC(i,r,s)]$ is associated to a shock on the exogenous variable $(cba(i,r,s))$ defined at line 3885 that assumes value=1 when the EU decides to complement internal carbon pricing ($NCTAXB(REGTOBLOC(s))$) with a CBAM, according to a carbon content ($CO2CBAM(i,s)$) which is computed on the basis of the EU technology. The CBAM can be applied by the EU region (s) to all regions defined by (r) according to the instructions provided in the START.CMF command file. The alternative composition of regions subject to the application of the *ad valorem* import tariff resulting from the CBAM is exogenously given by the definition of a group of countries/regions that are not applying domestic carbon pricing mechanisms and are consequently forced to pay the carbon price at the customs when exporting toward the EU market. This general model structure allows applying this GDynEP version to other simulation exercises with alternative clubs of countries bargaining common carbon pricing mechanisms.

4.1.2 Model database

The original databases used for building a GDyn version that includes combustion-based CO₂ emissions, non-CO₂ emissions and sources for the production of electricity are:

- GTAP10 for all base information of IO elements of a GTAP-based model in FlexAgg model;
- GDyn database for all inputs required to transform the model from a static to a dynamic version;

- GTAP-E for all information on the linkages between the energy sector and the related combustion-based CO₂ emissions associated to the use of fossil fuels for energy purposes;
- GTAP-Power for information about detailed energy sources in electricity production;
- GTAP-NCO₂ for GHG emissions different from CO₂ associated to the use of energy commodities and additional emissions associated to the production process including agriculture and livestock activities.

4.1.2.1 GTAP10

The GTAP Data Base is a consistent representation of the world economy for a pre-determined reference year. Underlying the data base there are several data sources, including among others: national IO tables, trade, macroeconomic, energy and protection data. The underlying IO tables are heterogeneous in sources, methodology, base years, and sectoral detail, thus for achieving consistency, substantial efforts are made to make the disparate sources comparable. For these reasons, the objective of the GTAP Data Base is not to provide IO tables, but to facilitate the operation of economic simulation models ensuring users a consistent set of economic facts. The data in the GTAP Data Base accurately depicts the magnitudes of economic variables, but they are presented in terms of the aggregates that serve the CGE modelling. The total number of countries and regions is 141 and the number of sectors is 65, with a substantial increase in the disaggregation of the service sector. For a complete description of all features in GTAP10 refer to Aguiar et al. (2019).

4.1.2.2 GDyn

The GDyn Model builds on the GTAP Data Base augmented with foreign income data and allows dynamic analysis to be undertaken without imposing severe limitations on the model size. The data aggregated by this program is based on the GTAP10 supplemented with additional data on income payments and convergence parameters. The total number of countries and regions is 141 and the number of sectors is 65, with a substantial increase in the disaggregation of the service sector. For a complete description of all features in GDyn database refer to Ianchovichina and Walmsley (2012). The version on which the table is built is GDyn v3.6 that includes corrections to avoid zero divide issues.

4.1.2.3 GTAP-E

The GTAP-E Data Base provides carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions data distinguished by fuel and by user for each of the 141 countries/regions and the 65 sectors in the GTAP10 Data Base. GTAP-E data is based on: GTAP10 and extended energy balances compiled by the International Energy Agency (IEA). A FlexAgg

distribution and GTAPAgg2 packages for each of the reference years are available. For a complete description of all features in GTAP-E database refer to McDougall and Golub (2009).

The version on which the Tab1o file is built is GDyn v3.6 that includes corrections to avoid zero divide issues plus the energy version corrected with climate damage (Costantini et al., 2018) and technical change in clean energy technologies (Corradini et al., 2018).

4.1.2.4 GTAP-Power

Electricity-detailed extension of the GTAP-E with the e1y sector in GTAP disaggregated into: transmission and distribution, seven base load technologies (nuclear, coal, gas, hydroelectric, oil, wind and other power technologies), and four peak load technologies (gas, oil, hydroelectric, and solar) for 2014 in GTAP-Power database. This is an electricity-detailed extension of the GTAP Data Base and the new sectors are combined with the original GTAP sectors resulting in a data base with 76 sectors and 141 regions. The original description of GTAP-Power is provided in Peters (2016).

More recently, Chepeliev (2020) provided an updated version of the methodology. Changes introduced to the GTAP-Power database construction process consist in a different way with which output of the electricity and heat generation sector has been split using electricity generation data together with heat generation volumes to provide a more representative sectoral split and better concordance with GTAP sectoral definitions. Second, data on country and year-specific shares of transformation and distribution costs in electricity tariff for 80 countries are introduced.

4.1.2.5 GTAP-NCO2

The GTAP-NCO2_V10a database compatible with the GTAP10 database version is based on the methodology developed by Irfanoglu and van der Mensbrugge (2016). The database provides emissions for 24 non-CO2 emissions categories with 119 unique emissions subcategories for 244 countries. Emissions by region and economic sector, as well as emissions drivers are provided for three major non-CO2 gases (or groups of gases), CH₄, N₂O, and the group of fluorinated gases (F-gases), including CF₄, HFCs, and SF₆. Emissions come from three different economic activities:

- consumption (by households and firms) of the goods (both for final consumption or as an intermediate input of the production process);
- use of the endowments (land and capital) in the production process mainly associated to the use of soil in agriculture and cattle in the livestock sector;

- final use of the output that is responsible for emissions independently from the consumption or production process (e.g., CH₄ emissions related to the extraction process of natural gas).

4.1.3 Methodology to embed GHG emissions in GDynEP

With respect to the emissions associated to consumption by firms and households the original har file has been transformed in order to be compatible with the structure of CO₂ emissions used in GTAP-Power with 76 sectors. With the excel file "GHG_transf.xlsx" we have first computed the share of emissions associated to imported and domestic inputs according to the shares obtained by imported and domestic CO₂ emissions for coal, oil, gas, p_c and gdt sectors. For the chm sector, we have computed the share of VIFM and VDFM on total intermediate use of chm input and the associated the share to the value of emissions. For non-CO₂ emissions associated to the e1y sector in the original database, we have associated the related non-CO₂ emissions based on the share of emissions for the e1y sector in Power for combustion-based CO₂ emissions.

The new "gsdemiss2.har" file contains the sum of combustion-based CO₂ emissions and non-CO₂ emissions associated to the use of energy inputs plus the chemical sector. Thanks to the changes in FlexAgg command for GTAP-Power, by computing emissions on the basis of trad_comm instead of ctax_comm it is possible to add the emissions associated to the chm sector without changing the definition of ctax_comm and at the same time obtaining emissions in har file compatible with the GDynE version. When making the model version with aggregation, it is necessary to substitute in the FlexAgg folder the "gsdemiss.har" file with the new "gsdemiss2.har" file by changing its name into "gsdemiss.har".

In addition, in order to include all other GHG emissions related to output in the production process and the emissions related to the endowments used in the production function, a set of conversion matrices has been added into GHG_transf.xlsx to add all GHG emissions in a matrix form which is compatible with the implementation of a carbon pricing system as modelled in GDynEP. The IO tables related to the share in inputs use in all production processes have been used to assign the GHG emissions related to the use of each endowment to the sector directly using that endowment. In so doing the model can be used with different set of GHG emissions. In order to distinguish them, we have two base data files in the model. The first one is gddat_cbam.har and includes CO₂ emissions plus non-CO₂ emissions expressed in CO₂-equivalent computed on the basis of the intermediate inputs used in the production process. The second one is gddat_cbam_ghg.har and it also includes non-CO₂ emissions expressed in CO₂-equivalent computed on the basis of the output and endowment related emissions

transferred to sectors and households on the basis of the IO table, obtaining data in 2014 as the starting year fully compatible with the carbon pricing mechanism.

4.1.4 Regions and sectors aggregation

The aggregation into regions and sectors has been agreed at the MATS Consortium level in order to express as much as detailed the regional areas and the most representative sectors in both climate and trade policy. The aggregation is also available in a compact excel format in the file `agg_GDynEP.xlsx` and in txt format for three different versions of FlexAgg database: `agg_GDynEP_dyn14.txt` is valid for GTAP10 and the dynamic version; `agg_GDynEP_ene.txt` is valid for GTAP-E, `agg_GDynEP_power.txt` is valid for GTAP-Power. The requirement for three different command files is justified by the use of three different GTAP original databases that have not the same number of sectors detailed. The regional aggregation is described in Table 28, while the specific countries and regions belonging to each GTAP region in the model are provided in Table 42 in the Appendix.

Table 28 - Regions aggregates in GDynEP

No	Model code	Description
1	AFEnex	Africa North energy exporters
2	AFNorth	Africa North rest
3	AFWest	Africa West
4	AFCentr	Africa Central
5	AFHorn	Africa Horn
6	SouthAfrica	South Africa
7	ASEnex	Middle East and Asia energy exporters
8	ASCentr	Asia Central
9	ASSouth	Asia South
10	China	China
11	India	India
12	Indonesia	Indonesia
13	Japan	Japan
14	Malaysia	Malaysia
15	Philippines	Philippines
16	SKorea	South Korea
17	Australia	Australia
18	NewZealand	New Zealand
19	EFTA	EFTA countries
20	EU27	European Union members
21	UK	UK
22	EurRest	Rest of Europe
23	Russia	Russian Federation
24	Turkey	Turkey
25	Canada	Canada
26	USA	USA
27	Mexico	Mexico
28	Brazil	Brazil
29	Andean	Andean countries
30	LAEnex	Latin America energy exporters
31	LARest	Latin America rest

32	Mercosur	Rest of Mercosur
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The aggregation of single GTAP sectors into macro-sectors that remain representative of the main drivers in energy consumption and related GHG emissions is represented in Table 29, with the detailed GTAP coded sectors available in the Appendix in Table 43.

The aggregation of single GTAP endowments into main inputs of the production process is represented in Table 30, with the detailed GTAP coded endowments available in the Appendix in Table 44.

Table 29 - Sectors aggregates in GDynEP

No	Model code	Description
1	rice	Rice
2	cer	Cereal grains
3	o_prim	Other primary
4	veg	Vegetable and fruit
5	cat	Cattle
6	liv	Other livestock
7	r_meat	Rumin meat
8	o_meat	Other meat
9	fish	Fishery
10	dai	Dairy
11	bev_t	Beverages and tobacco
12	food	Processed food
13	sug	Sugar
14	tex	Textile
15	pap	Paper and publishing
16	wood	Wood
17	chem	Chemical
18	plas	Plastics and rubber
19	phar	Pharmaceutics
20	min	Mineral
21	mot	Motor veichles
22	tr_eq	Transport equipment
23	ect_eq	Electronics and electronic equipment
24	elect	Electrical equipment
25	metal	Metal product
26	mach	Machinery
27	fer	Ferrous metal
28	o_man	Other manufacturing
29	coal	Coal
30	oil	Oil crude
31	gas	Natural gas and LNG
32	ely_f	Electricity from fossil fuels
33	ely_n	Electricity from nuclear
34	ely_rw	Electricity from renewables
35	oil_p	Oil products
36	r_transp	Road and railway transport
37	a_transp	Air transport
38	w_transp	Water transport
39	serv1	Service private

40	serv2	Service public
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Table 30 - Endowments aggregates in GDynEP

No	Model code	Description
1	Land	Land
2	SkLab	Skilled labour force
3	UnSkLab	Unskilled labour force
4	Capital	Capital
5	NatRes	Natural resources

4.2 Reference and policy scenarios

4.2.1 The policy-driven debate under scenario building

The scenarios developed for the dynamic comparative assessment of alternative policy solutions to mitigate GHG emissions follow the international debate on the relative benefits and risks associated with unilateral vs. multilateral emissions abatement policies (Aldy and Stavins, 2012; Best et al. 2020; Baranzini et al., 2017), and consequences emerging from the creation of potential climate clubs of virtuous countries in addressing climate change (Espa and Holzer, 2023; Szulecki et al., 2022).

Indeed, unilateral climate policies aiming to cut emissions present some risk of generating distortive effects in global prices, international competitiveness and geographical allocation of carbon intensive production (Helm et al., 2012; Eicke et al., 2021). To prevent these effects, with particular reference to carbon leakage, the EU is in 2023 implementing the CBAM as a complementary measure to the already active EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), by phasing-out of the allocation of free allowances under the EU ETS.⁵ The CBAM aims to adjust the price of imported goods to reflect the embedded carbon emissions generated in the production processes of those goods imported into the EU, based on the carbon price that these goods would have been paid under the EU-ETS (Carlson et al., 2023). Theory suggests these are the second-best instruments to improve the economic efficiency of unilateral policies if universally applied emissions pricing is not available (Hoel, 1996; Markusen, 1975). However, the efficacy of this solution has been studied by literature with mixed results (Branger and Quirion, 2014): while some studies find this mechanism to be effective (Fischer, 2015; Mörsdorf, 2022), others argued against it (Antimiani et al., 2013; Winchester et al., 2011). Whilst keeping in mind the limited applicability of CBAM to specific agricultural commodities or sectors thus far (Carlson et al., 2023), a recent review on the topic by Böhringer et al. (2022) highlights that Border Carbon Adjustments (BCAs) should be evaluated against four policy-relevant criteria: (a) the effectiveness in leakage reduction (Antimiani et al., 2016); (b) the competitiveness' reinstatement capacity of Energy-Intensive Trade-Exposed (EITE) industries (Fouré et al., 2016); (c) its potential to improve the global cost-effectiveness of unilateral emissions pricing via trade flows (Böhringer et al., 2012; Winchester, 2012); and (d) its

⁵ "The CBAM regulation officially entered into force the day following its publication in the Official Journal of the EU on 16 May 2023. The CBAM itself will enter into application in its transitional phase on 1 October 2023, with the first reporting period for importers ending 31 January 2024." https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism_en.

equity implication in shifting international climate policy burden sharing (Böhringer et al., 2018; Cosbey et al., 2019; Eicke et al., 2021).

Another solution to overcome the potential free-riding of certain actors and create a global framework for climate governance can be found in the literature studying climate clubs (Nordhaus, 2015; Hovi et al., 2016; Leal-Arcas, 2020; Paroussos et al., 2019; Sabel and Victor, 2017; Szulecki et al., 2022). The concept of climate club was proposed by Nordhaus (2015) as a formal or informal agreement by participating countries to undertake harmonized emissions reductions focusing on a commonly agreed target based on carbon price or abatement effort. To support this club, penalties should be introduced in the form of ad valorem tariffs on the imports of non-participants into the club. These tariffs should provide an incentive for non-compliant countries to join the club by sharing a common target (Carlson, 2016; Devarajan et al., 2022).

The international literature then expanded this definition to every cooperation on one or more climate change-related activities (Hovi et al., 2016). Even if the idea of climate clubs found many critics who saw it as unrealistic, non-effective or incompatible with WTO rules (Chen and Zeckhauser, 2018; Hagen and Schneider, 2021; Zeerman, 2018), recent literature builds on this concept, studying its governance issues (Szulecki et al., 2022) and comparing it directly to the different forms of BCA debated, especially in those countries or regions particularly interested in implementing ambitious abatement targets, as the EU (Overland and Huda, 2022; Overland and Sabyrbekov, 2022).

Building on this debate, the policy scenarios considered in this study are designed to address multiple dimensions related to the implementation of unilateral vs. cooperative solutions (Zefferman, 2018), including club agreements and penalties in the form of external tariffs. The main variables on which results are focused are the emissions patterns, the potential carbon leakage rate, carbon prices, the evolution in energy intensity and in the use of renewable sources, as well as macroeconomic impacts in terms of GDP and changes in bilateral trade relationships resulting from comparative advantages.

Furthermore, the same impacts are analysed in the presence of commitments by African countries to align their emissions standards to the ones required by the EU, consequently creating a special "climate club" deriving from the border adjustment policy, since African countries are the most likely to be at risk after the implementation of CBAM (Eicke et al., 2021), and consequently the most interested in entering into a climate club with the EU.

Along with recent contributions highlighting potential risks related to negative distributive effects, especially for poorer households, a further investigation is carried to detect if -and to what extent- the implementation of a carbon pricing

system (Fremstad and Paul, 2019; Oueslati et al., 2017) or more generally a stringency in environmental regulation (Säll, 2018; Wang et al., 2019) is associated to a general increase in consumption prices, and a consequent damage in income distribution.

Given that the heterogeneous characteristics of the African regions and sectors here disentangled in the GDynEP model might be a source of differentiated impacts on specific regions and sectors related to a common policy implementation (Kjær, 2015), a final element of assessment is given by the effects on external competitiveness and welfare distributive outcomes when socio-technical and environmental standards are specifically applied to **agricultural sectors** in order to improve the sustainability of production processes. The operationalisation of efficiency gains obtained from improved productivity standards is modelled via a standard procedure of transforming qualitative elements into different potential input-augmenting technical change effects in the sectors under evaluation in a sensitivity nuanced manner (Antimiani et al., 2023; Corradini et al., 2018).

4.2.2 Data sources for scenarios

All inputs (commands and files) for the construction of a scenario (i.e. including pre-determined shocks) are included in a common folder where there is a command do file for STATA MP16 version that is applied to the scenarios available for the main variables to be shocked for the 141 GTAP countries and regions in the file GTAP_GECO_EUREF_MATS.x1sx.

The final database is an excel file including the following variables: GDP at constant 2015US\$, total population starting from GTAP10 2014 data, skilled and unskilled labour force (aggregated according to Table 44 - Endowments in the Appendix), combustion-based CO₂ emissions starting from GTAP-E 2014 data, non-CO₂ emissions divided into total non-CO₂ GHG emissions derived from GTAP-NCO2V10a data for 2014 in Mton CO₂-eq, energy input related non-CO₂ emissions that are based on the sum of headers NCQF and NCQP in GTAP database associated to intermediate use and households consumption.

The source on which scenarios are based are divided between the current period 2014-2020 and projections for the time span 2021-2030.

For the reference period data on population for 2014 is taken by GTAP10 while for updates 2014-2020, data comes from Eurostat and World Development Indicators (WDI) from the World Bank. For the reference period data on combustion-based CO₂ emissions for 2014 is taken by GTAP-E while for updates 2014-2020, data comes from Eurostat, IEA CO₂ emissions highlights and WDI. Data for GDP in 2014-2020 are based on WDI. Data for non-CO₂ emissions in 2014 are based on

GTAP-NC02V10a database updated with change in 2014-2020 based on Eurostat and IEA energy balances. Data for skilled and unskilled labour force in 2014 are calculated as share of total labour force from CEPII (Centre d'études prospectives et d'informations internationales) information applied to GTAP population data and the period 2014-2020 is calibrated with International Labour Organisation (ILO) information on labour force and CEPII statistics based on the methodology developed by Fouré et al. (2013). Data for electricity produced with renewable sources (e1y_rw), with fossil fuels (e1y_f), and nuclear power (e1y_n) are taken from GTAP Power 2014 and projected according to growth rate of electricity production by source in GECO reference + EUREF (European Commission reference case) for EU countries (Capros et al., 2016; Keramidas et al., 2022) based on historical energy balances.

For the projections in the time span 2021-2030 there is a reference case computed on the basis of the combination of data on GDP, population, labour force, energy mix, electricity mix and CO₂-eq emissions taken from: i) the GECO reference case; ii) the EUREF for single EU members, iii) the World Energy Outlook (WEO) STEPS (Stated Policies) 2022 (IEA, 2022) scenario; iv) the Shared Socio-Economic Pathways "Middle of the road" referred as SSP2 and used in the Sixth Assessment Report by the IPCC as the average reference case; iv) the CEPII projections for labour forces. Emissions both in the reference case are aggregated into two databases: i) in gddat_cbam.har CO₂ emissions from combustion of fossil fuels and Non-CO₂ emissions in equivalent term from energy usage are aggregated; ii) in gddat_cbam_ghg.har also non-CO₂ emissions related to output and endowment in GTAP-NC02V10a database are aggregated, resulting into a database that excludes only emissions from land use change and forestry.

Together with the reference case, a decarbonisation pattern is designed with respect to the evolution of energy consumption, energy sources mix and the CO₂-eq emissions trend, according to the 1.5C scenario available from GECO and calibrated also with WEO-NZE (Net Zero Emissions) scenario, coherent with the 1.5C° temperature increase of the Paris Agreement and with the SSP1 used in the Sixth Assessment Report by the IPCC as the "Sustainability - Taking the Green Road" case.

The alternative policy scenarios are then designed to compare the main economic impacts associated with different mixes of policy instruments implemented unilaterally by the EU, or multilaterally by selected regions belonging to a club or by all regions at the world level to respect and match the abatement targets coherent with the decarbonisation pattern in terms of CO₂-eq emissions reduction.

4.2.3 Calibration procedure for the reference case

The baseline is calibrated with shocks associated to GDP, population, skilled and unskilled labour force and CO₂-eq emissions that are considered as exogenous and are calibrated with the increase in production and consumption efficiency. This is a requirement for the GTAP modelling exercise because otherwise CO₂-eq emissions have no cap and they proportionally follow the GDP and population trends without any assumptions on technological improvements that will reduce carbon intensity of economic dynamics.

Regarding the calibration of the production of electricity produced by the three sources into the electricity sub-domain we have projected the change in the three sectors `ely_f`, `ely_n`, `ely_rw` in the production nest according to GECO reference case projections, and calibrated the shocks in order to obtain by 2030 a share of `ely_rw` on total electricity for all regions compatible with GECO-EUREF baseline case. The shocks in baseline are based on the evolution over time in the reference case of the production of electricity by the two sources expressed in GWH, where the starting point in 2014 is the value of electricity production provided in the GTAP-Power database in GWH. Accordingly, the evolution over time is not fully aligned with the GECO-EUREF value in absolute terms, since the alignment has been made on the basis of growth rates (starting from different base-year values in GTAP-Power w.r.t. to GECO-EUREF). The calibration has been also carried by comparing the composition of the energy mix on the consumption side (the `CVOL` header in baseline results) with respect to GECO-EUREF information on total primary consumption volumes expressed in Mtoe.

4.2.4 Policy scenarios

According to the emissions typologies included in the model, there are two reference cases that constitute the Business As Usual (BAU) scenarios, the first one related to the CO₂-eq emissions associated with energy inputs (BAU) and the second one that includes all GHG emissions expressed in CO₂-eq including emissions related both to energy inputs and to outputs and endowments (BAU_GH). The BAU cases are built on exogenous shocks applied to main socio-economic variables as GDP, population, skilled and unskilled labour force according to the projections available from GECO-EUREF and CEPII, and calibrated with the SSP2 trends for comparison. The shock applied to the evolution of CO₂-eq emissions is compatible with the common approach of a reference case based on the future implementation of current policies, resulting into an emission pattern compatible with change rates obtained in GECO-EUREF, SSP2 and in the WEO-STEPS. Given the GDynEP structure, the standard modelling approach is to set an exogenous carbon taxation expressed as US\$ per ton of CO₂ emitted, and to endogenously compute the emissions trend. In order to calibrate the model to a

reference case that is coherent with GECO-EUREF, WEO-STEPS and SSP2 scenarios, the emissions are switched to be exogenous. In the BAU case, the endogenous corresponding variable is an input-augmenting technical change in production processes for energy inputs and an output-augmenting technical change for energy consumption at the household level.

Starting from the two baselines, the *first policy scenario* is designed to represent the implementation of a unilateral climate policy by the EU in the form of a carbon taxation applied to all CO₂-eq emissions related to economic activities by firms and households in the period 2023-2030. The mitigation target is applied as a shock computed on the evolution of emissions according to the GECO-15C scenario and the WEO-NZE and coherent with the 2030 target designed into the Fit-for-55 package of the EU (with a -55% of emissions w.r.t. 1990 levels). The exogenous emissions trend is obtained by endogenously computing the carbon tax (which is equivalent to an equilibrium carbon price of a permits market where all agents are involved) required to be compliant with the abatement target.

This is a standard procedure to have a benchmark cost for a domestic decarbonisation strategy, that is complemented by two additional shocks. The first allows representing the increase in electricity produced by renewables compatible with the projections in GECO-15C and WEO-NZE in the form of investments to output-augmenting technical change. The second one is designed to obtain an energy efficiency gain on average comparable with the GECO-15C and WEO-NZE energy consumption change. According to which reference case is considered for emissions, the unilateral EU climate policy scenarios to be on track w.r.t. to the Paris Agreement target are referred as EU_PA if only energy-related CO₂-eq emissions are included, and EU_PA_GH if all GHG emissions are modelled.

The second policy scenario consists in complementing the EU carbon tax policy instrument with a CBAM applied to all sectors belonging to the primary and industrial manufacturing activities (excluding services) on the basis of a carbon content that is WTO compatible, as in the equation reported in Section 2.1 from the table. As a result, the ad valorem tariff equivalent applied to imports from all regions is endogenously computed on the basis of the carbon price level and the carbon content (based on EU standards) of each good, and results in an increase of the internal EU market price of imports as in lines 4032-4033 of the table.

The levy would mirror the EU's carbon market price to prevent carbon leakage. Indeed, when the EU's emission reduction efforts are offset by increased emissions outside the bloc through relocation of production to non-EU countries with less ambitious climate policies, or by increased imports of carbon-intensive products, the tariff system should prevent the leakage effect.

According to the emissions type, the two scenarios are referred as EU_PA_CBAM and EU_PA_GH_CBAM. *Differently from the current EU regulation, the tariff is applied to all sectors responsible for emissions (and not only the cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, and electricity sectors as foreseen in the first implementation period) in accordance with the carbon taxation scheme here simulated with all sectors included (differently from the current ETS scheme where only energy-intensive sectors are covered by the pricing mechanism).* This modelling choice allows obtaining general results in economic terms that can be interpreted under the driving multilateral mechanisms typically defined under a CGE approach. Therefore, the scenario provides benchmark results w.r.t. the BAU case going beyond the current EU regulation that would rapidly evolve by adding new sectors to the tariff scheme.

The third policy scenario simulates a climate club approach as envisaged by the CBAM EU regulation in the case the exporter can demonstrate the payment for an internal carbon price applied to the domestic production process of the exported good. Accordingly, the regions exempted from the tariff scheme adopt an abatement target that corresponds to the emissions pattern compatible with the GECO-15C and WEO-NZE scenarios, with an endogenous carbon price resulting from the mitigation constraint in line with the mechanism applied to EU in the first policy case. The regions adopting the domestic carbon price system are expected to invest in decarbonisation technologies as the EU with an increase in electricity produced by renewable sources and a reduction in energy intensity as projected in GECO-15C and WEO-NZE. The scenario is tested with a climate club formed by the EU and the regions belonging to the African continent, namely AFenex, AFNorth, AFWest, AFCentr, AFHorn, SouthAfrica as defined in Table 28. According to the to the emissions type, the two scenarios are referred as EU_PA_CBAM_SA and EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA.

The fourth policy scenario is a benchmark case where the levy imposed by the EU is removed because carbon-intensive processes around the world are all subject to carbon pricing. From a modelling perspective, this corresponds to the adoption of domestic abatement targets by all regions in line with GECO-15C and WEO-NZE emissions trajectories, and a corresponding endogenous carbon taxation applied at the region level.

A general overview of scenarios is provided in Figure 47, while in Figure 48 the aggregation of African countries into the six regions modelled in GDynEP is visualised.

In addition to the general organisation of alternative scenarios, starting from the EU_PA_GH_CBMA_SA case, where African regions enter the climate club with the EU and are exempted from the CBAM scheme due to the adoption of a domestic carbon pricing system consistent with the abatement targets required for respecting the Paris Agreement goals, the model is used for impact evaluation of complementary actions to enhance **socio-technical sustainability in the agricultural sectors**. Given that the model version cannot disentangle all sectors and countries in detail to replicate an aggregation compatible with the **case studies developed in MATS**, as a standard solution there are additional exogenous shocks that can replicate the direct and indirect mechanisms into the production function when specific regulatory or voluntary sustainability instruments are included in the policy mix design. In this case, the assumptions are: i) **investments in new technologies** aiming at enhancing the sustainability of the productive system can be assessed in the form of input-augmenting technical change of selected endowments (land and natural resources); ii) **improvements in labour standards and workers protection initiatives** (taking into account work from MATS D3.4.) are assumed to evolve into input-augmenting technical change and increase in labour productivity (with an equal percentage change both for skilled and unskilled labour force).⁶ Given that there is no *a priori* empirical evidence on the effective quantification of productivity gains related to the introduction of standards or sustainable techniques, as a standard modelling approach, different productivity increases are tested with a +1, 1.5, and 2% increase in input productivity for all sectors classified in the agricultural aggregate (namely Rice, Cereal grains, Other primary, Vegetable and fruit, Cattle, Other livestock, Rumin meat, Other meat, Dairy, Sugar, as from Table 29). Details on model settings are provided in Appendix A with instructions and commands for replication in Table 45.

⁶ We contribute here to limited empirical evidence on the positive productivity implications of higher labour standards (Deakin and Sarkar, 2008) and the related question regarding the relationship between economic upgrading and social upgrading (Rossi, 2013).

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Emissions trends and carbon leakage

The emissions patterns for the two cases, as given in Figure 49, result from the exogenous projections of GTAP data on the basis of the shocks calibrated with the emissions change derived from the combination of different scenarios as described in Section 3.4. Despite the Covid-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine crisis, at the world level emissions are expected to increase by 10% in the period 2023-2030 if the emissions included only energy-based CO₂-eq and by 12% in the same period when all GHGs from anthropic activities (excluding land use change and forestry). In order to be on track with the achievement of the ambitious mitigation pathway required by the Paris Agreement main objective, the decarbonisation process should start in 2023, gradually reducing emissions until 2030 where an average decrease rate by 29% w.r.t. the BAU cases is needed. In absolute terms, this means that energy-related CO₂-eq must be abated by 11,900 Mton in the case of BAU and GHGs in CO₂-eq terms must be reduced by 14,900 Mton in the case of BAU_GH.

Figure 49 – CO₂-eq emissions trend 2020-2030 at the world level

By looking at the same representation for the EU as a single region, in Figure 50 it is worth noting that the pattern for the BAU cases is expected to be decreasing by -4% in the period 2023-2030, mainly due to the implementation of the sustainability measures supported by the investments under the EU Recovery

Plan. In order to be on track with the Fit-for-55 mitigation pathway (-55% of emissions w.r.t. 1990 level), the EU should reduce emissions arriving at a -29% w.r.t. BAU, with an absolute abatement of 860 Mton of energy-related CO₂-eq and 970 Mton of CO₂-eq when all GHGs are included.

Figure 50 – CO₂-eq emissions trend 2020-2030 for the EU

Looking more specifically to the emissions trends of the African regions here selected for the assessment of the economic impact of sustainable production choices, in Figure 51 we represent the 2020-2030 patterns in the reference case as compared with the pathway representative to be on a sustainability road to respect the Paris Agreement. Two key elements emerge from the cross-region comparison and from the different quantification of emissions type on which the climate policy is addressed. The first issue is represented by the large heterogeneity in the emissions change rates in the reference cases, very low for those relatively advanced regions (AFEnex and SouthAfrica) and much higher for developing areas, with a peak for the region AFWest. The heterogeneity is particularly evident when all GHGs are computed in the emissions pattern, revealing **a relevant contribution given by agricultural and livestock activities to the total CO₂-eq especially in AFWest and AFHorn**. The evolution of the economic system structure and the relative share in production activities in these regions reveal a relatively higher concentration in some primary sectors as cereal, vegetable oils, **cattle and other livestock activities, dairy and meat products**, which are typically associated with high non-CO₂ emissions

depending on land use, capital endowment (in the form of livestock) and use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides.

Figure 51 – CO₂-eq emissions trend 2020-2030 for African regions

Turning to the analysis of the impacts of the EU decarbonisation policy on the emission behaviour of the rest of the world, we recall that the general purpose of the EU regulation is to ensure that the implementation of a unilateral policy is not responsible for an increase in emissions abroad (carbon leakage). According to the specific impact on the African region, from Figure 52 it seems that, independently from the emissions type included in the analysis, there is an increase in emissions produced by these regions when the EU applies a unilateral climate mitigation policy, with a relatively higher increase in emissions when energy-related CO₂-eq emissions are investigated. More importantly, even when the carbon pricing policy instrument is complemented by the full implementation of a CBAM scheme applied to all regions and to all primary and manufacturing sectors, the reduction in emissions is not complete, with selected regions such as AFEnex, AFNorth and SouthAfrica remaining almost unaffected by the CBAM.

The low effectiveness of an EU CBAM in reducing the carbon leakage rate is confirmed at the general level in Figure 53 where the evolution of the leakage rate is reported for all scenarios embedding a unilateral EU policy. The maximum level of leakage is related to the joint implementation of an internal carbon pricing and an external CBAM scheme by the EU with all GHGs included, reaching around +61% of carbon leakage by 2030.

Four factors explain the low effectiveness of CBAM alone in correcting carbon leakage and the increase in foreign emissions when the combination of carbon pricing and tariff is implemented. The general increase in emissions produced by non-compliant regions in the case of a unilateral climate policy is strictly connected to two factors (De Maria and Van der Werf, 2008), (i) the reduction in international energy prices and the consequent increase in energy demand by non-abating countries and (ii) the related increase in energy-intensive production processes as they result relatively more competitive due to the reduced factor cost of energy inputs. When carbon pricing and CBAM are implemented by the EU, (iii) all intermediate goods imported by the EU on which the tariff is working are more expensive, with additional negative effects on EU competitiveness. Looking at the web of bilateral trade linkages, (iv) the EU export flows are replaced on the international markets by non-EU (more carbon-intensive) products, in a typical trade diversion effect where the composition of export flows remains unchanged while only the final destination markets are different (Antimiani et al., 2016).

Figure 52 – Change in emissions w.r.t. BAU case for African regions (2030)

Figure 53 – Carbon leakage effect under different EU policy scenarios

On the opposite, the effectiveness of a climate club strategy, here modelled between the EU and the African regions, in reducing the leakage effect is particularly evident when decarbonisation policies toward a sustainable production in African regions are implemented in all production processes, including the agricultural and livestock activities (EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA scenario) and related GHG emissions. **By accepting African region in the climate club once they have introduced domestic carbon pricing systems, the reduction in leakage rate is significant**, moving from a 60% (EU_PA_GH_CBAM) to a 40% (EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA) by 2030. On the opposite, sustainable production processes in African regions are less relevant in reducing the leakage rate when only energy-related CO₂-eq emissions are modelled, with a negligible reduction by 2030 from 60% to 54%.

4.3.2 Cost evaluation of alternative policy instruments

Turning to a cost evaluation of the alternative policy solutions here modelled, the first result is the computation of the carbon price evolution over the time span 2023-2030. In Figure 54 the unit cost of a ton of CO₂-eq for the EU is reported for all scenarios revealing key mechanisms in the carbon price formation. A general result is given by the relative higher unit value for carbon price when all GHGs are included in the emissions computation, independently from the specific policy instrument adopted. This is an expected result driven by the relative higher amount of Mton of CO₂-eq emissions to be abated to achieve the Paris Agreement

decarbonisation pathway. Another issue is the almost complete independency of the EU carbon price from the complementary use of a CBAM scheme if all regions are involved.

Figure 54 – Carbon price trend for the EU (US\$ per ton of CO₂-eq)

On the opposite, **when the climate club is extended to African regions** (EU_PA_CBAM_SA and EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA), the internal EU cost for each unit of CO₂-eq increases by 7% in both cases. If the climate club is global, meaning that no CBAM is applied and all regions respect a domestic carbon pricing mechanism, the increase in carbon price in the EU region is maximum, with a 27% and a 30% increase for WLD_PA and WLD_GH_PA cases, respectively. The main explanation behind this empirical evidence is directly associated to the concept of carbon leakage. The higher the number of regions respecting an abatement target, the lower the possibility to relocate emissions abroad, the higher the stringency of the EU domestic policy to be respected by internal change in the production structure for efficiency gain and low-carbon transformation of production and consumption processes. The effect is maximised when all regions respect the decarbonisation policies, since the possibility to exploit relatively cheaper and more carbon-intensive processes abroad is completely removed.

In Figure 55 the carbon price for African regions is reported for the four scenarios built on the road to sustainability. As a general result, in almost all regions (except for AFNorth with energy-related CO₂-eq emissions only) the carbon price is higher in the case of a generalised commitment in abating solutions (WLD_PA and WLD_GH_PA) w.r.t. the unilateral carbon pricing applied by African regions when

entering into the climate club with the EU, following the same mechanisms behind the results for the EU.

Figure 55 – Carbon price in 2030 for African regions (US\$ per ton of CO₂-eq)

Along with the EU, regions as AFNorth and AFHorn reveal a higher divergence in carbon prices when all GHGs are embedded into emissions data. Given the nature of GDynEP as a CGE model, the bilateral relations and the internal structure on the economy are the main drivers of such heterogeneous results.

In order to represent the relative impact in terms of carbon pricing at the global level, in Figure 56 unitary prices for CO₂-eq emissions are reported for all regions in 2030 for both emission-type data. The higher unit price in the case of all GHGs case is generally confirmed with few exceptions, AFEnex, AFCentr, SouthAfrica, ASEnex, LAEnex and Mercosur.

Figure 56 – Carbon price in 2030 for all regions (US\$ per ton of CO2-eq)

A common feature in the economic structure of these regions is the relatively higher share in use of fossil fuels w.r.t. the rest of the world explained by the comparative higher endowment of exhaustible energy sources (e.g. Ponstein et al., 2019). This brings to a substantial transformation of the production structure when energy-related CO2-eq emissions are modelled. On the opposite, when including all GHGs, the relative burden on extractive industries is partly reduced due to the relatively larger efforts that should be done by those countries with higher non-CO2 emissions in other productive sectors as **agriculture and livestock activities**.

As a matter of fact, the value of carbon price is not directly correlated with the relative impact in economic terms. As shown in Figure 57, the evolution of GDP for the EU w.r.t. the reference case doesn't follow the relative ranking in carbon prices as defined in Figure 54 – Carbon price trend for the EU (US\$ per ton of

CO₂-eq). On the opposite, the highest gains in terms of GDP change are associated with the policy scenarios with the highest carbon prices (WLD-PA and WLD_GH_PA). The result is consistent with the medium-term evolution of the technological trajectory designed to achieve ambitious emissions reduction target, which is more effective in ensuring a sustainable transition if resource efficiency and clean energy technologies are diffused all around the world.

In the case of unilateral climate policy applied by the EU, it is worth mentioning that the **complementary introduction of a CBAM scheme** is not effective in changing the unitary value of the carbon price, but it is responsible for a **further reduction in GDP** w.r.t the reference case (EU_PA vs. EU_PA_CBAM). By comparing results from the carbon leakage effects (Figure 53 – Carbon leakage effect under different EU policy scenarios) and the carbon price trends (Figure 54 – Carbon price trend for the EU (US\$ per ton of CO₂-eq)), the ex-ante analysis here developed is not favourable to the implementation of a carbon-related tariff as an effective solution for correcting distortion of emissions relocated abroad, and at the same time it reveals a potential economic loss for the EU. From a policy perspective, while the CBAM scheme in the current EU regulation is justified by the main purpose of protecting the relative competitiveness of EU energy-intensive industries, in the case the scheme is diffused to all primary and manufacturing sectors responsible for GHGs emissions, the general outcome could be a reduction in GDP.

In the case of a climate club formed by the EU and the African regions, the EU would not gain any improvement in GDP w.r.t. to the application of CBAM to all regions, with a net loss w.r.t to the implementation of a simple carbon pricing mechanism. Only **when all GHGs are included** in the model, the negotiation solution with an EU-Africa climate club is partly convenient for the EU only if compared with a full CBAM approach, but far from being competitive with a pure carbon pricing mechanism.

Given the dynamic nature of GDynEP, by applying a discount rate of 3% as suggested in Sartori et al. (2014), it is possible to compute the cumulated difference in GDP w.r.t. to the relative BAU case in net absolute present value expressed in constant 2020 US\$ along the time span 2023-2030. In Figure 58 it emerges that almost all regions could gain from being compliant with an ambitious abatement target up to 2030 to be on track with the Paris Agreement goal.

Figure 57 – Change in GDP w.r.t. BAU in the EU

a) Scenarios with energy-based CO₂-eq

b) Scenarios with all GHGs

There are only a few exceptions with countries or regions presenting a negative value of cumulated GDP difference, as India and Turkey when only energy-related CO₂-eq emissions are included, and AsCentr, India, Russia and Brazil when all GHGs are modelled.

Focusing on African regions, from Figure 59 it is worth noting that the relative convenience in cumulated GDP terms across different scenarios is region specific.

Figure 58 – Change in cumulated GDP w.r.t. BAU for all regions (constant 2020 US\$)

Two regions, AFEnex and AFWest, find the highest gain from taking part to the climate club, while the full implementation at a global scale of a carbon pricing mechanism is relatively less convenient. On the opposite, for both regions the exclusion from the EU climate club in the case of domestic inaction toward decarbonisation and a sustainable production process results into a net loss in cumulated GDP terms.

In the case of AFNorth and AFHorn results are almost reversed with respect to the previous cases, with a net gain obtained from the implementation of a CBAM by the EU to all regions and a net loss in the case the two regions should be compliant with a domestic carbon pricing to be included in the EU climate club (with a slight difference in AFHorn depending on the emissions type modelled in the analysis).

The last two regions, AFCentr and SouthAfrica, present positive values whatever policy scenario is tested, and a relative preference toward an EU-Africa or global climate club depending on the specific region and the emissions type.

Despite in percentage terms it appears a net preference toward a climate club solution, from aggregated values in Table 31 results are less straightforward.

Figure 59 – Change in cumulated GDP w.r.t. BAU for African regions (constant 2020 US\$)

Table 31 – Difference in cumulated GDP w.r.t. BAU (Bln constant 2020 US\$)

Scenario	EU	Africa	EU+Africa
EU_PA	-319	-22	-341
EU_PA_CBAM	-482	-16	-498
EU_PA_CBAM_SA	-452	457	6
WLD_PA	1040	472	1511
EU_PA_GH	-280	-21	-301
EU_PA_GH_CBAM	-571	-14	-585
EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA	-513	462	-51

WLD_GH_PA	1298	264	1562
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Summing up the net present value of the difference between the GDP value in the BAU case and in the policy scenario at constant 2000 Bln US\$, **the EU-Africa climate club on aggregate appears to be economically convenient for Africa in both emissions-type scenarios**, while for the EU has a net gain only when energy-type emissions are modelled. On the contrary, when all GHGs are embedded into the emissions computation, on aggregate the net loss for the EU is higher than the net gain for Africa (although lower than the carbon price case only for the EU as in EU_PA_GH).

Under the lens of the total cumulated GDP gain, **the cooperative solution is by far the preferred solution whatever the emissions type is modelled**, as for both regions EU and Africa as an aggregate there is a net GDP increase w.r.t. the BAU cases.

4.3.3 Energy intensity and renewable sources in electricity

Together with the economic impacts related to the different scenarios, some interesting insights emerge from the **analysis of the technological trends** for the EU and the rest of regions represented in GDynEP. Recalling that the model is exogenously calibrated with an additional 1% increase in the use of each energy source homogeneously across all productive sectors and for households' consumption. Starting from the EU, in Figure 60 the additional investment in energy efficiency along the period 2023-2030 as a complementary measure to the carbon pricing mechanism, as clearly envisaged in the decarbonisation policy package of the EU, results into a reduction in energy intensity (computed as the ration between total energy consumption and GDP per year) w.r.t. the BAU case by around 18% in 2030.

This result holds in all scenarios with a unilateral EU climate policy implementation, with and without the complementing CBAM, and also in the case where the African regions are included in the climate club. The energy intensity gain is almost overlapping in the case all GHGs are included in the emissions computation, as the non-CO2 emissions related to outputs and endowments are not associated with energy consumption.

When the cooperative solution is explored, the intensity in energy consumption is significantly reduced, reaching a -25% by 2030 w.r.t. BAU. This result is explained by two complementary factors. First, the implementation of domestic carbon pricing mechanisms all over the regions forming the world in the model is associated with an increase in GDP for the EU as from Figure 57. Second, the cooperative solution is also characterised by a general improvement in energy

efficiency in all regions, bringing to a generalised reduction in energy consumption for all productive process. This improvement in energy efficiency can be quantified for the EU with a reduction in energy consumption by -35% in the scenario WLD_PA compared to the unilateral EU carbon pricing mechanism EU_PA.

Figure 60 – Change in energy intensity w.r.t. BAU in the EU

The improvement in energy efficiency, when diffused across all regions in the case of a global involvement into abatement policies, can be appreciated by single regions in Figure 61, where for several areas the reduction in energy intensity could be similar or even higher than the EU case by 2030.

Turning the focus on African regions, from Figure 62 it is worth mentioning that the **unilateral EU climate policy applied** through the design of a carbon pricing mechanism, complemented by the application of an external tariff as the CBAM, induces African regions to increase their internal energy intensity, perfectly in line with the **carbon leakage effect** represented in Figure 51. Energy-intensive production processes are exploited in African regions to substitute intermediate inputs in the EU market due to the relative comparative advantages given by not stringent African carbon policies, and they are not discouraged by the application of the carbon tariff. On the opposite, if the African regions enter the climate club by implementing domestic carbon pricing, their domestic energy consumption decreases w.r.t. to the EU_PA_CBAM scenario arriving at a -12% by 2030.

At the same time, the economic gains obtained by **closer trade relationships between African regions and the EU market** allow the African GDP value to

increase w.r.t. the generalised CBAM case, further improving the energy intensity reduction.

Together with the technological improvement in efficiency for intermediate energy inputs, according to the EU climate strategy, and in particular in line with targets designed by the Fit-for-55 package, output augmenting technical change is modelled for calibrating the policy shocks with the target related to the share of renewable sources in electricity production. In this case, the target has been modelled directly by imposing the evolution of the electricity production according to the trajectory designed by the bottom-up energy data available from the multiple data sources as described in section 3.3.

Figure 61 – Change in energy intensity w.r.t. BAU for all regions in WLD_PA scenario

The different shares of renewable electricity sources (RES) for the EU, as exogenously modelled from the methodology described, are represented in Figure 63 with a 54% of RES in electricity by 2030.

Figure 62 – Change in energy intensity w.r.t. BAU in 2030 for African regions

Figure 63 – Share of renewables (RES) in electricity consumption in the EU

The model reaction to the shock provides a slight difference w.r.t. to the expected target (54% instead of 55%) because the starting point of GTAP data is calibrated at the global level and it is not perfectly overlapping with values from historical energy balances. The 1% difference is due to the application of growth change shocks, derived from the bottom-up energy models described in section 3.2, to GTAP consumption-based calibrated data. The difference between the EU_PA and the WLD_PA scenarios for the EU is explained by a relatively higher (although negligible) increase in consumption of electricity from RES w.r.t. the increase in total electricity consumption derived from the IO-based optimised results at the global level.

The same computation is provided for all regions in Figure 64, comparing the share of RES in electricity consumption in BAU and in WLD_PA.

Figure 64 – Share of renewables (RES) in electricity consumption in 2030 for all regions

At the world level, the **implementation of a sustainable energy transition characterised by a domestic carbon pricing mechanism complemented by investments in energy efficiency and in electricity production with renewable sources** would increase the share of RES in electricity consumption by 2030 from a 33% in the BAU case to a 42% in the WLD_PA scenario. This average improvement is not homogenous through the regions forming the model. Focusing on Africa, most regions would increase their share of RES in the range from 1% to 8% with the higher peaks in AFEnex and AFNorth, followed by SouthAfrica, which are the regions with a relatively higher potential in technological capability endowment and capacity to embed technology transferred from developed countries. On the opposite, regions as AFCentr and AFHorn already have a large portion of electricity produced with hydropower but are less equipped in receiving new technologies for producing electricity with the alternative available sources, mainly wind and solar power.

4.3.4 Trade effects for African regions

The inclusion of African regions within the **climate club** with the EU presents mixed results in terms of the economic impacts faced by the different players from several perspectives. Moreover, divergent results also emerge when the sustainability of the production and consumption processes are investigated.

As already noticed, the cumulative impact on GDP for the EU points to the adoption of a unilateral carbon pricing without the complementary role of a CBAM, which is not successful in reducing carbon leakage while is responsible for an additional loss in GDP. Turning to the **African regions, results are highly heterogenous with some regions gaining from entering the club and others loosing** w.r.t. facing a carbon tariff while not taking a domestic decarbonisation pattern.

Such heterogeneity in a CGE-type model can be interpreted by looking at multilateral trade mechanisms that are the basis of the economic linkages across sectors and regions. Recalling that the CBAM scenario applied by the EU is a benchmark case, with all carbon-responsible sectors covered by the rule, in Figure 65 it is evident that a carbon tariff (reported here for the year 2030) might have significantly different impacts according to the general structure of the economic system. Primary and manufacturing sectors are taxed at the border with a relative impact which is given by the ad valorem equivalent on internal import prices in the EU market. In other words, the impact of the carbon tariff is based on three components:

- 1) the EU domestic carbon pricing level endogenously computed on the basis of the EU emissions reduction target;
- 2) the EU carbon content that corresponds to a BAT computation technique;

- 3) the endogenous price formation mechanisms based on changes in demand at the international level that contributes to shape the final price faced by EU agents when importing the different goods from the international market.

Three key elements emerge from the comparison of the *ad valorem* values expressed as percentage change of the EU domestic price of imports based on three driving factors mentioned. First the relative impact of the carbon tariff is positively correlated with the type of emissions embedded into the model. The tariffs endogenously computed from the scenario with energy-related CO₂-eq emissions (EU_PA_CBAM) are always lower than those obtained from including all GHGs (EU_PA_GH_CBAM). Second, the larger difference between the two scenarios with different computation of emissions arises in those sectors that are less energy-intensive but are responsible for output and endowment based non-CO₂ emissions, mainly the primary sector.

Figure 65 – Ad valorem equivalent from CBAM as % of market prices of EU imports (2030)

Third, sectors highly ranked in the range of percentage increase in prices (excluding chemical, mineral, and iron and steel sectors) correspond to agricultural and livestock-based sectors. This specific result might be interpreted under the lens of the development of the innovative trajectories in clean technologies occurring in the EU over the past decades. The massive efforts in energy efficiency and renewable energy sources, combined with the implementation of the EU-ETS, directed the production processes to be more efficient and less carbon-intensive. Accordingly, given the weight applied to the tariff computed on the EU carbon content, the relative impact in *ad valorem* term on import prices is reduced thanks to the efficiency gains already obtained by the EU. On the opposite, when including all GHGs into the policy impact evaluation, primary sectors are still lagging behind in the technological ladder, and consequently the carbon tariffs are relatively higher than for the manufacturing sectors.

Focusing on the potential impact of a ***climate club with African regions***, the first general result is that by exempting these regions from the tariff scheme as they demonstrate to apply an internal carbon pricing system, ***the ad valorem equivalent values for all EU import prices increase, particularly for four primary sectors, namely rice, cereals, other primary goods, vegetable oils, and sugar***, and to a less extent for two manufacturing sectors as chemicals and iron and steel.

An in-depth analysis of the specific trade impacts on African regions in the two different emissions computation cases, as in Figure 66 and Figure 67, reveals that some regions are particularly profiting from the potential increase in the EU market as a final destination for domestic production.

The ***region benefiting the most from being included in the EU climate club is AFWest*** regardless of the emissions type modelled. In almost all reported primary sectors, the region benefits from an increase in percentage points of the export share both on the EU market and on the rest of the world. This brings to positively evaluating the efforts implemented by the region to decarbonise the production processes, since the general efficiency gains overcome the cost of mitigation by letting exports from AFWest to be comparatively more competitive on the world market. Sectors as rice, cereal, raw meat, ***dairy products*** and sugar increase their export share on both the EU and other markets, benefiting from a trade creation effect that is maximised when all GHGs are accounted among emissions.

The ***adoption of sustainable practices in the agricultural and livestock sectors*** that are not only focused on reducing the energy intensity of the production process appears to be a win-win strategy for this region, with a

reduction in environmental pressure coupled with a larger capacity to be competitive on the international markets and an overall economic gain in GDP terms (see Figure 59).

The same result holds for the AFCentr region, where the introduction of production techniques that are less emission-intensive, especially in the rice and raw meat sectors, intensifies the export activities toward the EU and the rest of the world. The whole economic impact in GDP terms is even larger for this region, gaining a 3% increase in cumulated GDP in the case all GHGs are accounted into emissions reduction target (see Figure 14).

Figure 66 – Perc. points change w.r.t. CBAM case in export share (energy-related CO₂-eq) in 2030

The trade and economic impact of the AFEnex region is more mixed, with interesting hints emerging from the comparison with the relative export shares toward the EU market at the sector level (Table 5). For several sectors the export share on the EU market of products with AFEnex origin (Algeria, Egypt, Lybia) is the highest with respect to the other African regions (e.g., rice, cereals, cattle, fishery, sugar), but in selected cases the implementation of a domestic carbon pricing system to be exempted from the EU carbon tariff would reduce the export

share on the EU market. Nonetheless, trade diversion provoked by the inclusion in the climate club would not bring to negative results in general economic terms, as the exemption from the EU carbon tariff is the best solution for maximising the cumulated GDP over the period 2023-2030 w.r.t. a BAU case. This means that the efficiency gains diffused in all productive sectors and the **consequent reduction in carbon and energy intensity are key to improve economic competitiveness and development opportunities.**

Figure 22, reveals that there is a high heterogeneity across sectors and regions, also **depending on the emissions type included** in the simulation. The assessment is based on the results obtained for the year 2030, recalling that the direction of results is consistent also for the previous years, with small differences in the value of the impact but with no changes in the direction. The sectoral composition of the economic system of the different regions and the relative export linkages with the EU market are the main driving factors explaining the direction and magnitude of results.

Figure 67 – Perc. points change w.r.t. CBAM case in export share (all GHGs) in 2030

Lastly, the **AFHorn region** appears as poorly affected by the inclusion in the EU climate club, with benefits in terms of improved export capacity toward the EU market mainly in the **dairy sector and with a positive trade creation effect** directed to the rest of the world for the cattle sector only when all GHGs are included in the model. While trade effects in the primary sectors appear negligible, the efforts made for an overall reduction in carbon intensity, via a domestic carbon pricing system complemented by improvements in resource efficiency and renewable energy production, are economically convenient in a global climate club perspective, where all regions participate to the common abatement goal. On the opposite, with **a selective EU-Africa climate club**, the exemption from the EU carbon tariff is not enough to compensate the burden of a domestic climate policy, bringing to a negative impact on cumulated GDP, as in the case of the AFNorth region.

Table 32 – Export share on EU market in EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA scenario (2030)

Sector	AFEnex	AFNorth	AFWest	AFCentr	AFHorn	SouthAfrica
rice	9.5%	0.2%	9.7%	7.0%	0.5%	0.4%
cer	19.0%	9.4%	3.1%	1.8%	4.7%	2.1%
o_prim	1.5%	1.4%	0.2%	0.3%	0.4%	0.8%
veg	4.1%	0.6%	0.7%	0.3%	0.2%	0.2%
cat	22.7%	10.8%	0.5%	0.0%	0.5%	0.1%
liv	4.4%	1.8%	5.3%	1.0%	2.0%	0.1%
r_meat	0.2%	0.5%	2.2%	0.6%	0.0%	0.4%
o_meat	0.0%	0.1%	9.5%	2.4%	0.1%	1.1%
dai	5.1%	11.9%	2.2%	0.9%	0.2%	0.0%
fish	18.5%	2.0%	6.7%	0.2%	0.5%	0.1%
sug	12.6%	4.2%	11.0%	0.3%	0.6%	0.2%

4.3.5 Sustainable carbon intensity patterns in Africa

The relative contribution of sectors and regions in the African area in reducing the emissions due to the diffusion of sustainable production processes can be assessed starting from the carbon intensity in the reference case. In Figure 68 the ratio between the total CO₂-eq emissions in the two emissions accounting types and the sector value added is represented for the year 2030 in the reference case.

Agriculture and livestock activities are assessed through the lens of carbon intensity for the six African regions, showing a large heterogeneity across sectors and regions. Focusing on the energy-based CO₂-eq emissions (panel a) in Figure 68), **AFNorth, AFCentr and SouthAfrica** are the three regions where different sectors, among which cereals, other primary, vegetable oils and cattle appear as **highly intensive in carbon content**. Fishery and the sugar sectors follow, with SouthAfrica as the country with most carbon-intensive producers.

When all GHGs are embedded into the CO₂-eq computation the picture significantly changes, both across sectors and regions. Meat and dairy production turn to be characterised by the largest intensity in CO₂-eq emissions, while AFHorn appears in this case as a region with particularly emission-intensive production processes.

Starting from the reference case for both emission types (BAU and BAU_GH, respectively) in Figure 69-Figure 70-Figure 71 it is possible to assess the relative impact on carbon content of alternative policy solutions. Results for changes in carbon intensity must be interpreted under an economic point of view, remembering that they come from the simultaneous change of the carbon content value and the sector-specific value added in monetary terms.

Figure 68 – Carbon intensity in BAU (ton CO₂-eq per Mln US\$) for African regions in 2030

Figure 69 – % change in carbon intensity w.r.t. BAU for AFEnex and AFNorth (2030)

As a first result, the change in carbon intensity when a unilateral EU climate policy is complemented by a CBAM-based tariff is always positive for each African region, independently from the sector and the emission type. For two regions, AFNorth and AFWest, the percentage increase in carbon intensity assumes values larger than 5% for different sectors, revealing that the imposition of a carbon tariff would not discourage the carbon intensity of foreign production processes, but on the opposite might push emissions up by exploiting relative comparative advantages derived from weaker environmental policy stringency, in line with the mechanism known as the pollution haven effect (Levinson and Taylor, 2008; Suárez-Varela and Rodríguez-Crespo, 2022).

Figure 70 – % change in carbon intensity w.r.t. BAU for AFWest and AFCentr (2030)

The implementation of a domestic climate policy with an **internal carbon pricing mechanism followed by investments in resource efficiency and renewable energy** sources would help African regions to be on a sustainable development pathway for the **agricultural sector**. Gains measured as reduction in carbon intensity are differentiated across sectors, following the relative production specialisation in the six regions.

Regions as **AFEnex and AFNorth** (Figure 69) show **large reductions in carbon intensity mainly for livestock, raw meat and dairy products**, with a prevailing effect when energy-related CO₂ emissions are included. AFWest and AFCentr present more mixed results (Figure 70) with the other primary, fishery dairy and sugar sectors mainly involved by an improvement in production sustainability. In this specific case, together with a sector heterogeneity, there are also mixed results w.r.t. the emission type embedded into model data, with sectors as cereals, other primary, vegetable oils (and sugar only for AFWest) whose carbon intensity is significantly reduced when sustainable production practices are applied to mitigate all GHG emissions.

Figure 71 – % change in carbon intensity w.r.t. BAU for AFHorn and SouthAfrica (2030)

The AFHorn region is peculiar (Figure 71) because the reduction in carbon intensity appears to be relatively higher than the rest of Africa for many sectors, including cereals, other primary, vegetable oils, livestock, fishery, and sugar. Despite the efforts in making agricultural production more sustainable from the carbon content point of view, in sectors as cereals and sugar the negative impact of the abatement costs on international competitiveness overcomes the positive effects related to resource efficiency, bringing to a trade diversion effect since the export shares on the international markets tend to decrease (Figure 67).

4.3.6 Factor productivity effects in agriculture

Given the potential development opportunities associated to a sustainable and innovative trajectory in the agricultural sector, the final set of scenarios starts from the Africa-EU climate club case **including all GHGs** (EU_GH_PA_CBAM_SA) and tests to which extent input-augmenting productivity investments in these sectors might improve the **socio-economic sustainability of African regions**. This scenario setting is also able to provide a benchmark for the potential impact of effective actions dedicated to specific countries and sectors evaluated with single case studies.

The overall assessment of the socio-economic potential impacts of sustainable-oriented improvements in the production process should also include potential **negative impacts in distribution across consumers driven by indirect price adjustments** resulting from the pass-through mechanism of carbon taxation (Bernard and Kichian, 2021).

According to the model structure of GDynEP, it is possible to consider this mechanism by computing the difference in percentage points of changes in consumer prices for single commodities by comparing across scenarios. In this case the starting point is the **CBAM case with all GHGs included**, where the EU implements its domestic decarbonisation policy by complementing the carbon pricing system with the CBAM applied to imports from foreign countries. In Figure 72 the difference is calculated by considering with respect to the introduction in African regions of a domestic carbon pricing and the simultaneous exemption from the EU CBAM tariff scheme. Despite the positive general effects already described in export market shares and GDP, **private consumers are losing part of their welfare gain due** to the increase in market prices in all agricultural sectors.

As a general outcome, all regions and sectors are affected by an increase in consumer prices when the introduction of low-carbon objectives is achieved only by carbon pricing and technology improvements in clean energy solutions. Depending on the economic structure and the relative burden in mitigation w.r.t. the reference case, there is a **large diversity in the impact on prices for different regions and sectors**. The rice sector appears particularly influenced in AFEnex and AFCentr while for SouthAfrica the difference in prices is almost negligible. On the opposite, **consumers in SouthAfrica are particularly vulnerable for vegetables, cattle, livestock, and raw meat**, revealing that the modelling approach here proposed with all GHGs make clear that also a relatively more developed economy as SouthAfrica is at risk of inequal distribution in the climate policy impacts.

Those regions that are mostly impacted in several sectors are AFWest and AFCentr, while in AFHorn only livestock and dairy products are at risk of a high redistributive impact on final consumers.

Figure 72 – Perc. points change w.r.t. CBAM case in domestic consumer prices (2030)

Given that it is not possible to precisely transform into productivity gains the multiple actions that can be adopted for specific inputs, specific sectors and single countries, the model choice here adopted is to evaluate the relative impact of different percentage change values in input-augmenting technical change for labour force, soil and natural resources, with three values, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%, as a sort of sensitivity analysis.

The first result reported is represented by the difference in changes in consumer prices between the EU_GH_PA_CBAM_SA scenario without any productivity gain and the three percentage values, respectively. In Figure 73, the difference in prices is reported for the six African regions, for all sectors tested with the three values.

Figure 73 – Perc. points change in consumer prices with alternative productivity gain (2030)

With few exceptions (rice in AFNorth, dairy in AFEnex and AFWest) the values are always negative, revealing that an **improvement in factor productivity is negatively correlated with consumer prices**. In other words, by investing in

sustainable production techniques that are able to improve the efficiency in the production process, private consumers are generally benefiting from a **reduction in consumer prices, with sectors as cereals, other primary, and vegetables** that could gain a reduction in percentage point by more than 1.5% in almost all regions when the upper value in productivity gain by 2% is tested.

The reduction in price changes from a CGE perspective can be interpreted as an increase in final domestic demand, meaning that the availability of primary goods for internal consumers is performing better, resulting into an expected **improvement in food security**. The relative increase in internal demand might turn into changes in export composition, as revealed in Figure 74, where the effects are reported for the year 2030 with the highest productivity improvement corresponding to a homogeneous input productivity gain by 2%. The values reported are computed in the same way as in Figure 67, showing that the **introduction of additional sustainability investments in input productivity** complementing achievements in energy efficiency and renewable sources might encourage domestic consumption at the expense of export flows.

Figure 74 – Perc. points change w.r.t. CBAM_SA case in export share (2030 with 2% productivity)

Even in this case results are highly heterogeneous, with some peaks in reduction in export share in the EU market for the rice and cereal sectors, and other positive peaks in export share in the rest of the world for cattle and dairy products. In order to provide a general assessment of the socio-economic impacts associated with the full set of sustainability practices, in Figure 75 the GDP trajectories for the six Africa regions are reported in terms of difference in GDP calculated as the net present value (NPV) at 2020 w.r.t to the EU_GH_PA_CBAM_SA scenario. With the **exception of AFCentr** for the first three implementation years (2023-204-2025), **all regions are positively impacted by the introduction social and environmentally sustainable production techniques in agricultural sectors**, with AFWest and AFHorn achieving by 2030 an increase in GDP by more than 5% with respect to the scenario in which the carbon pricing system is complemented by only efficiency gain in energy consumption and in renewable energy production.

Figure 75 – GDP % change w.r.t. EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA at 2020 present value (with 2% productivity)

Potential benefits arising from the introduction of standards and norms oriented toward a more sustainable use of inputs in agricultural production can be assessed in specific terms by looking at changes in sectoral consumer prices as in Figure 73, but also as an aggregate impact on welfare composition. For this purpose, the model output here considered is the quantification of the equivalent variation (EV). In the context of CGE modelling, the EV is a measure of welfare change that considers both changes in prices and changes in income (An et al., 2023). More specifically, the EV is the amount of money that would have to be given to a household after a price or policy change to make them as well off as they were before the change. It is called the EV

because it represents the change in income that is equivalent in terms of welfare to the actual price or policy change. It is important to note that the EV is based on a number of assumptions about household behaviour and preferences and may not fully capture all of the complex interactions and feedback effects that occur in real-world economies. Nonetheless, it can represent the general direction of change in welfare by comparing different scenarios. In Figure 76 there is EV percentage change trend in 2023-2030 comparing the results from GDynEP with the assumption of a 2% increase in input productivity in the agricultural sectors with the EU_GH_PA_CBAM_SA scenario. The monetary value of EV given by GDynEP is discounted with a social discount rate by 3% and reported to 2020 level for both scenarios as a standard procedure.

Figure 76 – EV % change w.r.t. EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA at 2020 present value (with 2% productivity)

It is worth mentioning that the impact in EV terms is always positive for the six regions but with highly differentiated impacts across regions, with a top player as AFEneX and the **lowest (although positive) gains occurring in South Africa.**

4.4 Conclusions

Based on input provided from the MATS analytical framework D2.4, the debate around forthcoming governance changes (e.g. EU's CBAM; Carlson et al., 2023) and emerging output from several MATS case studies reporting on competitiveness and labour standards in African regions, this report presents results from extensive simulation exercises based on Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) modelling, providing insights into alternative scenarios up to 2030. Results from the dynamic CGE model GDynEP provide many suggestions for policy design when the EU unilateral climate policy is compared with alternative policy solutions directly involving other regions, extending from regional (Africa) up to the world level. The implementation of a domestic carbon pricing mechanism complemented by the adoption of a carbon tariff in line with the EU regulation of the CBAM is assessed, by creating a comparable scenario in which the potential socio-economic benefits arising from the creation of selected climate clubs are explored.

In this report the focus is dedicated to the possible outcomes of having different African regions (as they are also assessed at micro-level through different MATS case studies) embrace sustainable production processes, with the use of a domestic carbon pricing together with the implementation of investments for a sustainable transition, thereby allowing these regions to avoid the application of an EU-driven carbon tariff.

The main results can be summarised as follows:

- (1) The implementation of a carbon pricing mechanism in the EU (CBAM) could result into a net loss for the EU in GDP terms, if a net present value approach is adopted to the cumulative effect over the years.
- (2) The carbon leakage effect might partly offset the internal EU efforts by reducing the global abatement up to 60% by 2030.
- (3) The introduction of a tariff on imports based on a CBAM rule applied to all sectors (in contrast to the current limited sectoral applicability of CBAM) would not induce carbon leakage to be significantly reduced.
- (4) The design of climate clubs with a cooperative solution tested with African regions would help reducing the leakage effect considerably by one third; this result substantiates further the analysis of Eicke et al. (2021), which suggests that countries in Southern and Western Africa are among the most affected by the EU's CBAM. Furthermore, these potential benefits of such a cooperative solution likely go beyond economic benefits with respect to this substantive reduction in leakage, if political economy perspectives were also taken into account, since Jakob (2023) concludes that the CBAM should be

- implemented as an enabler of domestic mitigation efforts in an open climate alliance instead of an attempt to extend EU climate policy to other countries.
- (5) The cumulative effect on GDP for the EU is negative in all *unilateral* climate policy scenarios, with the worst impact found in the case of a domestic carbon price complemented by a CBAM-based tariff applied to rest of the world.
 - (6) Results provide some support against the unravelling of global value chains, since the economic gains obtained by closer trade relationships between African regions and the EU market allow the African GDP value to increase w.r.t. the generalised CBAM case investigated, further improving the energy intensity reduction desired for the sustainability transition.
 - (7) From a Pareto improvement effect, the *EU-Africa climate club* consisting in applying the CBAM to the rest of the world only is particularly favourable to help African regions to develop at a sustainable path while ensuring a larger international competitiveness potential on both the EU and the world market; this partial cooperative approach seems not only desirable from an economic perspective, yet also receives support from a political economy perspective, since the analysis by Jakob (2023) suggests that countries which would be most severely affected by the CBAM would also benefit most from a polycentric multi-level governance perspective.
 - (8) A fully cooperative approach involving all regions with domestic carbon pricing *complemented by investments in resource efficiency and renewable energy sources* could be the optimal solution from a global economic perspective, as this would be accompanied with the highest positive cumulated impact on GDP. This positive expected economic implication may also support the way for the much-needed political acceptability (Klenert et al., 2018).
 - (9) All African regions are negatively affected by an increase in consumer prices when the introduction of low-carbon objectives is achieved only by carbon pricing without additional productivity improvements. Selected African regions such as AFEnex, AFCentr and SouthAfrica strongly suffer from price increase in agricultural sectors that are key to food security with respect to rice, vegetables, and livestock activities. On the opposite, an improvement in factor productivity is negatively correlated with consumer prices. In other words, by investing in sustainable production techniques that are able to improve the efficiency in the production process, private consumers are generally benefiting from a reduction in consumer prices.
 - (10) Trade effects are heterogenous according to the specific climate policy scenario involving African regions. When entering the EU climate club, African regions generally face an increase in their export share for agricultural production both in the EU and in the global market. If additional sustainable practices are introduced in agricultural production, investments

in input productivity complementing achievements in energy efficiency and renewable sources might encourage domestic consumption at the expense of export flows. In this scenario, sectors such as cereals, other primary, and vegetables could be gaining in productivity terms by more than 1.5% in almost all regions. The generalised equivalent variation computation is homogeneously positive in the medium term for all African regions, revealing that food security improvements given by higher affordability of domestic crops (lower consumer prices) is welfare improving despite the slight decrease in export shares.

5 Policy Brief

The MATS project aims to expand and enhance the available knowledge on the relationships between agricultural markets, trade, investments, policy, environmental sustainability, human well-being, and hence the SDGs. It intends to set a new benchmark in agricultural trade policy analysis to deliver novel solutions for the necessary sustainability transition. The EU Green Deal, as an example of a policy programme that aims at improving sustainability, represents both a challenge and an opportunity for agrifood imports for all countries, in differentiated ways. To turn this opportunity into reality the improvement of the design, governance, and implementation of trade policies and regimes are required all the way from private sector to national, EU, African and global levels.

As the core part of the MATS project, an integrated modelling framework was developed and applied to seven case studies. The impact of unsustainable practices, as well as the multidimensional gains emerging from improved sustainability have been identified and quantified. The results provide guidance for assessing the impact of sustainable agricultural trade policy at local, national, regional and global level, across a range of social, economic and environmental indicators. This policy brief - integrated model-based simulation and assessment of linkages with agricultural market, trade and investment dynamics summarizes the insights emerging from these modelling assessments.

Methodology

The integrated modelling framework consist of three modelling approaches: a participatory systems approach, customized quantitative systems model, and Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model. These together are used to forecast and assess the outcomes of policy intervention across sectors, economic actors, dimensions of development, over time and in space (on a map).

First, the participatory systems approach consisted of the co-creation of system maps between the case study leaders and the modelers. The identification of key indicators, their interconnections, and dynamics of change in the system analysed was based on the emerging output from the case studies. This exercise was performed for seven case studies ranging from oats and dairy production in Finland, to olive oil production in Tunisia, then extending to poultry in Ghana and soy production in Brazil.

Second, customized quantitative systems models were created for four case studies. The focus was on milk (Germany, Algeria and USA) and dairy products (Finland), poultry (Ghana) and feed (soybean) production (Brazil). Different modelling approaches were employed, including spatial models (based on GIS

maps), integrated Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) using MS Excel, and System Dynamics models using the software Vensim.

Third, a Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model was used to explore trade dynamics between countries and regions and quantify the impacts of instruments such as the carbon border adjustment measure (CBAM).

Results

Participatory systems approach

Qualitative modelling (i.e. system maps) offer insights into the dynamic interrelations across indicators, and hence on the transformative potential of policy intervention in the form of more sustainable agricultural trade policies. In this policy brief we present insights from two selected case studies.

First, in the context of **olive oil production in Tunisia**, we find that the establishment of export targets has dual consequences: on the one hand, increased production benefits farmers, particularly large and export-oriented operations, through trade but on the other hand, the production level guaranteed by the export targets results in higher water demand and competition of the use of water. This leads to water stress, especially in relation to observed climate change impacts. To address water stress, strategies include improving irrigation efficiency, adopting ecologically responsible practices, and shifting away from water-intensive monoculture practices. **Improving resource efficiency across uses, diversifying agricultural activities, optimizing the olive oil value chain, and ensuring that small-scale farms have access to export markets are proposed to offset potential declines in revenue caused by water stress. Effective decision-making for sustainability at all levels (environmental as entry point, then affecting social and economic sustainability) should account not only for agricultural water needs but for other water uses, recognizing the complex interplay that also climate dynamics generate.**

The second example focuses on **beef production, across various countries**. This case study aimed at identifying the presence of circular relations, or feedback loops that either stimulate or counter the expansion of beef production. Among the reinforcing factors that trigger expansion, access to capital is key. It supports cost reductions, improvements in labour productivity, and technology adoption. The growth of farm size itself is a strategy to create economies of scale and improve cost competitiveness. However, we find that growth creates constraints, such as the overproduction resulting in lower beef prices, growing environmental impacts, and the increasing pressure from consumers on sustainability of production and consumption. **Various intervention options, including**

stimulating technology adoption, introducing sustainability labelling, and addressing environmental concerns, are proposed to decouple production from environmental impacts, avoid the emergence of future costs (e.g. related to nutrient concentration and GHG emissions) and unlock further, sustainable growth.

Customized quantitative systems models

The use of sectoral models (i.e. models that represent impacts which arise from activities in a given sector, such as the dairy sector) allowed us to obtain quantitative results for selected case studies to complement the qualitative analysis. For instance, one case study focused on the land use changes that occurred in North Ostrobothnia (Finland) since the 2000s, as a result of the expansion of agriculture activities. The analysis indicates that **the expansion of agricultural areas led to the deterioration of ecosystem services, including carbon storage and habitat quality (declining by 3.3% and 8% respectively), and nitrogen and phosphorus exports (increasing by almost 6% and 3% respectively)**. Another example on how sectoral models allowed us to gain insights on how to shift towards sustainability comes from a case study on dairy production, covering Algeria, Germany and the USA. In the case of Algeria, we find that **in order to improve social conditions**, such as by increasing the salary level making it closer to the average income at the country level, **productivity and farm size would need to increase**. This could be realized for instance via capacity building, the use of improved practices, the production and purchase of more nutritious feed, as well as improved climate resilience. Specifically, we assume that labour costs increase (as a result of higher salary), and we estimate that -in order to offset this higher cost- milk productivity would need to increase from 3,550 kg/cow/year to 4,850 kg/cow/year (+36%) and that the average farm size would need to grow from 18 to 50 cows (2.7x increase). These changes combined would result in a higher unit production cost (1.01 USD/kg, as opposed to 0.81 USD/kg in the BAU scenario) as well as a higher revenue, leading to improved profitability overall (-0.1 USD/kg, as opposed to -0.29 USD/kg in the BAU scenario). **This increase of productivity and farm size, if applied to the existing number of farms, would allow Algeria to become self-sufficient in milk production under current market conditions.**

Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model

The assessments implemented at the sectoral, national, and sub-national level were complemented by an international trade analysis. This macro assessment was performed with a model called Computable General Equilibrium (GCE model). The findings indicate that **the implementation of a unilateral climate policy**

(i.e. the carbon pricing mechanisms of the CBAM, without technology transfer nor other forms of support) by the EU could lead to a considerable carbon leakage effect by 2030. This is because the EU's efforts to reduce emissions may be offset by increased emissions in other regions due to trade diversion effects and lower international energy prices. Further, we find that the EU's joint carbon pricing and CBAM policy may reduce its GDP by -0.2% compared to carbon pricing alone. **In Africa, energy-exporting nations could face a -0.36% GDP loss, while countries in the Horn of Africa may experience a 0.10-0.12% gain by 2030.** The policy implication from these results is that the capacity of CBAM to prevent the risk of carbon leakage and support the EU's increased ambition on climate mitigation, while ensuring WTO compatibility, is limited if foreign partners do not apply domestic carbon pricing mechanisms. On the opposite, in the case of the African regions considered in this study, domestic efforts in mitigation and the consequent exemption from CBAM application would generate both an improvement in export competitiveness towards the EU market and a reduction of carbon leakage by 6% in the case of fossil-based CO₂ emissions and by 21% when all GHGs are considered. **We find that the EU carbon policy mechanisms, to meet the targets of the Fit-for-55 plan, should include both a CBAM and efforts in forming as many climate clubs as possible, especially in Africa and other carbon-intensive regions** (with the goal to build a global commitment to carbon neutrality, originating from a stimulus towards decarbonization at country level). Additionally, by **sustaining technology transfer and the diffusion of best practices in agricultural production in less developed regions, the inclusion into a climate club** could be complemented by ad hoc support instruments to make the carbon neutrality pathway also compatible with a more inclusive and equal development transition, resulting into typical win-win solution with environmental gains followed by positive well-being achievements.

Lessons Learned

The sustainability of agricultural trade is intimately tied to the sustainability of domestic production, including social dimensions (e.g. labour standards and salary) and environmental dimensions (e.g. water availability, soil erosion). Therefore, an all-encompassing approach to sustainable agricultural production and food value chains is needed globally that considers both domestic and international dimensions. In crafting such trade and investment related policies, it is recommended to employ a dual strategy that combines provisions inducing change externally, such as the implementation of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), with domestic or local measures that promote change from within the country and relevant sectors. These internal initiatives could include training programs for farmers, wholesalers and retailers,

and widespread adoption of sustainable practices within the domestic agricultural sector, with the goal to generate co-benefits, especially across environmental and social indicators. Furthermore, internal initiatives could relate to and build upon ongoing external EU-initiatives aiming to improve governance through [due diligence directives](#) regarding negative human rights and environmental impacts, and the [EU Directive 2019/633](#) on unfair trading practices, strengthening farmers' position in the food supply chain and [tackling unfair trading practices](#).

Not new is that the economic valuation of externalities, including social and environmental impacts, emerges as a crucial instrument in driving sustainability. However, economic valuation, when seamlessly integrated with policy frameworks that can assign a market price to externalities, becomes a powerful tool for creating domestic incentives that encourage the adoption of sustainable practices. This economic incentive serves as a motivator for farmers and businesses to transition towards sustainable practices, aligning environmental and social considerations with economic interests. Hence, we propose that trade and investment policies should always be accompanied with sustainable impact assessments (SIAs) that contain economic valuation of social and environmental externalities.

Furthermore, the adoption of sustainable practices in agriculture goes beyond mere environmental stewardship. It directly influences economic viability by reducing direct, indirect, and induced costs. Sustainable practices contribute to a significant reduction in the direct, unit costs associated with production (this is the case of agriculture production, with reduced use of production inputs and a simultaneous increase in land productivity), indirect costs related to environmental and social impacts, and induced costs linked to long-term societal consequences. As a result, sustainable practices unlock the potential for scaling up agricultural operations. The scalability, in turn, facilitates the creation of synergies within the agricultural value chain, leading to increased competitiveness in the market. However, current trade rules do not enable formal differentiation between sustainable and unsustainable agricultural products which might hinder global scalability of more sustainable production. Trade rules should be modernised to allow competitive advantage of sustainable products over unsustainable products.

In essence, the use of an integrated modelling approach highlights the need for a comprehensive strategy that acknowledges the interconnectedness of domestic, EU and international factors in ensuring the sustainability of agricultural trade. A balanced approach is required, incorporating regulatory measures and economic incentives, to stimulate the widespread adoption of sustainable practices. This requires out-of-the box thinking in research, policy making, and practise. With the use of a systemic

approach, trade policies linked to food systems can generate direct, indirect and induced economic benefits that further trigger investments in social and environmental sustainability, contributing to the overall well-being of the population and resilience of the sector and the broader economy.

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Appendix

A.1 Model building procedure

A.1.1 Software installation

The preliminary step for building and running the GTAP model here developed is the installation of three software: GFortran, GEMPACK and RunDynam.

GFortran is the free and open-source GNU Fortran compiler supported by the source-code versions of GEMPACK that can be used on Windows PCs. The GFortran compiler can be downloaded from <http://www.copsmodels.com/gpgfort.htm>. The choice about which install package to be used depends on: the operating system (both 32-bit and 64-bit install packages are available); the GEMPACK version (the GFortran package to be used needs to be compatible with the GEMPACK version). In what follows, we refer to the 64-bit GFortran package "mingw-w64-gcc-6.4.0-setup.exe" compatible with the GEMPACK releases 11.2. While following the standard software installation procedure, it is recommended to use the default directory: "C:\MinGW-w64".

Before installing GEMPACK, it is also recommended to test the correct installation of GFortran as follows: save the program hello.for (can be downloaded from <http://www.copsmodels.com/gpgfort.htm>) into a temporary folder "C:\test"; access the terminal command prompt and type the following commands:

```
cd\test
C:\test>gfortvars intel64
C:\test>gfortran hello.for -o hello.exe
C:\test>hello
```

The first command changes the directory to the "C:\test" folder containing hello.for; the second command sets up the environment for the compiler; the third command compiles the program "hello.exe"; the fourth command runs the "hello.exe" program. If the GFortran compiler has been correctly installed (thus it is correctly working), the "hello.exe" program will write "Hello World" to the terminal.

Differently from the GFortran compiler, both the GEMPACK and RunDynam software require licences.

The second software to install is the General Equilibrium Modelling PACKage, namely GEMPACK, that is the suite of economic modelling software. In what follows, we refer to the GEMPACK releases 12.1 made available in December 2019

(see <https://www.copsmodels.com/gp121.htm> for further details). The standard software installation procedure can be launched by running the file “gp12.0.001-install.exe”. As remarked above, it requires a valid GEMPACK licence file (“licen.gem”) that is requested during the installation procedure. In some cases, the licence requires activation to ensure the software continues to work, in which case an additional further software (“gpactivate.exe”) is required.⁷

The GTAP model here developed is a multi-period CGE models, in which results are computed one-period-at-a-time, hence the third required software is RunDynam. RunDynam, a Windows interface that provides an environment tailored for carrying out forecasts and policy deviations with recursive-dynamic models. Similarly to what has been described for the GEMPACK installation, the standard software installation procedure can be launched by running the file “rundynam-install-381.exe” and, also in this case, a valid RunDynam licence file (“licen.rdn”) is requested during the installation procedure.

A.1.2 Building aggregation with FlexAgg model

FlexAgg is a command-line aggregation program that uses a batch file to run a series of GEMPACK executable files to aggregate data bases from the fully disaggregated GTAP Data Base. The data required to run the model here described results from merging different GTAP databases with 2014 reference year (further enriched with additional information for better representing trade, energy and climate dynamics). The GTAP databases used are: GTAP10, GDyn, GTAP-Power and GTAP-E. Please refer to the following section (2. Model database) for a detailed description of each database. In what follows, it is described the general method to map the fully disaggregated GTAP Data Base into the desired number of regional, sectoral and endowment grouping.

Each GTAP database is associated to: a FlexAgg utility folder and a text file describing the aggregation of the model, i.e., commodity, regions and endowment aggregation mapping.

The general procedure consists of the following steps (to be repeated for each of the databases). The first step is the definition of the aggregation mapping in the text file (e.g., “agg_GDynEP.txt”). This file needs to be located in the corresponding FlexAgg folder (e.g., “flexagg10”), which in turns needs to be in C (hence the path to access the aggregation text file should be: “C:\flexagg10\agg_ GDynEP.txt”). The second step involves the creation of a folder containing all data, set and

⁷ A general description of the issue can be found here <https://www.copsmodels.com/gpactivation.htm> and refer to <https://www.copsmodels.com/pdf/activation.pdf> for technical details.

parameters in accordance with the aggregation defined. In order to perform this step, it is required to access the terminal command prompt and type the following commands:

```
C:\ cd flexagg10
data-agg agg_GDynEP
```

The first command changes the directory to the targeted FlexAgg folder; the second command run the FlexAgg program and automatically creates a folder (named "agg_GDynEP" that will be located in C) with data, set and parameters coherent with the aggregation scheme in the text file (notice that among the files created, the ones required for running the final model are: gdset.har, gddat.har, gdpar.har and gdpextra.har). Table 33 reports the specific command to run for each GTAP database to be aggregated.

Table 33 - Commands to run for specific GTAP database

Model database	Change directory path	Run FlexAgg aggregation
GTAP10 database	cd\flexagg10Y14	data-agg agg_GDYnEP_dyn14
GDyn	cd\GDYNflexagg10A_Y14	data-agg agg_DGTRADE_dyn14
GTAP-E	cd\flexagg10E14	data-agg agg_DGTRADE_ene
GTAP-Power	cd\flexagg10Power14	data-agg agg_DGTRADE_power

Two further details need to be noticed. First, while the fully disaggregated GTAP10, GDyn and GTAP-E databases share the same number of regions and sectors (141 countries/regions and 65 sectors, among which only one electricity sector), GTAP-Power is an electricity-detailed extension that splits the electricity sectors in 12 sub-sectors (i.e., transmission and distribution, seven base load technologies and four peak load technologies) resulting in 141 countries/regions and 76 sectors. Hence, based on the GTAP-Power database, the reference aggregated sector mapping distinguishes between electricity from fossil fuels and from renewable energy. Accordingly, the final model uses the aggregated version of the GTAP-Power database as reference, integrated with data and parameters from the other versions that have been adapted to match the exact sectoral dimension as detailed in the next sections.

As second and related issue, a change in the FlexAgg command for GTAP-Power has been introduced in order to integrate in the model also the non-CO2 emissions. Specifically, in the FlexAgg tab file we defined the command for computing emissions on the basis of the traded commodities set (trad_comm) instead of the set of the commodities subject to carbon tax (ctax_comm). By running the modified GTAP-Power FlexAgg program on the basis of a har emission file that includes also non-CO2 emissions (i.e., "gsdemiss_cbam_ghg.har"), we directly obtain the aggregated emissions in har file compatible with the GDynE

version that also includes the emissions associated to the chemical sector without changing the definition commodities subject to carbon tax (i.e., coal, oil, gas and oil products). The model aggregation including non-CO2 emissions then relies on the same `gdset.har` and `gdpextra.har` as the version without non-CO2 emissions, while it requires different `har` files for data and standard parameters (i.e., `gddat1.har` and `gdpar1.har`).

A.1.3 Composition of the `dat` file

The file containing the required base data for running the model is based on the `dat` file produced by the GTAP-Power aggregation procedure, integrated as follows. The following headers defined over the regional set need to be imported from the `gddat.har` file obtained from the aggregation of the GDyn version as in Table 34:

Table 34 - Header to be imported in `gddat.har` from the GDyn version

Header	Dimension	Coeff	Name
KHAT	REG	CKHAT	Normal growth rate of Capital
YHAT	REG	CYHAT	Normal growth rate of Income
RRGE	REG	CRRGE	Expected Gross Rate of return
RRGT	REG	CRRGT	Target Gross Rate of Return
YQHT	REG	CYQHT	Income earned on household equity located in the trust
YQTF	REG	CYQTF	Income earned on equity owned by the trust in Domestic firms
YQHF	REG	CYQHF	Income earned on household equity located in domestic firms

In addition to the `har` files described above, the aggregation of the GTAP-Power version also generates a file containing CO2 emissions associated to use and consumption of fossil fuels expressed in Mt CO2 ("`gsdgemiss.har`"). Hence, all headers from the file "`gsdgemiss.har`" have been imported in the `dat` file. CO2 emissions are associated only to coal, oil, gas and oil products, but the sectoral aggregation of `trad_comm` already includes the electricity sector divided between fossil and renewable. Since the headers names are different from the ones in the `tablo` file used for the simulation, these have to be renamed according to Table 35.

Table 35 - Name changes to headers related to CO2 emission for the GDynE version

Old Header	New Header	Dimension	Coeff	Name
n.a.	FC	4 length 12		Set FUEL_COMM
MDF	CODF	TRAD_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	CCODF	Emissions from intermediate usage of domestic product
MIF	COIF	TRAD_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	CCOIF	Emissions from intermediate usage of imports
MDG	CODG	TRAD_COMM*REG	CCODG	Emissions from government consumption of domestic product
MIG	COIG	TRAD_COMM*REG	CCOIG	Emissions from government consumption of imports

MDP	CODP	TRAD_COMM*REG	CCODP	Emissions from private consumption of domestic product
MIP	COIP	TRAD_COMM*REG	CCOIP	Emissions from private consumption of imports

The exe files in FlexAgg for GTAP-Power have been changed in order to run over the specification TRAD_COMM and PROD_COMM instead of EGY_COMM and PROD_COMM in order to obtain the headers for emissions that are compatible with the structure of GDynE. The FlexAgg module also contains a correction for an error in modelling the average value of emissions that had a ge 0 check range that was giving back an error.

Similarly, we import the following headers from a further har file generated by the aggregation of the GTAP-Power version ("gsdvo1e.har") that contains information about the volume of energy purchases by sector and region expressed in Mtoe. In addition, as in Table 36 we include two further variables: CVOL, as the sum of EDF, EIF, EDP, EIP, EDG and EIG by energy commodity and region (fossil fuels and the two electricity sectors); CVOC, equivalent to CVOL but defined over the traded commodities set instead of the energy commodities set (thus for all non-energy commodities the volume is equal to zero).

Table 36 - Name changes to headers related to energy volumes for the GDynE version

New Header	Dimension	Coeff	Name
EDF	EGY_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	CEDF	Volume of domestic purchases by firms
EIF	EGY_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	CEIF	Volume of import purchases by firms
EDP	EGY_COMM*REG	CEDP	Volume of domestic purchases by households
EIP	EGY_COMM*REG	CEIP	Volume of import purchases by households
EDG	EGY_COMM*REG	CEDG	Volume of domestic purchases by government
EIG	EGY_COMM*REG	CEIG	Volume of import purchases by government
EXI	EGY_COMM*REG*REG	CEXI	Volume of bilateral trade
CVOL	EGY_COMM*REG	CCVOL	Total Volume
CVOC	TRAD_COMM*REG	CVOLC	CVOL for all trade comm

Further, as in Table 37 the following headers related to purchases and imports net of carbon tax are obtained by cloning existing headers within the gddat.har of the GTAP-Power version, renaming according to the table below and adjusting the values according to the value obtained from the GTAP-E version. Since GTAP-E has a different sectoral aggregation (the renewable electricity sector is not included), after the headers have been cloned, to ensure that the original value provided by GTAP-E is associated to the correct sector, it is recommended to copy the GTAP-E value on a temporary excel file, add a row corresponding to the renewable electricity sector (according to the order in the GTAP-Power version) and then paste it in the corresponding header in the dat file. Notice that all values associated to energy commodities are equal to zero. Finally, all headers from past

model versions need to be included as in Table 38, coherently with the table file used for running the model.

In the following table we report all headers that have been derived from (or whose values have been updated with) past model versions, i.e., a dynamic energy version corrected with climate damage (Costantini et al., 2018) and with endogenous technical change in clean energy technologies (Corradini et al., 2018).

Table 37 - Cloning headers for the GDynE version

Cloned Header	New Header	Dimension	Coeff	Name
VDGA	DGNC	TRAD_COMM*REG	CDGN	Government - Domestic Purchases at Agents' Prices - Net Carbon Tax
VIGA	IGNC	TRAD_COMM*REG	CIGNC	Government - Imports at Agents' Prices- Net Carbon Tax
VDPA	DPNC	TRAD_COMM*REG	CDPNC	Private Households - Domestic Purchases at Agents' Prices- Net Carbon Tax
VIPA	IPNC	TRAD_COMM*REG	CIPNC	Private Households - Imports at Agents' Prices- Net Carbon Tax
VDFA	DFNC	TRAD_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	CDFNC	Intermediates - Firms' Domestic Purchases at Agents' Prices- Net Carbon Tax
VIFA	IFNC	TRAD_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	CIFNC	Intermediates - Firms' Imports at Agents' Prices- Net Carbon Tax

Table 38 - Headers to be imported in dat from old versions to be compatible with the table in GDynE

Header	Dimension	Coeff	Name
RFLX	REG	RFLX	Coefficient for changing rigidity of firms
LKT	REG	LKHAT	Coefficient for changing speed of adjustment normal rate of growth
LROR	REG	LROR	Coefficient for changing speed of adjustment normal rate of return
RGF	REG	RGF	Coefficient for changing rigidity of firms
RGH	REG	RGH	Coefficient for changing rigidity of households
Endogenous technical change in clean energy technologies			
GFM	1	GFM	Share to be shocked for world carbon fund quota to mitigation costs
GFA	1	GFA	Share to be shocked for world carbon fund quota to adaptation costs
SHA	FIRM_COM*PROD_COMM*REG	SHA	Parameter to change share of world carbon fund to factor augmenting technical change
SHAS	REG	SHARS	Parameter to change share of world carbon fund to RD in renewables
SHF	REG	SHF	Parameter to change share of contribution from world carbon fund
SHT	REG	SHT	Parameter to change share of contribution to world carbon fund
SHR	REG	SHR	Parameter to change share of contribution from world carbon fund to RD
SHWS	PROD_COMM*REG	SHAWS	Parameter to change elasticity of substitution in capital-energy re
EFL	PROD_COMM*REG	EFL	Parameter to change elasticity of substitution in energy nest
EFM	PROD_COMM*REG	EFM	Parameter to change elasticity of substitution in capital-energy

SHAH	REG	SHARH	Parameter to change share of contribution from CWTRFD to EE in building
HASH	ENY_PCOMM*REG	SHAFSH	Parameter to change elasticity of technical change to EE in household
ELF	PROD_COMM*REG	ELF	Parameter to change elasticity of substitution in electricity sub-nest
Dynamic energy version corrected with climate damage			
WHCT	1	InitGCF	Initial value of GCF independent from financing mech
STCO	1	StockofCO2	Stock of CO2 in Mton equivalent to PPM
CCM	1	CCM	Average climate change cost, world level MlnUSD per MtonCO2 Stock
VULN	REG	VULN	Parameter to calculate vulnerability to climate change
CCR	REG	CCR	Value of cost of climate change at regional level
Additional header included in the development of the present model version			
COIH	TRAD_COMM*REG	COIH	Coefficient to shock COIH for change in carbon intensity households
COI	TRAD_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	COI	Coefficient to shock COIN for change in carbon intensity of firms

A.1.4 Composition of the par file

The variables in the `gdpar.har` file contains the behavioural parameters. As for the base data, also in this case the original file obtained from the aggregation of the GTAP-Power version needs to be integrated with additional headers from the other GTAP versions as in Table 39. Firstly, from the GTAP-E aggregation the following coefficient regulating the substitution possibilities in the energy nests need to be imported.⁸ The parameters defined over the regional set, assume the same value for all regions. The parameters defined over the regional and `prod_comm` sets need to be adapted according to the sectoral aggregation of the GTAP-Power version that includes the additional sector of electricity produced from renewable (it is recommend following the same procedure described for the headers related to purchases and imports net of carbon tax). In these cases, the value for the renewable electricity is set equal to the fossil electricity sector, with the only exception of the coefficient `ELFKEN` (equal to 0.38 for fossil electricity and 0.80 for renewable electricity sector). The CDE parameters (regulating the private household demands according to constant difference of elasticities functional form specification) `SUBP` and `INCP` are equivalent to `SUB1` and `INC1` from the GTAP-Power par file, but are defined over the `up_comm` set (see section 1.6 for further details). The coefficients `TRBL` and `MAPB` are required to define regions subject to carbon pricing and to distinguish between domestic carbon tax and international emission trading.

⁸ Since some of the parameters need to be redefined according to the aggregation of the GTAP-Power version, it is recommended to import the sets over which the parameters are defined from the `gdset.har` file.

As for the base data, all parameters from past model versions have included, coherently with the `tablo` file used for running the model and are reported in Table 40.

There are three additional parameters that have been included while developing the present model version, with the purpose of distributing the effect of calibration of emissions on firms and households in the baseline.

Finally, values for the `ESUBD` and `ESUBM` parameters have been updated according to `CEPII`, while `ESBT`, `ESBM` and `ESUBVA` according to previous version of the model.

Table 39 - Headers to be imported in par from old versions to be compatible with the `tablo` in `GDynE`

Header	Dimension	Coeff	Name
EGEN	REG	ELGENY	Elasticity of substitution in gov. energy sub-consumption
EGNN	REG	ELGNENY	Elasticity of substitution in gov. non-energy sub-consumption
EGUG	REG	ELGUG	Elasticity of substitution in the top of Government consumption nest
EPEN	REG	ELPENY	Elasticity of substitution in household's energy sub-consumption
EFEN	PROD_COMM*REG	ELFENY	Elasticity of substitution in energy sub-production
EFKE	PROD_COMM*REG	ELFKEN	Elasticity of substitution in capital-energy sub-production
EFNC	PROD_COMM*REG	ELFNCOAL	Elasticity of substitution in non-coal energy sub-production
EFNL	PROD_COMM*REG	ELFNELY	Elasticity of substitution in non-electricity energy sub-production
EFVE	PROD_COMM*REG	ELFVAEN	Elasticity of substitution in value-added- energy sub-production
SUBP	UP_COMM*REG	SUBPAR	CDE substitution parameter
INCP	UP_COMM*REG	INCPAR	CDE expansion parameter
TRBL	33 length 12		Set <code>TR_BLOCK</code> emissions trading blocs
MAPB	33 length 12		Mapping <code>REGTOBLOC</code> from <code>REG</code> to <code>TRBL</code>

Table 40 - Elasticity of substitution headers and related shock variables

Header	Dimension	Coeff	Name
EFEL	PROD_COMM*REG	ELFELY	Elasticity of substitution in electricity energy sub-production
SHAW	PROD_COMM*REG	SHAW	Changes elasticity of substitution in capital-energy renewables
DIF	REG*PROD_COMM	DIFF	Productivity differential (factor productivity growth differential among energy commodities)
DIFF	FIRM_COM*PROD_COMM*REG	DIFF1	Productivity differential for endowment (non-accumulable endowment productivity growth differential)
DF2C	FIRM_COM*PROD_COMM*REG	DIFFc	Productivity for energy commodities in quantity (QF)
Endogenous technical change in clean energy technologies			
SHCT	REG	SHCT	Share of contribution to world carbon fund
SHCF	REG	SHCF	Share of contribution from world carbon fund
SHAR	REG	SHAR	Share of world carbon fund to RD in renewables
SHRD	REG	SHRD	Share of world carbon fund not to RD (e.g., to EE)
SHAF	FIRM_COM*PROD_COMM*REG	SHAF	Elasticity for factor augmenting technical change from world carbon fund

HARH	REG	SHARSH	Parameter to change share of contribution from CWTRFD to EE in building
SHHH	ENY_PCOMM*REG	SHAFH	Parameter to change elasticity of technical change EE in household
CONC	TRAD_COMM*REG	CONC	Consumption quota differential
New parameters to distribute efficiency between firms and households for emission calibration in baseline case			
CVOC	TRAD_COMM*REG	CVOLc	Parameter to calibrate effirm in BAU
COIP	TRAD_COMM*REG	COIP	Parameter to change COIP in carbon intensity of households
COIN	TRAD_COMM*PROD_COMM*REG	COIN	Parameter to change carbon intensity for firms

A.1.5 Composition of the parextra file

The variables in the `gdpextra.har` file contains the special parameters regulating the dynamic features of the model. They are all generated in the aggregation of the GDyn model version and the `parextra.har` file just needs to be copied in the final folder of the model together with the rest of the `har` files. The values of these dynamic parameters have been updated according to past model versions and in accordance with the GTAP community suggestions obtained in several years of scientific exchanges. This is strongly recommended when working on the last `tablo` version 3.6 of GDyn as closures are changed and the original dynamic parameters bring to optimization errors very likely.

A.1.6 Composition of the set file

The `gdset.har` file contains all mapping information required to run the model according to the equations in the `tablo` file. Besides the sets automatically generated from the GTAP-Power aggregation procedure, the sets in Table 41 need to be added.

Table 41 - Energy commodity aggregation

Header	Dimension	Name	Sectors
FC	4 length 12	Set FUEL_COMM	Coil, oil, gas, oil products
ENY	6 length 8	Set ENY_PCOMM Energy commodities households	FUEL_COMM + ely_rw +ely_f
EGY	6 length 8	Set EGY_COMM Energy commodities	FUEL_COMM + ely_rw +ely_f
HF	47 length 8	Set FIRM_COM	Endowments + trad_comm + vaen+ ken + eny+ ely+ nely + ncoal
H10	37 length 8	Set PROD_COMM	TRAD_COMM + CGDS
ELY	2 length 6	Set ELY_COMM Electricity commodities	ely_rw +ely_f
SUP	31 length 8	Set UP_COMM	TRAD_COMM with ENY_PCOMM aggregated in one sector (eny)

A.2 Model database and settings

The original databases used for building a GDyn version that includes combustion-based CO₂ emissions, non-CO₂ emissions and renewable sources for the production of electricity are: GTAP10 for all base information of input-output elements of a GTAP-based model in FlexAgg mode; GDyn database for all inputs required to transform the model from a static to a dynamic version; GTAP-E for all information on the linkages between the energy sector and the related combustion-based CO₂ emissions associated to the use of fossil fuels for energy purposes; GTAP-Power for information about renewable energy sources in electricity production; GTAP-NCO₂ for GHG emissions different from CO₂ associated to the use of energy commodities and additional emissions associated to the production process including agriculture and livestock activities. All input files are included in the folder "Model database" while commands for aggregation are in the folder "Aggregation".

A.2.1 GTAP10

The GTAP Data Base is a consistent representation of the world economy for a pre-determined reference year. Underlying the data base there are several data sources, including among others: national input-output (IO) tables, trade, macroeconomic, energy and protection data. The underlying input-output tables are heterogeneous in sources, methodology, base years, and sectoral detail, thus for achieving consistency, substantial efforts are made to make the disparate sources comparable. For these reasons, the objective of the GTAP Data Base is not to provide I-O tables, but to facilitate the operation of economic simulation models ensuring users a consistent set of economic facts. Some users interested in particular Social Accounting Matrices (SAMs) use utilities written by researchers in the network to extract them. Users building IO tables based on this information do that under their own risk, and are assumed to understand the limitations imposed by the process of data base construction. The data in the GTAP Data Base accurately depicts the magnitudes of economic variables, but they are presented in terms of the aggregates that serve CGE modelling. The total number of countries and regions is 141 and the number of sectors is 65, with a substantial increase in the disaggregation of the service sector. For a complete description of all features in GTAP10 refer to Aguiar et al. (2019).

The name of the folder with GTAP10 database shaped in FlexAgg utility is "flexagg10Y14" and the text file for aggregation of the model for GDynEP is "agg_GDynEP_dyn14.txt".

A.2.2 GDyn

The GDyn Model builds on the GTAP Data Base augmented with foreign income data and allows dynamic analysis to be undertaken without imposing severe limitations on the model size. The data aggregated by this program is based on the GTAP10 supplemented with additional data on income payments and convergence parameters.

The total number of countries and regions is 141 and the number of sectors is 65, with a substantial increase in the disaggregation of the service sector. For a complete description of all features in GDyn database refer to Ianchovichina and Walmsley (2012).

The name of the folder with GDyn database shaped in FlexAgg utility is "GDYNflexagg10A_Y14" and the text file for aggregation of the model for DGTRADE is "agg_GDYNep_dyn14.txt". The version on which the table is built is GDyn v3.6 that includes corrections to avoid zero divide issues.

A.2.3 GTAP-E

The GTAP-E Data Base provides carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions data distinguished by fuel and by user for each of the 141 countries/regions and the 65 sectors in the GTAP10 Data Base. GTAP-E data is based on: GTAP 10 and extended energy balances compiled by the International Energy Agency (IEA). A FlexAgg distribution and GTAPAgg2 packages for each of the reference years are available. For a complete description of all features in GTAP-E database refer to McDougall and Golub (2009).

The name of the folder with GTAP-E database associated to the GTAP10 shaped in FlexAgg utility is "flexagg10E14" and the text file for aggregation of the model for DGTRADE is "agg_GDYNep_ene.txt".

A.2.4 GTAP-Power

Electricity-detailed extension ('ely' sector in GTAP disaggregated into: transmission and distribution, seven base load technologies (nuclear, coal, gas, hydroelectric, oil, wind and other power technologies), and four peak load technologies (gas, oil, hydroelectric, and solar) for 2014 is detailed in GTAP-Power database. This is an electricity-detailed extension of the GTAP Data Base. These new sectors are combined with the original GTAP sectors resulting in a data base with 76 sectors and 141 regions. The original description of GTAP-Power is provided in Peters (2016).

More recently, Chepeliev (2020) provided an updated version of the methodology. Changes introduced to the GTAP-Power database construction process consist in a different way with which output of the electricity and heat generation sector has been split using electricity generation data together with heat generation volumes to provide a more representative sectoral split and better concordance with GTAP sectoral definitions. Second, data on country and year-specific shares of transformation and distribution costs in electricity tariff for 80 countries are introduced.

The name of the folder with GTAP-Power database associated to the GTAP10 shaped in FlexAgg utility is "flexagg10Power14" and the text file for aggregation of the model for DGTRADE is "agg_GDynEP_power.txt".

A.2.5 GTAP-NCO2

The GTAP-NCO2_V10a database compatible with the GTAP10 database version is based on the methodology developed by Irfanoglu and van der Mensbrugge (2016). The database provides emissions for 24 non-CO2 emissions categories with 119 unique emissions subcategories for 244 countries. Emissions by region and economic sector, as well as emissions driver, for three major non-CO2 gases (or groups of gases) are provided, CH₄, N₂O, and the group of fluorinated gases (F-gases), including CF₄, HFCs, and SF₆. Emissions come from three emissions drivers: consumption (by consumers and firms), endowment use (land and capital), and output.

With respect to the emissions associated to consumption by firms and households the original har file has been transformed in order to be compatible with the structure of CO2 emissions used in GTAP-Power with 76 sectors. With the excel file "GHG_transf.xlsx" we have first computed the share of emissions associated to imported and domestic inputs according to the shares obtained by imported and domestic CO2 emissions for coal, oil, gas, p_c and gdt sectors. For the chm sector, we have computed the share of VIFM and VDFM on total intermediate use of chm input and the associated the share to the value of emissions. For non-CO2 emissions associated to the "ely" sector in the original database, we have associated the related non-CO2 emissions based on the share of emissions for the ely sector in Power for combustion-based CO2 emissions.

The new "gsdemiss_cbam.har" file contains the sum of combustion-based CO2 emissions and non-CO2 emissions associated to the use of energy inputs plus the chemical sector. Thanks to the changes in flexagg command for GTAP-Power, by computing emissions on the basis of trad_comm instead of ctax_comm it is possible to add the emissions associated to the chm sector without changing the definition of ctax_comm and at the same time obtaining emissions in har file

compatible with the GDynE version. When making the model version with aggregation, it is necessary to substitute in the flexagg folder the “gsdemiss.har” file with the new “gsdemiss_cbam.har” file. An additional emissions file is then computed to add GHG emissions from output and endowment and named “gsdemiss_cbam_ghg.har” that is used for simulations including all GHGs.

A.2.6 Region and sector aggregation

The aggregation into regions, sectors, and endowments is detailed in Table 42, Table 43, Table 44, respectively. The aggregation is available in a compact excel format in the file `agg_GDynEP` and in txt format for three different versions of flexagg database: `agg_GDynEP_dyn14.txt` is valid for GTAP10 and the dynamic version; `agg_GDynEP_ene.txt` is valid for GTAP-E, `agg_GDynEP_power.txt` is valid for GTAP-Power.

Table 42 - Regions aggregates in GDynEP with code details

No	Model code	Description	GTAP code region
1	AFEnex	Africa North energy exporters	egy, xnf
2	AFNorth	Africa North rest	mar, tun
3	AFWest	Africa West	ben, bfa, civ, cmr, gha, gin, nga, sen, tgo, xcf, xwf
4	AFCentr	Africa Central	bwa, mdg, moz, mus, nam, tza, zmb, zwe, xac, xsc
5	AFHorn	Africa Horn	eth, ken, mwi, rwa, uga, xec
6	SouthAfrica	South Africa	zaf
7	ASEnex	Middle East and Asia energy exporters	are, bhr, irn, kaz, kwt, omn, qat, sau
8	ASCentr	Asia Central	arm, aze, geo, isr, jor, kgz, mng, npl, pak, tjk, xsa, xsu, xws
9	ASSouth	Asia South	bgd, brn, khm, lao, lka, sgp, tha, twm, vnm, xea, xse
10	China	China	chn, hkg
11	India	India	ind
12	Indonesia	Indonesia	idn
13	Japan	Japan	jpn
14	Malaysia	Malaysia	mys
15	Philippines	Philippines	phl
16	SKorea	South Korea	kor
17	Australia	Australia	aus, xoc
18	NewZealand	New Zealand	nzl
19	EFTA	EFTA countries	che, nor, xef
20	EU27	European Union members	aut, bel, bgr, cyp, cze, deu, dnk, esp, est, fin, fra, grc, hrv, hun, irl, ita, ltu, lux, lva, mlt, nld, pol, prt, rou, svk, svn, swe
21	UK	UK	gbr
22	EurRest	Rest of Europe	alb, blr, ukr, xee, xer
23	Russia	Russian Federation	rus
24	Turkey	Turkey	tur
25	Canada	Canada	can, xtw
26	USA	USA	usa, xna
27	Mexico	Mexico	mex
28	Brazil	Brazil	bra
29	Andean	Andean countries	bol, chl, per

30	LAEnex	Latin America energy exporters	col, ecu, ven
31	LARest	Latin America rest	cri, dom, gtm, hnd, jam, nic, pan, pri, slv, tto, xca, xcb, xsm
32	Mercosur	Rest of Mercosur	arg, pry, ury

Table 43 - Sectors aggregates in GDynEP with code details

No	Model code	Description	GTAP sector code
1	rice	Rice	pdr, pcr
2	cer	Cereal grains	wht, gro
3	o_prim	Other primary	osd, pfb, ocr, wol
4	veg	Vegetable and fruit	v_f
5	cat	Cattle	ctl
6	liv	Other livestock	oap
7	r_meat	Rumin meat	cmt
8	o_meat	Other meat	omt
9	fish	Fishery	fsh
10	dai	Dairy	rmk, mil
11	bev_t	Beverages and tobacco	b_t
12	food	Processed food	vol, ofd
13	sug	Sugar	c_b, sgr
14	tex	Textile	tex, wap, lea
15	pap	Paper and publishing	ppp
16	wood	Wood	frs, lum
17	chem	Chemical	chm
18	plas	Plastics and rubber	rpp
19	phar	Pharmaceutics	bph
20	min	Mineral	nmm, oxt
21	mot	Motor veichles	mvh
22	tr_eq	Transport equipment	otn
23	ect_eq	Electronics and electronic equipment	ele
24	elect	Electrical equipment	eeq
25	metal	Metal product	fmp
26	mach	Machinery	ome
27	fer	Ferrous metal	i_s, nfm
28	o_man	Other manufacturing	omf
29	coal	Coal	coa
30	oil	Oil crude	oil
31	gas	Natural gas and LNG	gas, gdt
32	ely_f	Electricity from fossil fuels	CoalBL, GasBL, OilBL, OilP, GasP
33	ely_n	Electricity from nuclear	NuclearBL
34	ely_rw	Electricity from renewables	HydroBL, HydroP, OtherBL, SolarP, WindBL
35	oil_p	Oil products	p_c
36	r_transp	Road and railway transport	otp
37	a_transp	Air transport	atp
38	w_transp	Water transport	wtp
39	serv1	Service private	TnD, ofi, ins, rsa, obs, whs, cmn, trd, cns, afs
40	serv2	Service public	ros, osg, hht, edu, wtr, dwe

Table 44 - Endowments aggregates in GDynEP with code details

No	Model code	Description	GTAP endowment code
1	Land	Land	Land
2	SkLab	Skilled labour force	tech_aspros, off_mgr_pros

3	UnSkLab	Unskilled labour force	service_shop
4	Capital	Capital	Capital
5	NatRes	Natural resources	NatlRes

A.2.7 Scenario command details

The details for each simulation are saved into the model folder with all results for each scenario as reported in Table 45 – Command details for scenario replication. The information about the details is provided where the name of the simulation is assigned to one ds1 type file dedicated to each scenario. For scenarios applied to CO2-eq emissions related to energy input only, there is a specific `tab1o` file named `cbam_nocoin_ge.tab` where the sectors under the carbon pricing system are described in line 402 as:

```
402 Set CTAX_COMM # commodities subject to carbon tax #
403 (coal, oil, gas, oil_pcts, chem);
404 Subset CTAX_COMM is subset of TRAD_COMM;
```

For scenarios applied to all GHG emissions related also to outputs and endowments, there is a specific `tab1o` file named `cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab` where the sectors under the carbon pricing system are described in line 402 as:

```
402 Set CTAX_COMM # commodities subject to carbon tax #
403 (rice, cer, o_prim, veg, cat, liv, r_meat, o_meat, dai, bev_t, food,
404 sug, tex, pap, wood, chem, plas, phar, min, mot, tr_eq, ect_eq, elect,
405 metal, mach, fer, o_man, coal, oil, gas, oil_pcts);
406 Subset CTAX_COMM is subset of TRAD_COMM;
```

According to the different set of countries where a carbon pricing system is applied, the command file `START_EU.CMF` includes the EU only withing the set of regions applying a carbon taxation, the command file `START_CC.CMF` includes the EU and the African regions withing the set of regions applying a carbon taxation, and finally the command file `START_P.CMF` includes all region under a domestic carbon taxation regime.

With respect to the implementation of the CBAM scheme, sectors included in the tariff application are defined in the set `CBAM` in `START_EU.CMF` as:

```
xset CBAM (rice, cer, o_prim, veg, cat, liv, r_meat, o_meat, dai, bev_t, food,
sug, tex, pap, wood, chem, plas, phar, min, mot, tr_eq, ect_eq, elect, metal,
mach, fer, o_man);
xsubset CBAM is subset of TRAD_COMM;
```

while countries subject to the tariff are defined in the set `NOPA` as:

```
xset NOPA (AFEnex, AFNorth, AFWest, AFCentr, AFHorn, SouthAfrica, ASEnex,
```

ASCentr, ASSouth, China, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, SKorea, Australia, NewZealand, EFTA, UK, EurRest, Russia, Turkey, Canada, USA, Mexico, Brazil, Andean, LAEnex, LARest, Mercosur);
xsubset NOPA is subset of REG;

Sectors that are excluded from the CBAM scheme in this simulation set are: fisheries (because in the original GTAP database this sector is not associated to CO2 emissions); services (since the carbon content is more difficult to be computed and they are still completely excluded from any CBAM setting rule at the EU level); and fossil fuels products since they are already subject to taxation as carbon pricing is associated to the carbon emissions related to both domestic and external inputs.

In order to simulate the Africa-EU climate club in the command file START_CC.CMF countries subject to the tariff are defined in the set **NOPA** as:

xset NOPA (ASEnex, ASCentr, ASSouth, China, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, SKorea, Australia, NewZealand, EFTA, UK, EurRest, Russia, Turkey, Canada, USA, Mexico, Brazil, Andean, LAEnex, LARest, Mercosur);
xsubset NOPA is subset of REG;

In order to simulate the additional efforts in labour, soil, and natural resources productivity in the agricultural sectors for African regions, in the command file START_CC.CMF a subset of countries grouping African regions, a subset of sectors dedicated only to agricultural activities experiencing improvement in input productivity and a subset of endowments in which exogenous technical change with different intensities (shaped into the PSH files with policy shocks) are created as **xset SA**, **xset SAGR**, **xset SAEN**, respectively:

xset SA (AFEnex, AFNorth, AFWest, AFCentr, AFHorn, SouthAfrica);
xsubset SA is subset of REG;

xset SAGR (rice, cer, o_prim, veg, cat, liv, r_meat, o_meat, dai, sug);
xsubset SAGR is subset of PROD_COMM;

xset SAEN (Land, UnSkLab, SkLab, NatRes);
xsubset SAEN is subset of FIRM_COMM;

As an example, if the improved sustainable and labour standards in agricultural practices are assumed to drive an input-augmenting technical change in the endowments used in the agricultural sectors used for the scenario (namely land, skilled and unskilled labour force and natural resources), in the PSH files for each year starting from 2023 when the transformation into technical change is assumed

to be by 2% increase by year, the command for the shock is applied to the variable `afall` as follows:

```
tshock afall(SAEN,SAGR,SA)= uniform 2;
```

Table 45 – Command details for scenario replication

Scenario	Simulation detail	Tablo	Gddat	Comm and base	Base shock	Command shock	Policy shock
EU_PA	EU1.ds1	cbam_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_EU.CMF	POL.CLS (23_F.PSH)
EU_PA_CBAM	EU2.ds1	cbam_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_EU.CMF	POL.CLS (15_CB.PSH) (23_F.PSH)
EU_PA_CBAM_SA	EU3.ds1	cbam_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_CC.CMF	POL.CLS (15_CB.PSH) (23_F.PSH)
WLD_PA	PA1.ds1	cbam_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_P.CMF	POL.CLS (23_F1.PSH)
EU_PA_GH	EU1_GH.ds1	cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam_ghg.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_EU.CMF	POL.CLS (23_F.PSH)
EU_PA_GH_CBAM	EU2_GH.ds1	cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam_ghg.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_EU.CMF	POL.CLS (15_CB.PSH) (23_F.PSH)
EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA	EU3_GH.ds1	cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam_ghg.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_CC.CMF	POL.CLS (15_CB.PSH) (23_F.PSH)
WLD_GH_PA	PA1_GH.ds1	cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam_ghg.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_P.CMF	POL.CLS (23_F1.PSH)
EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA1	EU3_GH1.ds1	cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam_ghg.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_CC.CMF	POL.CLS (15_CB.PSH) (23_FD1.PSH)
EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA15	EU3_GH15.ds1	cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam_ghg.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_CC.CMF	POL.CLS (15_CB.PSH) (23_FD15.PSH)
EU_PA_GH_CBAM_SA2	EU3_GH2.ds1	cbam_ghg_nocoin_ge.tab	gddat_cbam_ghg.har	START.CMF	BASB.CLS	START_CC.CMF	POL.CLS (15_CB.PSH) (23_FD2.PSH)